

**PROPOSED INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT DESIGN FOR UMULERI, ANAMBRA
STATE.**

(ENHANCING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN AIRPORT TERMINAL BUILDINGS)

BY

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MATRIC NO. AAU/SPS/FES/ARC/17/MS/03390

B.SC. (EKPOMA)

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**A THESIS IN THE DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE, SUBMITTED TO THE
SCHOOL OF POSTGRADUATE STUDIES, IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF THE DEGREE OF MASTER OF SCIENCE IN
ARCHITECTURE, AMBROSE ALLI UNIVERSITY, EKPOMA, EDO STATE NIGERIA.**

JANUARY, 2021

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this study was carried out by ABU ITIOKHAIRWO MICHAEL in the department of Architecture of the faculty of Environmental studies, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, in partial fulfilment of the requirements leading to the award of the degree of Master of Science in Architecture.

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DEDICATION.

This phase of my academic work is specially dedicated to Almighty God, maker of the heavens and the earth, my strength and inspiration.

Also to my parents, Mr. & Mrs. S. T. Abu for their support, prayers and sacrifices.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Listing down all names would almost mean writing an entire chapter. But then, I cannot resist naming a few.

An invaluable debt of gratitude goes to my parents, Mr. & Mrs. S. T. Abu, for their financial, moral and particularly parental guidance and support, nothing in my life would be possible without them. My appreciation also goes to my beloved siblings Pastor. Irene, Dr. Nelly, Engr. Samuel, Barr. Jennifer, Oseremen, and Uwaifoh for their love and moral support they rendered all through the course of my research work.

I am also grateful to all lecturers in the Department of Architecture for impacting their knowledge in teaching and tutoring me especially ARC. DR. M. E. O. OMATSONE (*fnia*) for his constructive criticism, immeasurable guidance, encouragements, tolerance, good disposition, invaluable assistance, prompt attention and suggestions which were instrumental to the successful completion of this work and Arc. A. A. AKHANOLU (*mnia*) for his constant support, guidance and advice throughout my academic sojourn.

Special thanks and appreciation to the Director of Awada Concepts, Mr. Monday Akpan, his wife and the entire staff of Awada Concept, I say thank you.

Finally, to my good friends Oarhe Victor, Kalu Grace, Osegbo Brenda, Omobhude Mary, Egwabor Justice, Nwaomu Kobindi, Members of The SAGE Group; Barr. Samson Obaro, Igiehon Osaretin, Justin Otokhagua, Ighalo Afoke, Irusota Philemon, Akhigbe Sunday, Abulu Ose, Ofuya Godswill, Eimuhi Martins and Egharevba Nosa. Special thanks to Taofique Ibn' Yakub, Favour Nwantumjor, Nkenchor Bernard for his assistance towards the completion of this thesis.

All my colleagues thank You for Your Solitude, I am grateful to you all.

Above all, with Humility and a grateful heart, I appreciate the almighty God for His love, care, and protection over me, my family, lecturers, and friends and loved ones.

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ABSTRACT

Transport is one of the most important sector of any economy that hopes to grow and develop, although it is not the only prerequisite for development and growth of an economy. There exist other factors, including commerce, social and civil peace, technology, and environmental stability. In developing countries like Nigeria, air transportation has become a norm for its citizens as it is much faster, convenient and more efficient than all other means of transportation within the country.

A city's airport is a gateway to the city. An Airport gives the first impression to an international visitor, and the last impression they will have when leaving. This impression should convey our unique culture and do so through inspirational and innovative architectural forms.

An airport facilitates face to face conversations, which is important to generating innovations, attracting and retaining cooperation with national and global ties, as well as talented people to work with them.

This thesis aims at improving the design of airport terminals to provide a more convenient environment for passengers and airport staff using energy efficiency and sustainability measures. Enhancing the comfort, convenience, and experience of air travel and shorten the time required from arrival to check-in to boarding.

The airport will not only stand as a major landmark in its location (Eastern Nigeria) but will also be an architectural masterpiece, with the best of material and finishes to depict modern architecture of today, with the use of Parametric processes and elements of Afrocentricism showing the unique

culture of its location and do so through inspirational and innovative architectural forms, as well as a major emphasis on Energy Efficiency and Circulation.

The structure would be designed for expansion for new terminals and facilities in the future.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of Study

There are several means of transportation in Nigeria, and air transportation is one of them. This mode of transportation has presently become a norm for Nigerian citizens. This is as a result of the ease of this mode of transportation, the ever-increasing road accidents that occur with the usage of land transportation and water transportation, as well as the state of insecurity and highway banditry in the country. The air system of transport provides for individuals and organizations, the opportunity to run their businesses and general activities within states and nations conveniently, and in record time

There are several airports in Nigeria, 5 of which are rated as international airports, and the others being domestic airports and airstrips (usually run by the Nigerian Airforce, and some multinational companies.). These international airports located in different states in Nigeria are not 100% functional as an international airport. A survey conducted by an aviation organization (sleeping in airports) rated Port Harcourt International Airport and Murtala Muhammed International Airport 3rd and 5th worst airport respectively. (source:<https://www.sleepinginairports.net/survey/2017-worst-airports-overall-experience.htm>)

The congestion of Murtala Muhammed International Airport and Nnamdi Azikiwe International Airport in Lagos State and Abuja respectively has contributed to their poor rating in the list of the world's worst airports, while the Port Harcourt International airport's appearance on the list is due to lack of sufficient facilities for travellers.

The need and demand of more effective international airports in Nigeria notably for the South-East Geo-Political Zone are on the rise because the poor flight activities within the region create stress and inconvenience to people of the region and therefore the country at large. The siting of an airport facility would help in the effective distribution of the traveller population and cargo capacity and thereby decongesting traffic and traveller population of the Murtala Muhammed International Airport and Nnamdi Azikiwe International Airport in Lagos State and Abuja respectively.

The design, construction and development of Anambra State international airport is important because it would not only serve the citizens of Anambra state but will also serve the citizens of the Eastern Region of Nigeria. This will create convenience for persons travelling from other countries to any part of the Eastern Region in Nigeria and vice versa. This will also encourage the re-routing of freight and cargo and thereby create ease and convenience for businessmen and traders. The state's economic and social viability would be increased and substantial job opportunities made available.

With the presence of the international markets at Onitsha, Nnewi and Eke-Awka international market at Awka, the siting of this airport would encourage and improve the transportation of goods and services to and from the state and the eastern region as a whole to other parts of the country and the world conveniently and in record time as well as reduce the cost of such goods which would have been, as a result of indirect transportation to its destination, inflated the prices or cost of such goods or services. Transportation has remained one of the most vital factors that influence the development of any given nation. The credibility of this statement has been proven over the centuries, that if one decides to examine earlier civilizations, from the time of the Early Egyptian civilization to the present civilized world, it will be discovered that a lot of

the great feat achieved during these civilizations would have been impossible without any form of transportation or the other.

Transportation is an important aspect of economic development. It represents one of the yardsticks for gauging development. The aviation industry all over the world is credited for significant influence in terms of development; that is, no meaningful development of a nation, can be birthed without major improvements in the transportation system.

Transportation has been defined in different ways with all definition bearing a sole purpose. According to Encarta Reference Library DVD 2005, transportation is defined as the movement of people and goods from one location to another. According to the American peoples' encyclopedia, transportation is the conveying of materials and persons from place to place.

Transportation is the physical movement of things such as goods, persons, information etc. from one location to another through a physical medium. As one of the critical national assets, the airport plays a major role in the nation's socio-economic growth and advancement. Throughout history, the economic wealth and military power of a people or a nation have been closely tied to efficient methods of transportation. It is a major catalyst for the development of a place. The benefits of transportation in daily activities are evident from the movement of people to the haulage of bulky goods over a seemingly insurmountable expanse of space.

Transportation can be broadly classified into three distinct groups:

1. Land Transportation
2. Water transportation
3. Air transportation.

Land transportation is the most common of the three groups of transportation and dates back to the beginning of civilization. It can be represented in various forms, which are dependent on the sophistication, stage of civilization and the development of a society or country. It can be by the use of such animals as the camels, donkeys, mules, etc or by the use of such machines as the wheelbarrows, the carts, the cars, the trains, etc.

Water transportation similarly dates back to a long time. It can be by the use of such machines as the canoe, the boat, the ship, etc. all depending on the stage of civilization and development of a society or country.

Air transportation is the transportation of passengers and cargo by aircraft and helicopters. It is a transport system that involves the movement or carriage by air of persons or goods using airplanes and helicopters. It has become the most preferred means of common carrier travelling. The Greatest efficiency and value are obtained when long distances are involved and high-value payloads are moved, although the time and cost efficiencies obtained reduces as distances travelled are decreased, air transport is often worthwhile even for relatively short distances. (oecd.org 2014).

Air transportation, of which we are most concerned about for the achievement of this thesis project can be by the use of machines such as the hot air balloons, the gliders, the airplanes/aircrafts, the helicopters, etc. all depending on the stage of civilization and development of a society or a country.

At about the 5th century BC, the first form of aircraft made was the kite. During the 19th Century, flying for pleasure and adventure with hot air balloons and gliders began and by the 20th Century, on the 17th of December, 1903, the first powered flight in a machine by the Wright brothers- Orville Wright and Wilbur Wright occurred at Kitty Hawk, North Carolina. This ushered

in the air transport age. The longest flight by Wilbur Wright which covered a distance of 260 meters (852 ft) in 59 seconds above the ground created interest and drew the attention of people to the possibility and opportunities of air travel. It brought about increased participation of the other inventors in the development of a safe aircraft that will carry people and goods from one area to another.

On the 1st of January, 1914, a group of Florida businessmen launched the first scheduled air service using an airplane. For a period of four (4) months, this air service transported a total of 1200 passengers across Tampa Bay in a two (2) seat Benoist seaplane which took about twenty (20) minutes. This was the first venture that indicated scheduled air service could be commercially viable.

During World War 1 which lasted between 1914 and 1918, roads and railroads were devastated. The war also proved the military value of airplanes and sparked a dramatic acceleration in aircraft production as there was the replacement of the surveillance hot air balloons by airplanes used as scouts. The efficiency of the airplanes in air surveillance intrigued the warring nations that they encouraged the development of faster airplanes which could be fitted with a gun to shoot down enemy surveillance airplanes. This marked the birth of the air force in wars. At the end of the war, fledgeling commercial air carriers took advantage of the ruined ground transportation system and the large surplus of aircraft and pilots and better and faster planes were produced based on researches and improvements achieved during the war. Based on these research works, it became practicable to develop larger aircraft which would be used in the transfer of people and goods from one place to another; unlike the single-seat airplanes. This marked the beginning of commercial air transportation. In later years, preceding and during the World War 2, continuous research led to the development of the jet aircraft and better commercial aircrafts like the Boeing

727, 737, 747-400, etc. as air service within Europe flourished, and by the 1930s government-sponsored airlines were operating well beyond Europe to numerous European colonies in the Middle East, Africa, Asia, and Latin America.

In 1979, the Federal Government of Nigeria approved the establishment of airports in different areas of the country. Priority was given to new states of high population densities especially where airfields were not available. These proposals were guided by the Federal Government's aim to connect all state capitals to the national capital.

The air age in Nigeria which dates back to the late forties includes recordings of the landing of aeroplanes in Nigeria. The National Carrier, Nigerian Airways, carried 233,130 International passengers and 1,352,210 Domestic passengers in 1979; with such airlines as Virgin Nigeria, Arik, Aero contractors, Bell view in the recent times in Nigeria that carried 2,124,533 International passengers and 6,222,746 Domestic passengers in 2005, 2,311,326 International passengers and 5,896,868 Domestic passengers in 2006, 2,744,151 International passengers and 5,665,693 Domestic passengers in 2007. This shows the growth of air transportation and the economic viability of air transportation in Nigerian.

This Dissertation project is an 'INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT' which is the shelter/accommodation of one of the major modes of transportation (air transportation systems), the airplane which could also be referred to as aircraft. The Airport not only houses the aircraft but also accommodates people or persons, goods to be transported from one place to another. The size of an airport is dependent on the performance characteristics and size of aircraft expected to use airport and the anticipated volume of traffic; location of the site (high altitudes require longer runways) and need to minimize nuisance. In this regard, airports are classified by runway lengths.

Therefore, an international airport requires a minimum runway length of 4000m (13000ft). The customs and immigration facilities also identify international airports

As an essential component of the air transportation system, the airport is the physical site where the modal transfer is made between air mode and land surface mode. It should provide the spaces, facilities and services appropriate for the modal transfer. The function of the airport facility is to enable aircraft to land, unload and load payload and crew, be serviced and take-off. Therefore, an airport should take into account the landing and taking-off of aircraft, the landside access by surface transport modes as well as the handling of passengers and cargo, to successfully guarantee modal transfer.

The recent trends in the airline industry as regarding the airport's role as a terminal for passengers, cargo and airlines need to be considered continuously throughout the airport design and development process. In recent years, as passenger and cargo markets have grown continuously, there have been large changes in the route structure, deregulation, privatization, computerization, congestion, delay and so on. Thus, it is required that airport designers and planners respond flexibly to the dynamic changes to provide appropriate services for passengers, cargo, and the airline industry while still managing the airport itself profitably.

Airport Design for development and construction are usually considered to be very large and capital-intensive projects. However, not a few governments have been forced in recent years to devote enormous economic resources either to the building of new Airports or the expansion of existing airports, to keep pace with the growing passenger and cargo demand. Airport development should be planned for in advance, with serious considerations given to the rate of growth in air transport demand, the availability of required capital, the integrity of the transportation system and the degree of environmental protection.

1.2. Statement of Architectural Problems.

Often times, every project has its special features and its peculiar problems, which requires original solutions that allow the integration of physical architectural development into a comprehensive framework taking into account aesthetics, economy, technological and social factors.

In Airports, these problems consist primarily of a number of items of which solutions would be proffered to that effect. They include the following:

- i. Inadequate parking facilities: For International airports, it is required that parking facilities be adequately provided for. In the course of this project, solutions to the inadequate parking facilities as well as the proximity and convenience of these parking facilities from the terminal building shall be taken into consideration.
- ii. Inadequate disability facilities: These shall also be taken into consideration and provision of facilities which would make their journey a blissful one.
- iii. Security: This is a major problem in airports as both people need to feel safe and also require optimum care and safe carriage of their baggage or luggage. This is a result of the fact that a lot of people often lose their luggage to staff/personnel inefficiency and theft also resulting from poor security.
- iv. Inadequate relaxation facilities: These are really needed in airport terminals to help the airport customers, visitors and personnel feel at home, feel relaxed and safe within the airport environment.

In the course of accomplishing this project, such problems shall be resolved in the best possible means.

1.3. Motivation for the Project.

Nigerian citizens in recent times have reverted to the constant use of air transportation systems. This mode of transportation was encouraged for reasons, such as its time economy, its convenience and its reduced rate of accident in comparison to land and water modes of transportation. This is as a result of the ever-increasing rate of in accident rates as regards land transportation and water transportation.

Anambra State in its years of existence has neither domestic nor international airport. This is most appalling as this eliminates the chances or opportunities for the convenience of inter-country air transportation occurring between other countries and Nigeria with emphasis on the eastern region.

1.4. Aim of the Study.

The aim of this study (research) is to design an energy-efficient, effective, convenient and safe air transportation terminal which will ease up and aid the movement of persons and goods from one place to another.

1.5. Objectives of the Study.

The objectives are not limited to the following, but they include:

- i. To enhance operational efficiency within passenger terminals using modern technological innovations.

- ii. To design an airport facility that will not only inspire the use of spaces and attract people to its use, but also improve the experience of airport users generally.
- iii. To design an airport terminal complex that will be an embodiment of the unity of all its required facilities.
- iv. Designing an airport terminal facility that will exhibit and display its architectural design and creativity into everyone in an unselfconscious manner.

1.6. Justification of the Study.

The current administration of Anambra State Government led by Governor Willie Obiano proposed the development of an International Airport that would be developed under the "Public-Private-Partnership" (PPP) scheme with Orient Petroleum Resources and Elite International Investments. Anambra State is a business inclined state and virtually all-important businessmen and women in Anambra travel a lot to other parts of the country or overseas for one business transaction or the other. Presently, there is a major hurdle of travelling by road to Anambra State with its attendant hazards. An airport in the State will checkmate these hazards.

Building an Airport in this state will enhance the business and economic tempo in Anambra State, Investors will have a one-stop access to the state. It would also boost tourism as well as boost the state's growth as it would not only create employment opportunities but also provide easy access of persons into the state, convenience of also accessing the international markets at Onitsha, Nnewi and Awka other environmental services available within the state as well as easy access into the eastern region.

The multiplier effect of an airport in Anambra State is simply Overwhelming.

1.7. Scope of the Project.

As large industrial complexes, airports consist primarily of:

- i. Runway and taxiing areas
- ii. Air traffic control tower
- iii. Passenger terminal
- iv. Car parks and Road system
- v. Freight depot and warehouse areas

For the architect, the passenger terminal is the main airport building and an opportunity for architectural expression. Organizationally, the terminal building is the key element within the airport estate. It is, however, just part of an integrated system, which involves a complex interaction between airline companies, airport authorities and the traveller. The reputation of an airport is, however, determined by the quality of its terminal buildings, not just as architectural imagery but in terms of customer needs.

For the purpose of this thesis project, emphasis will be given primarily to the design of the airport passenger terminal building, along with other major physical elements. This, therefore, implies that architectural details of this thesis will be of the airport terminal building and all major physical elements of the Airport.

All secondary elements of the airport such as

- i. Accommodation facilities
- ii. Conference facilities
- iii. Restaurants
- iv. Financial institutions

- v. Airline buildings
- vi. Leisure and recreational facilities

All these would be taken into account during the general site planning and will also be well integrated and related with the international airport terminal building, but not detailed as the design will be focused on the design of the airport terminal and the functional flow of the required services within the airport complex.

1.8. Research Methodology.

An architectural masterpiece shall evolve through analysis and projections based on the research methods used for the collection of data in this project. These research methods are briefly classified as follows:

- i. General study of airports.
- ii. History of aviation.
 - Worldwide.
 - Nigerian context.
- iii. Literature review: by consulting the internet and libraries for books, magazines, newspapers, journals with articles related to the project topic.
- iv. Case studies: On existing international airports within and outside the shores of Nigeria.
 - Nigerian International Airport Targeted.
 - Murtala Muhammed International Airport.
 - Nnamdi Azikiwe International Airport.
 - International Airport Targeted.

- Seymour Galapagos Airport.
 - Boston Logan International Airport.
 - Singapore Changi Airport.
 - Oslo International Airport
- v. Interviews: On employees and management staff of airports.
- vi. Observations, Analysis and Findings (Qualitative/Quantitative)
- vii. Program formulation and Analysis.
- viii. Site.
- Selection.
 - Analysis.
- ix. Design.
- Design Concept.
 - Design development.
 - Final design.
- x. Conclusion.

1.9. Definition of Terms.

In this thesis project, there are certain definitions that would be made to help explain certain words that would be used subsequently in this project and they are as follows:

i. AIRPORT

According to Encarta Reference Library, an airport has been defined as an area where civil aircraft may take off and land, especially one equipped with surfaced runways and facilities for handling passengers and cargo. Wikipedia Encyclopedia defines it as a facility where aircraft such as aeroplanes, helicopters, and blimps take off and land. As defined by Britannica Encyclopedia, is a place from which aircraft operate that usually has paved runways and maintenance facilities and often serves as a terminal.

ii. AIRPLANE

As defined by Cambridge Dictionary is a vehicle designed for air travel that has wings and one or more engines

iii. RUNWAY

As defined by Cambridge Dictionary is a long, level piece of ground with a specially prepared smooth, hard surface on which aircraft take off and land. Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English defines it as a long specially prepared hard surface like a road on which aircrafts land and take off. As defined by Wikipedia Encyclopedia, is a strip of land on an airport, on which aircraft can take off and land.

iv. TERMINAL

As defined by Cambridge Dictionary the area or building at a station, airport, or port that is used by passengers leaving or arriving by train, aircraft, or ship. As defined by Merriam-Webster Dictionary, a freight or passenger station that is central to a considerable area or serves as a junction at any point with other lines.

v. APRON

Merriam-Webster Dictionary the extensive paved part of an airport immediately adjacent to the terminal area or hangars. Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English defines it as the hard surface in an airport on which planes are turned around, loaded, unloaded, etc.

vi. HANGAR

As defined by the Encarta Dictionary, is a large building in which aircraft are kept or repaired.

As defined by Merriam- Webster Dictionary is a covered and usually enclosed area for housing and repairing aircraft.

vii. LOUNGE

As defined by Encarta Dictionary, is a room in a public building or vehicle, for example, a hotel, airport, or ship, in which people may relax or wait.

As defined by the Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, is a waiting room at an airport.

viii. AVIATION

This is an organization charged with the design, manufacture, use or operation of airplanes with airports as its key development element.

ix. CLEARWAY

As defined in the book Planning and Design of Airports, is an area beyond the runway not less than 150m (500ft) wide, centrally located about the extended centerline of the runway, and under the control of the airport authorities.

x. STOPWAY

As defined in the book Planning and Design of Airports, is an area beyond the runway, not less in width than the width of the runway, centrally located about the extended centerline of the runway, and designated by the airport authorities for the use in decelerating the aircraft during an aborted takeoff.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 GENERAL INFORMATION ON AIRPORT

An airport has been defined as an area where civil aircraft may take off and land, especially one equipped with surfaced runways and facilities for handling passengers and cargo (According to Encarta Reference Library DVD 2005). Airport can include not only the civil airports familiar to holidaymakers but also airfields (which may have few or no associated buildings) and heliports. An airport serves as a destination link that starts, continues and ends journeys. On a bigger scale, an airport plays a significant social and economic role by providing a connecting link between different communities and countries throughout the world. No other mode of transportation surpasses the aircraft in its ability to swiftly deliver passengers and cargo virtually anywhere on the planet. Even as advancements in technology have minimized the need for passengers to spend time in airports, tightening security measures have increased the time spent in these transit hubs. Concurrently, social evolution has upgraded expectation.

Recently, people now expect more out of everything in life and airports isn't an exception, it is logical for travellers to desire the same amenities found in the international wings of Lagos and Abuja airport to be present in every other airport they visit in Nigeria. Technological advancements have created a mindset in people that almost anything can be made available at any time, and at any place. This high expectation of comfort and convenience has spurred industry growth and led to the rethinking of airport passenger terminal design. Though national commonality is essential from an operational standpoint, it is equally important for air terminals to retain a welcoming sense of individuality by a sense of reference to their communities of origin. A successful airport passenger terminal design will require a functional and technologically

advanced transportation facility that is made uncommon by incorporating visual images and physical elements suggestive of the region it serves. Technological advancements have also made it now more important than ever to maintain a personal sense of place. An airport designed as an expression of the essence of the region or place, it is not only a remarkable transport facility but also a valuable civic asset.

By the nature of their purpose, airport terminals are a stressful environment. Twenty-four hours a day, thousands of air passengers race to make flights, stand in lines and queues, and have to pass through security points, shuttle from one terminal or wing of the airport to the next, and wait for their luggage from the baggage reclaim unit- all in an attempt to get somewhere else. In other words, passengers are forced to spend time at the airport. The environment in which they spend time and the activities and amenities offered to them can contribute to their sense of security, well-being and enjoyment. Therefore, it makes sense to design a facility that will help boost travellers morale and a variety of relaxation options. To achieve this, the architect must forget the traditional notion of airports filled with marginally comfortable waiting areas, overpriced gift shops and concession areas and think about what services and facilities make people happy and feel at ease. With this in mind, a user-friendly hub not only meets the required functional rigours but also be fully energy efficient, as this improves physical wellness when in an airport terminal facility, expands hospitality services to include reasonably priced retail stores with national and regional recognition, diverse restaurants and entertainment centres. This is one step towards meeting or indeed exceeding the passenger's expectations, reducing their stress and improving the airport's revenues.

It is important to also remember that passengers visit airports for one primary reason, which is to catch a plane. While the airport of the future may become a destination or community multi-use asset, its primary function must continue.

Airports facilities must be functional, energy-efficient, user-friendly, operationally efficient, cost-effective facilities that also provide a variety of attractive amenities in a unique, regionally inspired environment. Success is achieved when the design creates an environment not where people wait to catch a plane, but an environment where people want to wait to catch a plane.

2.2. HISTORICAL PREVIEW OF AIRPORTS

With the development processes of Air transportation system from airfields in the early 1910s and 1920s to the design and development of terminal buildings and runways facilities for an airport complex in the 1960s, bore the establishment of continuous domestic flights in large jets which flew once or twice a day. This greatly encouraged the growth of the air transportation system and also provided viable and convenient transportation alternatives for people who desire to move from one place to another for such reasons as the drastic reduction of transportation time (i.e. reduction of time of moving from one place to another).

2.2.1. HISTORICAL EVOLUTION

Air transport industry has become one of the world's major industries with a revenue of \$736 billion in 2017 (source: <https://www.iata.org/pressroom/pr/Pages/2016-12-08-01.aspx>). The airlines of the world have also operated at the forefront of technological progress. They exist in

the most internationally acclaimed commercial environments. They have brought every part of the world within a few hours of every other and by doing this, they have brought about a change in world trade, in business, contracts and in other methods of communication and transactions.

Throughout history, countless records have demonstrated man's fascination with flight. While the true origin of this quest to fly has long been lost, the reason behind it is quite obvious. As humans, we are hardwired with the desire to see the world, to visit the great landscapes that we have yet to lay eyes upon.

Having the ability to fly allows us to reach these places, and reach them fast. While the first untethered human flight occurred in the late 1700s, ideas and designs for man-carrying flight contraptions can be traced to as far back as 428 BC. Let's take a quick look at the past achievements that have led to the advanced aviation technologies of today.

Archaic origins

Stories of people attempting to fly can be found throughout various ancient cultures. In Greek mythology, there is the legend of Daedalus and Icarus, the father and son who created wings by combining feathers and wax. The story may have ended in tragedy, but it showed that men have always wanted to fly. Similar stories can be found in India, China and Europe.

In 852 AD, Armen Firman of Spain covered his body with feathers and created wing-like garments that he attached to his arms. He then proceeded to jump from a tower. Although his attempt was unsuccessful, the garments slowed his descent, allowing him to survive with only minor injuries.

Kites, which had been invented in China sometime in the 5th century, are known as the first aircraft made by man. Man-lifting kites were also utilized in China and Japan for military and punishment purposes. China is also credited with inventing hot air balloons (3rd century BC) and rotor wings (400 BC).

The Renaissance in Europe, from the 14th to 17th century, witnessed a creative explosion in architecture, art, music, politics and science. Famous Renaissance artist and inventor Leonardo da Vinci developed the early drafts for a rational aircraft. Among his inventions were the parachute and the aerial screw. While his ideas were not scientifically sound, they were at least reasonable.

The age of modern aviation began during the 1700s and came to embody two main categories: lighter-than-air aviation and heavier-than-air aviation.

Lighter than air aviation

This type of aviation mainly involved balloons and airships. On June 4, 1783, brothers Joseph-Michel and Jacques-Étienne Montgolfier exhibited their unmanned hot air balloon, which flew over Annonay, France. By August 27 of the same year, brothers Anne-Jean and Nicolas-Louis Robert, along with Jacques Charles, flew their unmanned hydrogen-filled balloon over Champ de Mars, Paris.

On October 19, the Montgolfier brothers sent up a manned flight with a tethered hot air balloon piloted by Giroud de Villette, Jean-Baptiste Réveillon and Jean-François Pilâtre de Rozier. Then, on November 21, the brothers launched their first untethered flight with Pilâtre de Rozier and François d'Arlandes onboard. The balloon was lifted by hot air from a wood fire and flew a total

of nine kilometres in 25 minutes. Despite having enough fuel to fly for a longer duration, the two aeronauts had to land because the firewood's embers began to burn the fabric.

Hot air balloons suffer from a disadvantage, however: lack of manoeuvrability. The invention of airships, otherwise known as dirigibles or zeppelins, solved this issue. Dirigibles derive lift from hydrogen or helium gas instead of from heat. These airships were the first to carry passengers over long distances. Perhaps the most famous was the dirigibles manufactured by German Airship Company Luftschiffbau Zeppelin GmbH. Airships are classified into three categories:

- Non-rigid – Also known as blimps, they lack a solid wood or metal framework. They basically consist of envelopes filled with gas, with a small gondola attached below.
- Semi-rigid – An airship with a solid supporting structure that only runs on the bottom part of the ship's interior.
- Rigid – These airships have a full internal framework, usually constructed from wood or some type of metal, covered with an envelope. One or more gasbags inside provide lift.

The age of lighter-than-air aviation waned with the development of better aeroplane designs. On May 6, 1937, the zeppelin Hindenburg burst into flames and crashed to the ground at Lakehurst, N.J., killing 22 crewmen, 13 passengers and a ground worker. The accident would mark the end of the airship era.

Heavier than air aviation

There had been various contenders for the title of having developed the first true heavier-than-air aircraft, and more than a little controversy surrounding the various claims. On October 9, 1890, French inventor Clément Ader made one of the first powered flights. His “flight” was only

20 centimetres above the ground but covered a total distance of 50 meters, which was quite significant at the time.

However, the official and most universally accepted date that kick-started aviation as we know it today is December 17, 1903 Orville Wright made the first successful flight, which lasted 12 seconds on an airplane which had a wingspan of 12 m (39 ft) and weighed 340 kg (750 lb), including the pilot. In the same year, the Wright was known to have made short flights for a distance of 63.5m (19.05ft) Kill Devil Hills near Kitty Hawk, North Carolina and long flights for a distance of 260 m (852 ft) in 59 sec.

Orville Wright and Wilbur Wright, though bicycle manufacturers by profession in their company Wright Cycle Company, made undisputed contribution to designing and contribution of the power-driven, heavier- than- air vehicles'.

The officially recorded flight was made by Orville Wright on the 26th of September, 1905. In the year 1908, the Wright brothers publicly exhibited their power-driven, heavier- than- air vehicles'. Attempts were made by enthusiastic inventors after this period from different parts of the world to emulate the American pioneers. In Brazil, Albert Santos- Dumont, in Paris on the 13th of September, 1906 made the first flight in Europe. On the 25th of July, 1909, Louis Blenoit flew across the English Channel, and on the 3rd of November of that same year, Henry Farman flew 232kilometers in 4 hours and 6 minutes. As from this moment onwards, progress was recorded and attempts were made to improve on the distance, altitude, size and speed of the aircraft.

The world's first scheduled passenger air service began in Florida on January 14, 1914. It operated between St. Petersburg and Tampa. Despite only lasting for four months, the flights helped pave the way for modern-day transcontinental service.

The 1920s and 1930s were a time of explosive growth in civil aviation. Revolutionary aircraft designs such as the Douglas DC-3 — a reliable all-metal passenger aeroplane — helped make air travel more accessible and comfortable for the public.

Post-World War II civil aviation.

By the end of World War II, many towns and cities had built their own airports. Civil aviation experienced rapid growth during this period, as military aircraft were repurposed as airliners or personal planes.

In 1944 the Convention on International Civil Aviation, aka the Chicago Convention, was established. The agency's goal was to standardize the efficiency, safety and consistency of all civil flights. Today that standardization has paid off in safer, more economical airliners operated by the major carriers. Europe-based Airbus, U.S.-based Boeing, Brazil-based Embraer, Russia-based United Aircraft Corporation and Canada-based Bombardier are five of the top aircraft manufacturers today.

The era of digital aviation.

With the emphasis during the modern era on adopting digital or computerized techniques, the aviation industry has really taken off. During the 1970s, computer-aided design and computer-aided manufacturing (CAD/CAM) software enabled the creation of better aircraft designs. Computer simulations have also led to the discovery of better materials for creating lighter and stronger airplanes.

Digital systems have found their way inside the modern aircraft, rendering most mechanical and analogue instruments obsolete. An example of this is the “glass cockpit”

employing LCD screens instead of the mechanical gauges and dials. Ever since the 1960s, the composite airframes have become lighter and quieter. The engines have become more competent. But the most significant lasting improvements have taken place in instrumentation and control, as we study the air transport history. The influx of solid-state electronics, the Global Positioning System, satellite communications have radically changed the cockpits of airliners. Small and powerful computers and LED displays help the pilots in navigating and viewing the terrain much more accurately, even at night or in low visibility.

As airplanes got larger and heavier, it became necessary for airports to have hard surface runways instead of the grass or gravel fields because such fields could not support the weight of heavier airplanes (a Boeing- 747 can weigh more than 800,000 pounds at take-off). Airports eventually began to offer more services for airplane operations and their increasing number of passengers. A large modern airport today has thousands of workers, accommodates tens of thousands of passengers, and loads and unloads hundreds of thousands of pound of baggage and cargo daily.

Airports may be divided into the following:

- i. Those which are public (i.e. accessible to any air travellers).
- ii. Those which are private (e.g. air- freight terminals, company airports, aeroclubs and air force bases).

Generally, these airports range from a single grass airstrip in an agricultural or rural area to the large airport serving major cities. The underlying factor that separates one airport from another depends on the type of services it provides, the airplane size it serves, the length of the runways with its complementary terminal facilities and its proximity to a dense populated area as airports

differ in size and layout depending on their function and the types of aircraft that use them, etc. Not all airports are located near towns and cities. Driving through agricultural regions, a single narrow strip of grass or pavement along the highway could indicate that there is an aerial operation based within the immediate environment. These are referred to as rural airstrips. They are not common in Nigeria but could be found in developed countries.

Several private communities can also have a small common airstrip where houses with attached hangars allow owners to taxi from the hangar to the shared runway.

Military airstrips or airports are usually restricted to military airplane usage from flight testing to military training routes. These airstrips are designed to handle rotorcraft or fixed-wing aircraft. Most of the runways of military airports can accommodate heavy, wide-bodied aircraft and have a runway length of 3000 meters to 4600 meters.

Many small communities have single airstrip airports where private and small business airplanes are based. These small community airports support general aviation flying. Most of these smaller airports do not have operating control towers. Often, these regional community airports offer facilities for training student pilots. A few of these smaller airports near remote towns and cities have limited airline services. These services usually consist of small propeller airplanes or small, regional jets that seat no more than 20-30 passengers or less such as the Cessna aircraft which seats a maximum of 30 passengers. The airline service from a small community airport can provide service to a major city airport and a regional airport, and also to a regional community airport. The regional community airports are usually larger than the small community airports, have airport control towers and have facilities for operation in conditions when visibility is poor. Commuter airlines using slightly larger jets (like the Boeing-727s) provides services from these airports to other regional community airports, regional airports, and to major city airports. Regional

airports are supported by several communities. Working together, these communities can have an airport with instrument facilities, a control tower, and airline services. These airports provide passengers and cargo services on a regular basis and support the larger passenger aircrafts.

Airports can be privately owned, owned by countries, cities or groups of cities. Some airports are owned by countries or small cities with the costs, profits and rewards being shared by the citizens of the country or city. Many of these smaller city airports have two or more runways and facilities for making instrument approaches when the weather causes ceilings and visibilities below authorized minimums.

There are three major types of airports that exist today as part of the air transportation system.

These include the following:

- i. Military airport.
- ii. General airport.
- iii. Commercial airport.

- Military airports have one or two paved runways, generally 3,000 to 4,600 m (10,000 to 15,000 ft) long. These airports are used only by military aircraft.
- General aviation airports, which cater to small civilian aircraft, are smaller than commercial airports. They are often found in rural areas or in small towns. General aviation airports have one or two runways from 900 to 1,500 m (3,000 to 5,000 ft) long. Some runways at general aviation airports are paved, but many are simply grass-covered paths. Facilities vary widely at general aviation airports, depending on the size of the airport.

- Commercial airports are used by airlines. These airports may be small or large. Small commercial airports have one or two runways from 1,800 to 2,400 m (6,000 to 8,000 ft) long and can accommodate larger aircraft than general aviation airports can. Large commercial airports serve the world's major cities. They usually have pairs of parallel runways from 3,000 to 3,700 m (10,000 to 12,000 ft) in length. Airports approved as destinations for flights

Presently, airports are classified into the following as stated below:

- i. International airport.
- ii. Principal domestic airport.
- iii. Domestic airport.
- iv. Local airport.
- v. Secondary airport.

The airport size is usually judged by the number of operations (take-offs and landings) made each day. They depend on performance characteristics and size of aircraft expected to use airport and the anticipated volume of traffic; location of the site (as higher altitudes require longer runways) and the need to minimize nuisance. For initial planning purposes, the peak hourly passenger throughput should be determined, the total arrivals and departures, and space of between 1.8m² and 2.3m² per person should be allowed. This results in an approximate gross area including offices and all support facilities for an international airport terminal. To determine the peak, the Standard Busy Rate and other factors affecting terminal planning, the following basic data will be required and these include the following:

i. Aircraft movements (passenger aircraft only):

- The number of aircraft movements.
- Aircraft types including combined types, mixed passenger and cargo.
- The number of stands per type of aircraft.
- Average and peak passenger load factors.
- The proportion of scheduled and non- scheduled, and charter flights.
- Details of general aviation (private aircrafts) if using the terminal.

ii. Passenger movements:

- Number of passenger movements.
- The proportion of arrivals, departures, transfer and transit (international and domestic).

iii. Baggage:

- The number of pieces per passenger.
- The proportion of arrivals, departures and transfer (international and domestic).

iv. Visitors:

- The number of accompanying visitors.
- The proportion of arrival and departures (international and domestic).
- The number of non-accompanying visitors (sightseers).

v. Employees:

- Number and proportion for the airport.

- Aircraft and airline operations and for concessionaries, ancillary facilities, etc.
- Proportions of males and females.

vi. Landside transportation:

- Number of passengers, visitors, employees arriving and departing by private vehicles (note ratio of owner-drivers); by public vehicles (note ratio of bus, hire car, taxi, rail transit, helicopter, etc).

Major city airports handle most national and international flights and support mainly the much larger airlines such as the Boeing 737s, 747s, and 777s respectively.

Characteristics of these major city airports include separate passenger terminals for national and international flights, two or more long runways capable of handling the 29 larger jet airlines and fully functioning airport control towers with instrument landing capabilities

2.3. AIRPORT DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

Air Travel in Nigeria commenced during World War II (1939-1945) when it became necessary to move troops and supplies fast across the country. Several airstrips were built then which were converted after the war, to Civilian use (Ileoje, 2003).

Nigerian Airways was established in October 1958 as a Joint Venture between the Nigerian Government, Elder Dempster Lines and the British Overseas Airways Corporation (BOAC). The Airways took over the operation of domestic flights from the disbanded West African Airways Corporation (WAAC) which had been operating commercial aircraft within the country since 1946 (Filani, 1983).

In 1963, the Nigerian Federal Government bought out the other shareholders and Nigeria Airways became wholly-owned by the Nigerian government. The airline has a monopoly for providing domestic air services in Nigeria. It was also the national flag carrier for international services along the West African Coast, Europe and the United States of America.

In 1976 Nigeria Airways operated a fleet of nineteen aircraft consisting of two each of Boeings 707 and 737 and one DC 10-30 aircraft used mainly for international flights. There were Seven F.28 Jets and Seven Folder F.27 propeller aircrafts used mainly on domestic routes (Filani, 1983). There were also other major international airlines which operate flights to Nigeria, thereby linking Nigeria with the World's major socio-economic and political centres. Within Nigeria itself, several charter companies operate additional flight in small aircraft from Lagos to the main economic centres in the Southern parts of the country. The Nigerian Federal Government realizing the role of air transport in the nation's development made significant attempts to develop the country's air transport system. The most gigantic was the 1975-1980 Airport development programme in which the Murtala Mohammed airport complex was about N240 million (Filani, 1983). Six other airports in Kano, Ilorin, Kaduna, Sokoto, Port Harcourt and Maiduguri were developed to accommodate the largest intercontinental aircraft. Apart from these airports development programme the Federal Government also intensifies manpower development in the aviation industry. The Nigerian Civil Aviation Training Centres provide a substantial number of trained air personnel. This is in the areas of piloting, maintenance engineers, air traffic controllers, aeronautics teleprompter operators and communications personnel. These personnels were reinforced with those from the Nigerian College of Aviation Technology, Zaria.

The responsibility to handle and manage the Nigerian airports was under the Nigerian Airports Authority (NAA), now known as the Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria (FAAN), was

as established in the year 1976. This body handled the operation of two (2) classes of airports. These include the long-distance flight airports and the short and medium-haul flights airports. About 30 major airports exist in Nigeria and out of them; about 15 are connected with scheduled services. Provisions for an emergency landing and other landing fields have been maintained either publicly or privately.

The Murtala Muhammed International airport located at Lagos was designed to handle present and future wide-body aircrafts which operate under international flights. The Kano International airport was designed to serve as a traveller's alternative to the Lagos airport. In terms of capacity and the intensity of the activities, the two (2) are similar. Hajj periods offer the Kano airport serious peak moments. Besides other international flights or international engagements, this airport also operates domestic flights.

To also handle international flights is the Kaduna airport which was designed much earlier when compared to the other two listed above. This was designed for aircrafts such as the Boeing-747, Boeing-737, BAC1-11, etc.

Maiduguri, Illorin and Sokoto airports are similar in capacity with the Kaduna airport and all are directed to operate international flights. All are designed to handle wide-body aircrafts like the Boeing 747. The Port Harcourt airport provides yet another international airport background designed to handle wide-body aircrafts like the Boeing 747. It also has provision for domestic flights as well. Other airports that operate short and medium-haul flights include the Enugu airport which was opened in 1976 after having been modernized. Basically, it handles domestic flight operations.

During the 1980s and 1990s, many airports were built, existing ones were modernized and more services and facilities added, all under the management of Nigerian Airports Authority.

Ileoje, 2003 states that it is estimated that by the year 2003, over four million Nigerian fly and use the airports each year. However, private domestic air carries began to win business at the expense of Nigeria, Airways, the government-owned national airline and it was declared bankrupt in 2004. According to Wikipedia (2019), Nigeria has 31 airports and 26 of the airports are operated by the Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria (FAAN), five of which are functional international airports. It also has a state-owned airport located in Akwa Ibom State. In addition, there are airstrips or airfields scattered around the country, built mainly by the Nigerian Air Force and multinational oil companies. Nigeria has only one private-public partnership airport operated by Bi-Courtney Aviation Services Ltd- Murtala Muhammed Airport Terminal Two.

Some of the Airports are listed below.

The Major domestic airports in Nigeria

1. Murtala Muhammed International Airport (Ikeja, Lagos)
2. Nnamdi Azikiwe International Airport (Abuja)
3. Mallam Aminu Kano International Airport (Kano)
4. Port Harcourt International Airport (Port Harcourt, Rivers)
5. Akanu Ibiam International Airport (Enugu)

The Major domestic airports in Nigeria are listed below.

1. Magaret Ekpo International Airport (Calabar, Cross River)
2. Sir Abubakar Tafawa Balewa Airport (Bauchi)
3. Kaduna Airport (Kaduna)
4. Maiduguri International Airport (Maiduguri, Borno)
5. Sultan Saddik Abubakar Airport (Sokoto)

6. Yakubu Gowon Airport (Plateau, Jos)
7. Yola Airport (Yola, Adamawa)
8. Kebbi International Airport (Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi)
9. Asaba International Airport (Asaba, Delta)
10. Bauchi Airport (Bauchi)
11. Sam Mbakwe Airport (Owerri, Imo)
12. Gombe Lawanti International Airport (Gombe)
13. Minna Airport (Minna, Niger)
14. Katsina Airport (Katsina)
15. Akwa Ibom Airport (Uyo, Akwa Ibom)
16. Ibadan Airport (Ibadan, Oyo)
17. Jalingo Airport (Jalingo, Taraba)
18. Akure Airport (Akure, Ondo)
19. Benin Airport (Benin, Edo)
20. Osubi Airport (Warri, Delta)
21. Ilorin Airport (Ilorin, Kwara)
22. Makurdi Airport (Makurdi, Benue)
23. Zaria Airport (Zaria, Kaduna)

List of Airstrips in Nigeria

1. Ajaokuta Airstrip in Kogi state
2. Azare Airstrip in Bauchi state
3. Bacita Airstrip in Kwara state

4. Bajoga Airstrip in Gombe state
5. Bebi Airstrip in Cross River state
6. Bida Airstrip in Niger state
7. Eket Airstrip in Akwa Ibom state
8. Escravos Airstrip in Delta state
9. Gusau Airstrip in Zamfara state
10. Nguru Airstrip in Yobe state
11. Potiskum Airstrip in Yobe
12. Shiroro Airstrip in Niger state
13. Tuga Airstrip in Kebbi state

Plate 1.1: Airports and Air routes in Nigeria

Source: google.com

In the year, 2011 the State Governors of Bauchi, Kebbi, Kwara and Niger carried out rehabilitation and upgrading of airports in their State capitals to attract investors from anywhere in the world. These airports are to create an efficient transportation network which is indispensable for economic growth (Alao, 2011) However few planes fly in these airports as the overwhelming majority in these States can only afford road transport.

In the years 2011 and 2012, there were new developments which have improved and further developed air transportation in Nigeria. These include renovation and upgrading of facilities at in Lagos, Kano, Port Harcourt, Enugu and Jos. Example include the construction of the new terminal at Nnamdi Azikwe International Airport Abuja and the construction of a domestic wing of Mallam Aminu Kano Airport. On December 12, 2011, Arik Air launched the Abuja-London Flight while earlier in the year, a new airline 1st Nation Continental Airlines started the Lagos (Nigeria)-Kigali (Rwanda) direct flight.

The rate at which major airports over the past years have consequently stirred up an increase in the traffic and demand for jet transport and greater runway lengths will greatly affect the capacity of cargo handling. The arrival of the four-engine jets, especially the Boeing 707, 747, 777, the Douglas DC-8 and the Airbus families of aircraft has been one of the activating factors. To this end, the government has instituted a body charged with providing the required airport specification that will accommodate the new wide-body jets.

2.4.1. FINANCING AIRPORT PROJECTS.

When an airport seeks to expand its facilities or a governmental entity seeks to build a new airport, enormous capital needs to be raised from public fund sources or private capital markets to finance such infrastructure development.

Capital sources include government loans and equity, loans from international organizations, commercial capital, markets and the extension of credit from contractors and suppliers. Commonly, some amount of governmental investments initiates airport development projects in the form of seed money while private sector financing follows complementarily.

The use of Commercial loans is usually minimized to the barest minimum because they incur the highest interest rates than governmental or public sector funds and the use of such commercial capital to finance airport development projects usually only arise due to the shortage of public sector funds. The trend towards airport privatization has been initiated to ease access to private money markets.

When an airport attempts development through private financing, it is common (for instance, in the United States of America) for the local authority to issue revenue bonds. This guarantees debt payment by airport revenue. Sometimes the raising of excess loans from private sources can lead to debt payment troubles for the local authority and the residents. Therefore, such capital sources have to be balanced with direct and indirect financing of equity and loans.

At larger airports, significant portions of the capital cost of a project are recovered through revenues from the airlines, concessionaires and other tenants. The remaining is recovered through capital cost from the Federal government and State government sources. The financial feasibility of the airport program is greatly determined by the magnitude and reasonableness of the charges and rents paid by airport users and tenants. The financing of general aviation airports continues to be a major problem since the revenue base available is usually insufficient to support significant capital improvements. It is, therefore, necessary that the benefits of the airport to the communities be carefully analyzed and the sources of financing ensured to be economically viable. The determination of financial feasibility of a project is usually instigated by an agreement between

the airport owners and the airport users. This will define the fiscal policies which will govern the setting of rates and charges for airport users. To achieve this, some basic process of steps must be followed:

- i. The capital cost of the project to the various cost centres established by airport management and airport users must be allocated. These cost centres are categorized as the airfield area, the hangar and other operational support building areas, the terminal area, the concession area(refreshment area- commercial franchise business), and other areas of the airport.
- ii. The net annual cost of the capital construction program and the assignments of these costs to the various cost centres should be projected; these costs should be amortized over a period of time specified in the agreement between the airport management and users.
- iii. The net annual administrative, operating and maintenance cost to each of the cost centres should be projected and allocated based on the knowledge of past cost experience as well as projections of these anticipated costs for the new facility.
- iv. The conversion of the total annual capital, administrative, operative and maintenance costs to a schedule of the fees and rents to be paid by the airport facility users, the utilizing available forecast of airport activity, passenger enplanements, parking usage, and other relevant projected airport activity.

The recovery of capital costs requires that the total capital investment in each cost centre be determined. This requires that the following be achieved: The ascertaining and assigning of the project costs in the airfield area for the runways, taxiways, aprons ramps, and land acquisition and improvement to the relevant cost centres are most essential. This also should be applied in the area

for terminal building construction, land and terminal support facilities. Airport support facilities such as access roads, service roads, sanitary and storm sewer systems, electrical and mechanical systems, communication and security services, emergency medical services, as well as crash, fire and rescue services, should be apportioned to appropriate cost centres to eliminate any imbalances in the determination of the facility cost centre revenue which may result in unreasonable rate and charges. The projected cost of airport administration, operation and maintenance which include all direct costs for salaries, materials and supplies, outside services and the related indirect cost are assigned to each cost centre on an annual basis. The terminal cost is divided by the terminal area which often considers the location and degree of finishing in ticketing facilities, baggage facilities, office space, and car- rental space to establish rental rates for the terminal building tenants.

The concession areas which are derived from rentals paid and fees paid on parking facility will be applied against the appropriate cost centre and the net revenue recovery requirements determined. The parking facility in large airports is usually the most significant concession cost centre and is usually assigned to the terminal cost centre since it produces a considerable capital cost.

Forecasts of landing weights are used to determine the landing fees charged to the airlines to recover airfield costs. The cost of the apron area are often isolated as a separate cost centre and ramp fees are established based on the frontage required by the airlines.

2.4.2. AIRPORT REVENUES

There are two basic sources of income for an airport: one is the commercial activity and the other type is based on aeronautical and other revenue. Internationally about 40% of the airport revenue comes from commercial activities, while the bigger chunk of the pie belongs to

aeronautical and other revenue. The aeronautical revenue comes from the main activity of the airport – airport fees that include, terminal, landing and passenger fees, noise and environmental charges and other payments related directly to the operation of the airport.

The commercial activities performed on the territory of the airport are also a great source of income. They include revenue from retail concessions to duty-free shops, restaurants, etc., renting terminal space, parking lots and the like. In both cases the bigger the airport is, the higher the revenue.

Revenues from aeronautical operations

- *Landing charges (including lighting and approach/aerodrome control charges).* Charges and fees collected for the use of runways, taxiways and apron areas, including associated lighting.
- *Passenger service charges.* Passenger service charges and other charges and fees collected for the use of the passenger terminal(s) and other passenger-processing facilities (e.g. for passengers embarking or disembarking).
- *Cargo charges.* Cargo charges and any other charges or fees collected in respect of cargo for the use of the airport's freight-processing facilities and areas.
- *Parking and hangar charges.* Charges collected from aircraft operators for the parking of aircraft (where not included in the landing charge) and their housing in airport-owned hangars, including any revenue from the leasing of such hangars to aircraft operators. Towing charges, if imposed, should also be included under this heading.

- *Security charges.* Charges and fees collected for the provision by the airport of security services for the protection of passengers and other persons at the airport, aircraft and other property.
- *Noise-related charges.* Charges collected related to the noise alleviation and prevention measures.
- *Emissions-related aircraft charges.* Charges collected to address local air quality problems at or around airports.
- *Other charges on air traffic operations.* All other charges and fees collected from aircraft operators for other types of facilities and services provided at the airport for the operation of aircraft.

Revenues from ground-handling charges.

This refers to charges and fees collected from aircraft operators for the use of facilities and services provided by the airport for the handling of aircraft. It should be noted that at the majority of airports ground handling is largely carried out by one or more airlines or special ground-handling enterprises. In the latter case, the airport will impose concession and/or rental fees which should be recorded as revenues from non-aeronautical activities.

Revenues from commercial (non-aeronautical) activities

- *Aviation fuel and oil concessions (including throughput charges).* All concession fees, including any throughput charges, payable by oil companies or any other entities for the right to sell or distribute aviation fuel and lubricants at the airport. Revenues from an automobile service station concession, including the sale of automobile fuel and lubricants,

should be entered in the revenue accounts covering “Other concessions and commercial activities operated by the airport.

- *Restaurants, bars, cafeterias and catering services.* Charges and fees payable by commercial enterprises or other entities for the right to operate restaurants, bars, cafeterias and catering services at the airport, including aircraft catering. It would also include any revenues derived from any such activities when operated by the airport.
- *Duty-free shops.* Charges and fees payable by a commercial enterprise or any other entity for the right to operate duty-free shop(s) at the airport, and for off-airport duty-free shops to deliver goods sold at the airport. It would also include any revenues derived from duty-free shops operated by the airport itself.
- *Automobile parking.* Charges and fees payable by a commercial enterprise or any other entity for the right to operate automobile parking facilities at the airport. It would also include any revenues derived from such facilities when operated by the airport itself.
- *Other concessions and commercial activities operated by the airport.* Any concession charges or fees, other than those mentioned above, payable by commercial enterprises or other entities for the right to sell goods and services (such as automobile rentals, and banking and exchange bureaus concessions) at the airport. Also included are any revenues derived from commercial activities (shops or services) operated by the airport itself and not mentioned above, as well as any public admission fees charged for entry to areas of special interest (e.g. terminal observation areas) or for guided tours within the airport area.
- *Rentals.* Rentals are payable by commercial enterprises and other entities for the use of airport-owned building space, land or equipment. Such rentals should include those payable by aircraft operators for airport-owned premises and facilities (e.g. check-in

counters, sales counters and administrative offices) other than those already covered under “air traffic operations” above.

- *Other revenues from non-aeronautical activities.* All other revenues the airport may derive from non-aeronautical activities. It would also include payments received by the airport for such services as heating, air conditioning, lighting, water, cleaning and telephone use, provided they are not included in the rental or concession fees.

Bank and cash management revenues

This includes any revenues derived from investments and cash management such as interest on bank accounts, treasury bills, short-term debentures and bonds, or from trading in discounted notes and other similar revenues. Interest received may be deducted from interest paid to arrive at a net interest cost which is then shown as an expense item.

Grants and subsidies

This covers any payments received and not requiring the transfer of assets or provision of services in return. This may entail a payment to the airport by the State.

2.5. ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS OF AIRPORT DEVELOPMENT

Since airport demand is a derived demand, the user benefits are demonstrated self-evidently by the revealed demand. However, the cost required to provide all the necessary services should be properly and carefully considered and compared with their economic benefits. The most striking benefits of airport development are those derived from the local employment and the stimulation of the regional economy.

A major commercial airport contributes 35,000 to 45,000 jobs to the local economy, and the presence of a convenient airport is highly instrumental in the decision by companies to locate their offices, companies and/or company headquarters within that region in which the airport exists.

The most striking disadvantages of the airport for airport development and operations are noise and other environmental impacts. To alleviate the problems associated with environmental impacts, substantial capital resources are constantly required.

A large scale investment is required in the development of an international airport and its ongoing operation as explained previously can generate considerable revenue for a long time. Therefore, during the airport planning stage, this can be determined through accounting the profitability or non-profitability of the development of the airport and this entails detailed analysis of the cost and revenues resulting from airport operations.

It is therefore generally recognized that large airports with high utilization rates can be operated as successful businesses as they generate revenues which can cover their full costs as well as capital charges.

2.6. FEDERAL AIRPORT AUTHORITY OF NIGERIA (FAAN).

The body has the power of developing and regulating the system of air transportation and possible maintenance. They guide and regulate the activities of different airlines that are established within the country. This ministry is further divided into three parts; each empowered to perform different duties. These bodies are:

- i. Management and Policy Division.
- ii. Civil Aviation Department

iii. Meteorological Department.

- The management and policy division of this ministry is responsible for drawing up policies and control the activities of different private bodies involved in the air travel industry.
- The civil aviation department controls the activities of private airlines that undertake commercial and private flights.
- The meteorological department is responsible for the weather services as it affects air transport.

2.6.2. FEDERAL MINISTRY OF AVIATION

The ministry through its civil aviation department implements the laws regulating safety in the aviation industry. The ministry also supervises and regulates the activities of the Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria (FAAN), the Nigerian Airways and the Nigerian Civil Aviation Training Center.

It is empowered to establish government policies and the provision of air traffic control and other precautionary measures that are necessary for operational purposes. The responsibility extends to the control of air transport, pilot licensing, airworthiness, the collection and dissemination of important guidelines to authorized airlines, economic and statistical data relating to the operations of civil aviation. The civil aviation school at Zaria is under the control of the ministry.

2.7. GENERAL PRINCIPLES OF DESIGN ASSOCIATED WITH AIRPORTS

The key to a good Airport design is flexibility and legibility. Flexibility comes into play to meet ever-changing marketing and operational needs in the terminal. While legibility allows passengers to steer their way through often labyrinthine airport environment.

A typical Airport consists of six major physical elements and up to a dozen secondary ones. The primary elements include;

- i. runway and taxi areas
- ii. Air traffic control Centre
- iii. Passenger terminal
- iv. Car parks and road system
- v. freight depot and warehouse areas
- vi. Hangars and aircraft service areas.

Also, there are many secondary elements which can form substantial parts of the airport layout such as;

- i. Accommodation facilities
- ii. Fire stations
- iii. Green spaces
- iv. Conference facilities
- v. Restaurants
- vi. Financial institutions
- vii. Airline buildings
- viii. Leisure and recreational facilities.

Integration and ease of connection is the key to a successful airport from the passenger's point of view. Good airport layout and building design should always seek to remove ambiguity, to reduce travel length, to maintain a sense of progression towards the destination and should wherever possible uplift the spirit. The psychological needs are as important as physical needs.

Two clear but divergent perceptions exist, they are;

- a. That of the airport authority which wishes to maximize profit.
- b. That of the passenger who wants stress-free travel.

A good Design aims at reconciling these viewpoints.

In the layout of the Airport, the determining factor is normally the orientation and length of the runways. These are mostly shaped by the direction of prevailing winds, the size of aircraft to be handled, and external factors such as position off towns, mountain ranges and power lines. It is also worthy to note that environmental impact assessment determines the key elements of the airport plan especially the resolution of noise ecological and visual impacts.

In any Airport, the terminal building is the key structure physically and aesthetically. It is the terminal building which way marks the airport and establishes a sense of architectural Quality to fulfil this role, the terminal should be the dominant building, with other structures having a secondary role.

There are three primary components of an airport layout they include;

- i. Airside
- ii. Terminal Building
- iii. Landside

Figure 2. illustration of airport layout zoning

Source: Author

2.8.1. TERMINAL PLANNING AND DESIGN PROCESS.

The process of planning airport passenger terminal facilities needs to take into account a multitude of safety, operational, commercial, financial, and environmental considerations, as well as have regard to local government and airline industry interests and aspirations. (Edward, 1974)

The first step in this process is to gather together and catalogue all of the existing data, information, and parameters that will have a bearing on the planning and subsequent design of the terminal facilities. The next step involves determining future forecasts of passenger, cargo, and aircraft movements that will form the demand basis for programming the future terminal and associated apron facility requirements. Once the facility requirements have been determined, the conceptual planning process can begin. This typically involves an iterative process of developing initial, and then progressively more refined, terminal complex concepts. These iterative conceptual development steps involve evaluation assessments that assist in narrowing the field of promising solutions, culminating in the selection of a single preferred option. The preferred terminal option

then forms the basis for the initial architectural and engineering schematic design, design development, preparation of construction drawings, and specifications and cost estimation. (Cincinnati et al. 2010).

Figure 2: Components of terminal complex

Source: Landrum & Brown

2.8.2. AIRSIDE TERMINAL FACILITIES

For the majority of new terminal planning and design projects, it is important from the outset to formulate solutions based on the airside component. This requires identifying gate requirements and locating aircraft parking positions and their supporting taxi lanes that optimize the overall efficiency of the airfield before developing the internal layout of the terminal building and the landside curb and terminal roadway systems. The efficiency of airfield operations will, to a very large extent, drive the overall efficiency of passenger processing through the terminal, and the ability of aircraft to park at the terminal and manoeuvre safely around the airfield. The airside's large spatial requirements and fixed requirements for aircraft wingtip separations and

manoeuvring clearances typically drive the physical geometry of the terminal complex more than either the passenger processing requirements within the terminal building, or its associated landside components.

The primary elements to consider when dealing with the airside component of a terminal complex include the following:

- Aircraft parking restrictions
 - Air traffic control tower line-of-sight
- Aircraft manoeuvring
 - Taxiway requirements
 - Taxilane requirements
 - Pushback areas
- Aircraft parking
 - Terminal gates
 - Remote aircraft parking positions
 - Wingtip clearances
 - Aircraft parking guidance systems
 - Aircraft parking apron
 - Apron gradients
 - Hydrant fueling
- Apron service roads
 - Tail-of-stand
 - Head-of-stand
- Ground service equipment

- Staging
 - Movement/manoeuvring
 - Storage
- Aircraft servicing
- Security and emergency response
- Environmental
 - Fuel spillage
 - Waste disposal
- Blast Fences
 - Public and employee protection
- Winter operations
 - Aircraft deicing
 - Apron snow removal

Sources: Cincinnatic, 2010, Norman, 2010

2.8.3. LANDSIDE TERMINAL FACILITIES

There are planning situations when the landside components may be the driving force behind the most appropriate terminal complex solution. Planning of landside terminal facilities requires considerable care because the efficiency, or lack thereof, can greatly influence the air traveller's perceptions of the overall efficiency and user-friendliness of the terminal. (Kaustubh et al. 2014, Edward, 1974)

The terminal landside system provides the interface between the airport and the regional ground transportation system. Ideally, passenger connectivity between the various points of landside access to the terminal by road and, when applicable, rail should be as seamless and convenient as possible with a minimum of pedestrian level changes. Pedestrian and vehicular movements on the landside are particularly vulnerable to congestion at many airports due to peaks of demand associated with air travel and a historic pattern of growth in enplanements. Expansion of these facilities is often difficult, so intensive and proactive management of the landside curb and road-way systems is required to cope with increased activity and congestion. This management can be performed using manpower or by the use of technology.

The primary elements to consider when dealing with the terminal building component of the terminal complex include the following:

- Curbfront pedestrian facilities
 - Sidewalk—adjacent to the terminal
 - Curb islands
 - Pedestrian crosswalks
 - Curbside baggage check-in
- Curbfront vehicle lanes
 - Loading/unloading lanes
 - Bypass lanes
 - Through lanes
- Parking
 - Terminal passenger parking
 - Remote passenger parking

- Off-airport parking
- Valet parking
- Employee parking (FAA, airlines, tenants, staff)
- Rental car parking
- Cell phone lots
- Entry/exit roadways
 - Primary terminal access and exit roadways
 - Recirculation roadways
 - Service roads/loading docks
- Commercial vehicle/transit staging areas
 - Taxi and bus holding areas
 - Ground transportation centres
- Rail transit
 - Platform configuration
 - Station location

2.9.1. TERMINAL PLANNING AND DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

At the start of a terminal planning project, there are several key terminal planning considerations with ramifications for the terminal's ultimate design that should be explored and discussed with the airport terminal sponsor and key stakeholders. The considerations presented in this section will focus on the terminal building itself as compared to the more macro considerations

such as land use compatibility, Airport Master Plan, ground access transportation, terminal site, environmental, and business planning strategies. (Kaustubh et al. 2010)

The following are terminal planning considerations:

- Mission
- Balance
- Level of service
- Passenger convenience
- Flexibility
- Security
- Wayfinding and terminal signage
- Accessibility
- Maintenance

2.9.2. FUNCTIONS OF THE TERMINAL BUILDING

The principal functions of an airport terminal building are as follows:

- i. It facilitates the change of transport mode (from plane to car, train, bus, etc).
- ii. It processes passengers and their luggage (tickets, check-in, customs, clearance, etc).
- iii. It provides services (shopping, conference, security, etc).
- iv. It organizes passengers for air transportation

2.9.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE TERMINAL BUILDING

The design objective should always be to:

- i. Minimized passenger walking distances.
- ii. Minimized delay in the processing of passengers and baggage
- iii. Create reliable and accessible baggage handling systems
- iv. Protect passengers from aircraft blast
- v. Make the terminal building flexible for growth and response to technology changes.
- vi. Achieve optimum occupancy levels
- vii. Create functional disposition of management, airline, and control units to allow maximum effective use of staff.
- viii. See to the provision of amenities for passengers that will satisfy varied needs in appropriate locations as well as contribute to airport revenue.
- ix. See to the provision of facilities for handicapped, and very young passengers. ‘

2.9.4 COMPONENTS OF THE TERMINAL SYSTEM

The terminal area is the major interface between airside and landside as the passenger terminal should function as the landside access, the processing centre of passengers and baggage and the boarding for departing passengers. The passenger terminal system has three major components:

i. ACCESS INTERFACE

In this interface, the passenger transfers from the access mode of travel to the passenger-processing component. This interface consists of the terminal curbs, car parking and the road system used for circulation in the land side of the airport.

ii. PROCESSING INTERFACE

In this interface, passengers and their baggage are processed in preparation for starting or ending of an air trip.

Table 1: Passenger Processing In Terminal Design

Airline Function	Ticketing check-in
	Baggage Handling (part)
	Gate check- in
Airport Function	Baggage Handling (part)
	Security (part)
Government Function	Immigration Control
	Passport Control
	Customs Control
	Health Control
	Security (part)

Source: The Author

This consists of the airline's counters for ticket issue and check-in, security checking facilities, airport administration and service area and the associated service facilities such as amenities, concession restaurants, lobby for circulation and waiting, spaces for airline offices and baggage handling and claim. Also included in the processing system are the services under governmental auspices such as customs, immigration and quarantine.

iii. FLIGHT INTERFACE

In this interface, the passenger transfers from the processing component to the aircraft. This comprises of the connections between the terminal and the parked aircraft. This system is composed of the concourse, departure lounge, passenger boarding devices, airline operations, security facilities, terminal service areas such as building maintenance and utilities.

Plate 2.1: International Airport Flow Plan Diagram

Source: *New Metric Handbook* edited by Patricia Tutt & David Adler, pg. 464

Plate 2.2: Terminal Building Functional Diagram

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas

Walliman, pg. 446

2.9.5. TERMINAL CONCEPT TYPES

Once the planner understands the mission of the terminal, gains insights from the key stakeholders, and assembles the necessary facility requirements to drive the planning process, it is possible to explore the development of initial concepts. In general, there are two categories of terminal concept types. The first category addresses the organization of terminal processing into either a centralized or decentralized type of airport terminal complex. The second category then organizes the terminal into one of four generally recognized types of terminal and concourse concepts.

2.9.6. BASIC PLAN CONFIGURATIONS

Over time, four basic terminal/concourse concept types have been recognized by the industry at large. (Kaustubh, 2014)

2.9.6.1. LINEAR CONCEPT

The linear concept, in its purest form, is the simplest and most straight-forward of the four basic terminal concept types. A simple linear terminal consists of a single passenger processing area adjacent to a single common hold room area, which, in turn, is adjacent to the aircraft parking apron. Aircraft boarding is handled via a series of gates that lead directly to the aircraft parking apron or to passenger loading bridges, which are spaced along the terminal face. (Cincinnati et al. 2010)

Plate 2.3: Linear Configuration (Decentralized) - Airport Terminal Configuration

Source: *New Metric Handbook* by Patricia Tutt & David Adler, pg. 63

2.9.6.2. PIER OR FINGER CONCEPT

In the pier concept, aircraft are parked on both sides of a concourse that extends from the terminal. Aircraft are usually arranged around the axis of the pier in a perpendicular, nose-in parked relationship. Access to the terminal area is at the base of the concourse or pier. Pedestrian circulation moves down the centre of the pier through a corridor with hold rooms, and various services and amenities arranged along both sides of the circulation spine serving enplaning and deplaning passengers. This concept fully separates the passenger processing functions from the concourse activities thus enabling each element to develop according to its requirements. Because the aircraft access on the pier is double loaded, walking distances for passengers are shortened. (Cincinnati et al. 2010)

Plate 2.4: Pier Configuration (Centralized) - Airport Terminal Configuration

Source: *New Metric Handbook* edited by Patricia Tutt & David Adler, pg. 63

2.9.6.3. SATELLITE CONCEPT

In the satellite concept, the terminal building is developed on the airside that is completely surrounded by aircraft and is connected to the processing areas of the terminal via an underground, at-grade, or overhead connector. This satellite building houses the passenger hold rooms, as well as various services and amenities for the passengers. The aircraft are normally parked in a nose-in arrangement around the satellite that can have common or separate departure lounges. Although the satellite concourse itself can be compact, the separation distance from the terminal is typically quite lengthy. This length requires that some type of mechanized people- moving system, such as moving walkways, bus, or APM system, be used to move passengers back and forth between the terminal processor and the satellite concourse. (Cincinnati et al. 2010)

Plate 2.5: Satellite Configuration (Centralized) - Airport Terminal Configuration

Source: *New Metric Handbook* edited by Patricia Tutt & David Adler, pg.63

2.9.6.4. TRANSPORTER CONCEPT

The transporter concept provides a complete separation of passenger facilities from those required to service and maintain the aircraft. Aircraft and aircraft-servicing functions are remotely located from the terminal. Originally, all passenger processing functions were to be housed in a single centralized terminal processor, sometimes referred to as the head-house, with large mobile lounges serving as temporary hold rooms. Passengers access the aircraft via the mobile lounges that leave from the terminal gates, go directly to the aircraft, and attach to the aircraft to provide weather-protected transit. (Cincinnati et al. 2010)

Plate 2.6: Transporter Configuration- Airport Terminal Configuration

Source: New Metric Handbook by Patricia Tutt & David Adler, pg.63

The prototypes make up the centralized processing systems, the decentralized processing system and the unit terminal system.

i. THE CENTRALIZED SYSTEM

In this system, all facilities of the system are housed in one building and used for processing all passengers using the building. In this system, all passenger routes converge on and diverge from a centralized passenger processing and amenities facility. The centralized processing facilities are economical as common facilities may be used to service a large number of aircraft gate operations.

ii. THE DECENTRALIZED SYSTEM

In this system, the passenger facilities are arranged in smaller modular units and repeated in one more building. Each unit is arranged around one or more aircraft gate position and serves the passenger using those gate positions. In this system, all passenger routes converge on and diverge from several of the separate passenger processing and amenities facility.

iii. UNIT TERMINAL SYSTEM

In this system, two or more separate of centralized or decentralized processing amenities facility is provided to serve specific functions. This includes the assigning of independent terminals to various airlines, international flights only or domestic flights only. This system has been developed with the increase in traffic demand. The passengers retain the benefits of reduced congestion and shorter walking distances to the boarding gates. With the decentralized organization, higher processing costs may be experienced than with the centralized system.

2.10.1 RUNWAYS

A runway is a rectangular strip of land on an airport prepared for the landing and taking- off of aircrafts. The orientation of a runway's direction needs to be determined at the initial stage of an airport design and is usually influenced by several factors such as:

- i. The prevailing wind patterns.
- ii. Area available for airport development.
- iii. Land- use around the airport.
- iv. Airspace restrictions in the vicinity of the airport.

The length of a runway depends on such factors as the prevailing weather, topography, altitude, temperature, environmental restrictions, aircraft type and weight expected to operate from the airport.

2.10.2 RUNWAY CONFIGURATIONS

Several options for runway configuration for airports exist. These runway configurations are a combination of several basic configurations. These basic configurations are:

- i. Single runways.
- ii. Parallel runways.
- iii. Intersecting runways.
- iv. Open- V runways.

i. SINGLE RUNWAYS

This is the simplest of runway configuration. It has been estimated that the hourly capacity of a single runway was estimated to be between 50 and 100 operations per hour in Visual Flight

Rule (VFR) conditions while the capacity is reduced to 50 or 70 operations in the Instrument Flight Rule (IFR) conditions, depending on the composition of aircraft mix and the navigation aids available.

ii. PARALLEL RUNWAYS

This exists when a pair of runways are constructed parallel to another. The capacity of parallel runway systems depends on the number of runways and the spacing between the runways. The spacing between parallel runways varies widely and therefore has been classified into three, depending on the degree of independence of the two runways in Instrument Rule Flight (IRF) conditions by the United State Federal Aviation Administration (U.S.F.A.A.). These are:

iii. CLOSE PARALLEL RUNWAYS

These are spaced form a minimum of 210 meters (700ft) to less than 750 meters (2500ft). With this configuration, Instrument Flight Rule (IFR) conditions states that the operation of one runway is dependent on the operation of the other runway. In IFR conditions, the hourly capacity of this type of runway is between 50 to 60 operations per hour.

iv. INTERMEDIATE PARALLEL RUNWAYS

These have been spaced between 750 meters (2500ft) to less than 1290 meters (4300ft). According to IFR conditions, this allows an arrival on one runway to occur independently of a departure on the other runway. In IFR conditions, the hourly capacity of this type of runway is between 60 to 75 operations per hour.

v. FAR PARALLEL RUNWAYS

These are spaced farther than 1290 meters (4300ft) apart, allowing the runways to be operated independently for both arrivals and departures. In IFR conditions, the hourly capacity of this type of runway is between 100 to 125 operations per hour.

vi. INTERSECTING RUNWAYS

These are two more runways in different directions that cross each other. These kinds of runways are necessary when relatively strong winds are prevalent from one or more directions. When the wind forms a certain direction is strong, only one runway of a pair of intersecting runways can be used. When the winds are relatively light, both runways can be used simultaneously.

The capacity of two intersecting runways depends on the location of the intersection (either midway or near the end) and on the way the runways are operated. The farther the intersection position is from the take-off end of the runway and the landing threshold, the lower the capacity and vice versa. Therefore, the capacity can be maximized when the intersecting position is located close to the take-off end and the landing threshold.

vii. OPEN-V RUNWAYS

These feature runways in different directions which do not intersect each other. Like intersecting runways, Open- V runways revert to the single runway the winds are strong from one direction while both runways can be used simultaneously when the winds are light enough. The highest capacity is achieved when the operations are away from the v- intersection. Therefore, to maximize capacity, the single direction runway configuration is most ideal as it is less complex than a multiple direction configuration of the air traffic control, particularly in the routing of aircrafts

around the airport. The intersecting runway configuration is the most complex and challenging for air traffic control operations. If it cannot be avoided, it is recommended to try to place the intersection of both runways as close as possible to their thresholds and to operate the intersection away from the intersection.

2.10.3 BASIC RUNWAY ELEMENTS

The runway system at an airport consists of the following:

i. STRUCTURAL PAVEMENT

This supports the aircraft for structural load, manoeuvrability, control, stability and other operational and dimensional criteria.

ii. SHOULDERS

These are adjacent to the end of the structural pavement and are designed to resist erosion due to jet blast and to accommodate maintenance and emergency equipment.

iii. BLAST PAD

This is an area designed to prevent erosion of surfaces adjacent to the ends of runways which are subjected to sustained or repeated jet blast. The width of the blast pad should include both the runway and the shoulder width.

iv. RUNWAY SAFETY AREA

This is an area which includes the structural pavement, shoulders, blast pad and stop way if provided. The area is usually cleared, drained and graded. This area should be capable of

supporting emergency (fire, crash) and maintenance (snow-removal) equipment under normal conditions, as well as provide support for aircraft in case they veer off the pavement.

- Legend**
- A. Single Runway
 - B. Two parallel runways - even threshold
 - C. Two parallel runways - staggered threshold
 - D. Four parallel runways
 - E. Intersecting runways
 - F. Intersecting runways
 - G. Intersecting runways
 - H. Open- V runways
 - I. Open- V runways
 - TO - Take Off
 - L- Landing

Plate 2.7: Typical Runway Configurations

Source: *Planning and Design of Airports* by Robert Horonjeff & Francis X. McKelvey, pg. 202

2.10.4. FACTORS INFLUENCING RUNWAY LENGTHS

There are a number of factors which influence runway lengths and these are as follows:

i. PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS AND SIZE OF THE AIRCRAFT

The size of an aircraft and its ability to properly perform determine the length of a runway as each aircraft size requires a certain runway length to achieve its efficient landing and taking-off.

ii. CONDITION OF RUNWAY SURFACE

This is important for the effective performance of aircrafts on the runways. It should therefore be ensured that such substances or conditions which could hinder the proper efficiency of aircraft operations are resolved. One of such substances is the slush or standing water (snow) which always has an undesirable effect on aircraft operations. It has a slippery texture which creates difficulty in the braking of aircrafts. This is extremely poor and can damage parts of the aircraft which would lead to possible accidents.

iii. ANTICIPATED VOLUME OF TRAFFIC

This influences the number of runways required, the configuration of taxiways and the size of the ramp area at the airside in an airport. This is determined by the number of aircrafts that take-off and land at the same time in the airside area of an airport as well as within peak-hours of airport operations.

iv. METEOROLOGICAL CONDITIONS

These influence the length and number of runway(s) and it can be affected by such important meteorological conditions as wind and temperature.

v. TEMPERATURE

This influences runway lengths as the higher the temperature, the longer the runway required for aircraft operations. This is as a result of the fact that high temperature reflects lower air density

which would result in lower output of thrust. The increase in runway lengths is not linear with temperature rather; it can be achieved by calculating the percentage of runway length for a give temperature. The rate of increase of runway lengths at higher temperature is usually greater than that at lower temperature.

vi. SURFACE WIND

The greater the headwind in an area, the shorter runway length; the greater the tail wind, the longer the runway length. The effect of wind varies, depending in part on temperature and aircraft weight. For the airport designing and planning purposes, it is essential to use no wind, particularly if light winds occur at the airport site.

vii. ELEVATION OF AIRPORT SITES

This also influences the runway length requirements of an aircraft. This would be explained through the following:

viii. SURFACE WIND

The higher the altitude of an airport, the longer the runway required for aircraft operations. This is increase in not linear but rather varies with weight and temperature. The rate of increase is usually higher at high altitude than at lower altitudes.

ix. RUNWAY GRADIENT

An uphill gradient requires more runway length than a level or downhill gradient. Is specific amount being dependent on the elevation of the airport and temperature. The relationship between uniform gradient and increase and decrease in runway length is relatively linear. The maximum gradient is limited to 1½percent. For airport planning process and effective gradient1 is used.

2.11. TAXIWAYS

A taxiway is a defined path on a strip of land on an airport established for the taxiing of aircraft and intended to provide a link between one part of a runway and another. The basic function of a taxiway is to provide access from the runway to the terminal building and service hangars. For the efficient flow of the operated aircraft, taxiways should be arranged so that aircrafts landing and aircrafts taking- off do not interfere with each other in the taxiways. If it is expected that the taxiing traffic is able to move simultaneously in both directions, a parallel one-way taxi route system is desirable for safety and efficiency. The minimum separation between parallel taxiways is determined by the wingspan of the largest aircraft. The taxiway system should be designed with the consideration for the volume of traffic, the runway configuration and the location of the terminal building and other facilities. Since the speeds of aircrafts are considerably less on taxiways than on runways, it permits the width of the taxiway to be less than that of the runway. Therefore, in order to provide a margin of safety in the airport operating areas, the traffic- ways must be separated sufficiently from each other and from adjacent obstructions.

2.11.2. EXIT- TAXIWAY

The function of the exit- taxiway otherwise called turnoffs is to minimize runway occupancy by landing aircraft. The exit- taxiways are usually placed at angles but when they are placed at an angle in the order of 30° to the runway, the term High- speed exit is used to denote that it is designed for high speeds than other exit taxiway configurations.

The location of the exit- taxiway depends to a great extent on the following below:

- i. The mix of aircraft
- ii. The approach and touchdown speeds

- iii. The point of touchdown
- iv. The exit speed and
- v. The rate of deceleration, which in turn depends on the conditions of the pavement surface and number of exits.

Therefore, for efficient traffic flow, the runways and the connecting taxiways should be arranged so as to:

- i. Provide shortest taxi distance possible from terminal area to the end of runways
- ii. Provide adequate separation in the air traffic pattern
- iii. Cause the least interference and delay in landing, taxiing and take-off operations
- iv. Provide adequate taxiways so landing aircraft can leave the runways as quickly as possible and follow routes as short as possible to the terminal area.

Plate 2.8: High- Speed Taxiway Exit

Source: Airport Design Standards, Federal Aviation Administration

Plate 2.9: Taxiway Exit

Source: Airport Design Standards, Federal Aviation Administration

2.12. HOLDING BAYS

These are small aprons placed at a convenient location in the airport for the temporary storage of aircrafts especially when the number of gates may be insufficient to handle the number of aircrafts available at the airport at a time. This is only possible during busy periods or peak hours of a day.

Terminal Apron Planning Criteria

Planning criteria for the terminal apron, combined with the analysis of aircraft gate requirements, drive the general configuration and the area required for the airside component of the terminal complex. These criteria cover the following:

- Aircraft gates and parking positions
- Aircraft gate wingtip clearances
- Aircraft parking guidance systems
- Apron gradients
- Blast fences
- Apron service roads
- Aircraft servicing
- Ground service equipment storage
- Apron lighting

2.12.1. Aircraft Gates and Parking Positions

The aircraft gate/stand - designated area intended for parking an aircraft so that passengers and cargo can be loaded and unloaded. For simplicity, the term “gate” will be used. The gate is the interface between passenger and aircraft flow. This section is devoted to discussing the multiple forms of aircraft gates/stands and the attributes that should be considered when planning these facilities.

2.12.2. Gate/Stand Capacity and Fleet Mix

When discussing airport capacity, there are two different forms of capacity:

1. dynamic capacity (i.e., airfield capacity as it is related to the flow of aircraft on and around the airfield) and
2. Static capacity (i.e., gate capacity as related to the ability to accommodate aircraft).

Gate capacity – The maximum number of aircraft that a fixed number of gates can accommodate during a specified interval of time (typically 1 hour). Gate capacity is affected by several factors including but not limited to the following:

- The number and type of gates available
- The fleet mix demanding apron and gate space
- The use of passenger loading bridges or ground passenger loading
- Any operating restrictions on the use of any or all gates
-

The nomenclature “gate” is typically associated with an aircraft parking position situated at a terminal building and is often referred to as a “contact” gate.

From a macro perspective, gates and stands are sometimes referenced by one of three broad aircraft size categories:

1. Wide body
2. Narrow body
3. Commuter or regional.

To maximize gate capacity, it is recommended to plan gates so that they are as flexible as possible. Various arrangements are used both in the United States and overseas to accomplish this goal. The *IATA Airport Development Reference Manual* shows one approach referred to as the Multi-Aircraft Ramp System (MARS).

MARS is a modular approach that allows two narrowbody aircraft to operate independently within the same footprint area of typically a Jumbo or Super Jumbo utilizing the same two loading bridges to serve all three aircraft positions.

Plate 2.10: Example of MARS with widebody aircraft.

Source: IATA Airport Development Reference Manual

Plate 2.11: Aircraft parking flexibility.

Source: IATA Airport Development Reference Manual

Table 2: Aircraft Gate Wingtip Clearances

FAA AIRPLANE DESIGN GROUP	ICAO AIRCRAFT CODE LETTER	WINGTIP CLEARANCE (FT/M)
I	A	10 / 3
II	B	10 / 3
III	C	15 / 4.5
IV	D	25 / 7.5
V	E	25 / 7.5
VI	F	25 / 7.5

Source: IATA Airport Development Reference Manual

2.13. AIRCRAFT PARKING GUIDANCE SYSTEMS

Visual Docking Guidance System

A visual docking guidance system should be provided when it is intended to indicate, by a visual aid, the precise positioning of an aircraft on an aircraft gate/stand and when other alternative means, such as wing walkers, are not practicable.

Several factors need to be considered when evaluating the need for a visual docking guidance system. Those factors include the number and type of aircraft using the aircraft gate/stand, weather conditions, the available space on the apron, and the degree of precision required for maneuvering due to aircraft servicing installations, passenger loading bridges, and other obstacles.

Design requirements for a visual docking system include both azimuth and stop guidance displays. Various types of visual docking systems can satisfy the operational requirements and specifications.

Such points may consist of fencing, monitored gates, and/or manned entrances and would allow maintenance, fire and rescue, fuel, baggage, freight, and aircraft service vehicles access to the roads.

If service roads involve cargo operations, they should be able to support unit load device transporter equipment between cargo terminals and aircraft, and exclusive use of part of the roadway system may become necessary by some categories of vehicles, such as unusually wide or high vehicles.

As a minimum, the apron service road should have one lane in each direction with an overall width of 24 feet (12 feet each lane). In high-congestion areas it may be necessary to include a separate turn lane (12 feet wide) to provide vehicle-queuing and by-pass capability.

Figure 3: Illustrates a visual docking guidance system

Source: IATA Airport Development Reference Manual

2.13.1. CONFIGURATIONS OF APRON SERVICE ROADS

Three configurations exist for apron service roads, and they are identified based on location relevant to an aircraft's parked position:

1. tail-of-stand/apron edge,
2. head-of-stand,
3. Between aircraft.

1. **Tail-of-Stand/Apron Edge.** Tail-of-stand service roads positioned behind aircraft, also known as apron edge service roads, are typically routed along the edge of the aircraft parking apron, outside of taxiway or taxi lane clearance areas, and along the aircraft parking limit lines.

- With this type of service road, a potential conflict between aircraft and vehicles can be an issue. If possible, additional clearance beyond the parking limit lines should be placed to protect aircraft from potential vehicle deviations on the service road. Clear markings are necessary to determine boundaries and to prevent impingement on apron taxiway/taxi lane operations
- Tail-of-stand service roads are beneficial for linear concourse pier terminals when airlines operate gates on both sides of the pier.

2. **Head-of-Stand.** Many large overseas airports that primarily service widebody aircraft tend to favour head-of-stand service roads located between the face of the terminal building and the aircraft parking and servicing area because significant portions of operational servicing activity occur at the front of the aircraft. However, the main problem with head-of-stand

service roads is clearance height issues for large vehicles that may need to pass under passenger loading bridges.

- Minimum height clearance of 14 feet (4.2 meters) for the road surface beneath loading bridges and terminal buildings is recommended per IATA standards. A head-of-stand road usually requires the addition of a fixed bridge section that spans over the service road from the terminal to a loading bridge pedestal. This additional distance of the head-of-stand roadway increases the total depth of the aircraft apron.
- Adequate room for pushback procedures should be planned to allow for aircraft tug manoeuvrability space that will not interfere with the service road and potentially cause congestion. Conflicts may also exist between these roads and GSE storage beneath the terminal building and apron-level door exits.

3. **Between Aircraft Wingtips.** These service roads usually occur in conjunction with tail-of-stand service roads and allow smaller size vehicles to pass under the terminal building and/or concourse instead of having to go around the entire face of the building. When roads are placed between aircraft, increased aircraft wingtip separation will be required to protect against aircraft damage in case of vehicle deviation from the service road.

2.13.2. APRON SAFETY CLEARANCES

The required safety clearances on the apron vary greatly depending on the type of operations being conducted. Safety clearances ensure that aircraft can manoeuvre into/out of gate/stands without colliding with other aircraft, terminal facilities, ground service vehicles, and pedestrians or causing damage from jet blast

Several procedures and enhancements can dramatically increase the effectiveness of these clearances:

- Gate/stand lead-in lines
- Nose-gear hold lines
- Apron safety lines
- Dedicated equipment areas
- Dedicated service vehicle road
- Use of wing-walkers during push-back procedures

2.13.3. APRON MARKINGS

i. Ground Service Equipment Parking and Staging.

The staging and parking are usually limited to the area between the apron safety line—which is painted in red—and either the head-of-stand service road configuration or the terminal building and tail-of-stand service road configuration.

ii. Taxiway/Taxi lane Centerline.

Taxiway and taxi lane centerlines provide a visual cue to the pilot to facilitate safe taxiing of the aircraft. The standard for taxiway/taxi lane centerline marking is a solid yellow line that is equidistant from either edge of the pavement for taxiways and meets the required safety separation for taxi lanes.

iii. Ground Vehicle Roadway Markings.

When planning apron spaces, it is essential to delineate where ground vehicles are permitted to operate to prevent unnecessary interference with aircraft operations or passengers. The standards for ground vehicle roadway markings are either solid white lines or a white “zipper” marking for a low-visibility condition Surface Movement Guidance and Control System (SMGCS) to delineate the roadway edges.

iv. Passenger Walkways.

Passenger walkways should be provided on the apron area and if necessary across service roads. The walkways should be painted with white stripes across any active roadway surface.

v. Aircraft Maneuvering.

From time to time under certain apron conditions and locations, it is necessary for aircraft to perform non-standard manoeuvres in the apron area. To assist pilots in completing these manoeuvres, special paths for the taxiway/taxi lane centerline or gate/ stand lead-in line should be painted on the pavement. An example of this would be the marking of an aircraft push-back line that a tug would follow to ensure adequate clearances are maintained.

Figure 4: Typical aircraft servicing equipment.

Source: IATA Airport Development Reference Manual

2.13.4. AIRCRAFT GATE REQUIREMENTS

2.13.4.1. Aircraft Gate Types

When planning an airport apron layout, an important aspect to consider is passenger loading and unloading between the terminal building and aircraft. The decision on which type of gate to use will depend largely on the level of aircraft traffic that is to be accommodated, the terminal layout, and local airport conditions.

Aircraft gates are either considered contact gates or remote gates.

- i. **Contact gates** are either in physical contact with the terminal through the use of a passenger loading bridge or in enough proximity to the terminal to allow passengers to walk to the aircraft.
- ii. **Remote gates (or stands)** are far enough from the terminal to require some type of bus or transporter for passengers. The terms “remote gate” and “stand” are synonymous, with the term remote gate being more commonly used in the United States.

Airports with lower levels of air service, or service by regional aircraft, have tended to use apron ground loading. Larger airports with higher commercial aircraft activity by mainline aircraft typically employ passenger loading bridges.

Contact Gates. When planning contact gates, consideration must be given to providing sufficient space for GSE operations. Aircraft must be parked to allow safe operation of passenger loading bridges for the range of aircraft that are expected to be using each gate. If passengers are to walk to their aircraft, well-marked paths must be maintained at a safe distance from ground equipment and engines of parked aircraft.

2.14. LOADING BRIDGES.

Passenger loading bridges are positioned to bring passengers to left-side aircraft boarding doors, with the bridges located forward of the aircraft wing. Many aircraft types support passenger boarding through only a left-side door. They also improve passenger and staff safety, passenger experience, and disabled access between the aircraft and terminal building in comparison to ground loading of passengers.

General loading bridge requirements include the ability to communicate with passengers queuing between the gate and aircraft in case of an emergency, bridge emergency escape stairs, backup systems, fire suppression systems, emergency lighting, and clear maneuvering range markings on the airport apron.

Also, maximum gradients must comply with ADA requirements of 1:12, while a 1:10 slope is recommended by IATA and ICAO.

Two primary types of loading bridges and slight variations of these tend to be utilized:

1. Apron drive bridges
2. Fixed bridges.

i. **APRON DRIVE BRIDGES.**

Apron drive bridges provide the most flexibility in serving a wide range of aircraft types. Apron drive bridges consist of a rotunda, two or three telescoping tunnels, and a rotating cab that docks to the aircraft as depicted in Figure below.

Figure 5: Apron Drive Bridge.

Source: IATA Airport Development Reference Manual

The rotunda is a fixed unit on the aircraft apron and the main support mechanism for the loading bridge. Apron drive bridges move on three axes: vertically about a pivot point on the rotunda, laterally through telescopic section movement, and on an arc rotating about the bridge rotunda. The cab that docks with the aircraft also rotates and can either be non-levelling or self-levelling.

The three-tunnel bridge is generally recommended for use when the range of aircraft height differential varies the most.

The apron drive bridge's operation should not interfere with other aircraft or GSE movements.

Most airports prohibit vehicle traffic or parked equipment under the movable portion of an apron drive bridge and therefore the apron should be striped as a no parking/ no traffic area.

The floor elevation of the terminal, or concourse, along with the floor levels of the fixed section, the rotunda, and the tunnel sections of the loading bridge itself, must provide a gradual transition for passengers walking to and from the aircraft without any steep slopes. In the United States, no ramped surface in the passenger's path to and from the aircraft to the building should exceed the ADA maximum slope requirements of 1:12.

Figure 6: Over-the-wing bridge.

Source: google.com

A specific category of an apron drive loading bridge, called the “over-the-wing apron drive bridge,” docks with the rear door of aircraft. This configuration permits two or three loading bridges to service a single aircraft. The downside to dual- and triple-service apron drive bridges.

ii. **FIXED BRIDGES.**

Airports with gates servicing one type of aircraft, or aircraft of similar sizes and door sill heights, may opt for fixed loading bridges. As depicted in Figure V-12, fixed bridges typically consist of a fixed link from the terminal to a pedestal, a two-tunnel telescoping section, and a cab with limited rotation as compared to an apron drive bridge.

Fixed bridges are more economical than apron drive bridges, but less flexible in accommodating different types of aircraft with wide-ranging door sill heights.

Fixed bridges move on two axes: vertically about a pivot point at the end of the telescoping section, and laterally through telescopic section movement. Also, fixed bridges require the aircraft to be stopped more accurately than is required for apron drive bridges, because cab movement is limited. However, less protection of the apron area is necessary compared to the apron drive bridge because the tunnel section moves over less apron space with the fixed bridge.

Figure 7: Fixed Bridge.

Source: IATA Airport Development Reference Manual

Apron-Level or Ground-Loaded Gates. Ground-loaded gates are typically used for smaller regional aircraft but may be used for mainline aircraft when traffic volume or terminal design does not justify a loading bridge. Planning for passenger walking routes between the terminal and aircraft should involve determining the shortest possible route and maintaining free movement of aircraft, vehicles, and passengers while avoiding conflict between them. Pathways for passengers must be clearly marked, free of obstacles, and closely monitored for safe and secure movement between aircraft and the terminal.

2.15. PARKING CONFIGURATIONS

Aircraft- parking type refers to how the aircraft is positioned to the terminal building and how the aircraft manoeuvre in and out of parking position. It is an important factor which affects the size of the parking positions and consequently the apron- gate area. When choosing a parking system of an aircraft on an apron, it is important to note that passengers should be protected from the adverse elements of noise, jet blast, weather as well as the operating and maintenance costs of needed ground equipment.

Parking of aircraft on the apron can be broadly categorized; however, into four basic parking configurations:

i. NOSE-IN PARKING AIRCRAFT

In this, aircraft configuration is parked perpendicular to the building line with the nose as close to the building as permissible. The operation here is the power-in of aircraft to parking position under its power and push-out of aircraft to a sufficient distance to allow it to proceed under its power.

Advantages: It requires the smallest gate area for a given aircraft, causes lower noise levels as there is no powered turning movement near the terminal building, sends no jet blast toward the building and facilitates passenger loading as the nose is near the building.

Disadvantages: It requires towing equipment and the nose is too far from the building to effectively use the rear doors for passenger loading.

Plate 2.12: Nose- In Parking- Aircraft Parking Configuration

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas Walliman,

pg. 447

ii. ANGLE NOSE-IN PARKING

Aircraft are parked at other angles to the building line with their nose pointing towards the terminal building.

Advantage: There the operation is power-in and power-out of the aircraft from the gate by its own power.

Disadvantage: It requires a larger gate area than the nose- in configuration and causes a higher noise level.

Plate 2.13: Angled Nose- in Parking- Aircraft Parking Configuration

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas Walliman, pg.

447

iii. ANGLE NOSE-OUT

Aircraft are parked with their nose pointing away from the terminal building at an angle.

Advantage: It allows the operation of power-in and power-out of aircraft from the gate without towing.

Disadvantage: It requires a larger gate area than the nose- in position but less than the angled nose- in position.

Plate 2.14: Angled Nose- Out Parking- Aircraft Parking Configuration

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas Walliman,

pg. 447

iv. PARALLEL PARKING

Aircraft are parked parallel to the terminal building line and is the easiest to achieve from aircraft maneuvering conditions.

Advantage: It minimizes noise and jet blast as there are no sharp turning maneuvers, loading and unloading of passengers from both forward and aft aircraft doors at the same time can be achieved.

Disadvantages: It requires larger gate position area particularly along the terminal building frontage and would require relatively long loading bridges.

Figure 8: Parallel Parking – Aircraft Parking Configuration

Source: Neufert Architects' Data Edited by Rudolf Herz, FRIBA, Dr Ing. (Berlin) pg. 259

2.16. AIRCRAFT FUELING

Aircraft fueling operation is usually carried out at the apron by fuel trucks, fueling pits and hydrant systems. The use of fuel trucks is predominant in small airports but in recent times, the use of hydrant systems in large airports is most favourable.

2.16.1 Fuel Trucks

This entails the use of fuel trucks to fuel an aircraft anywhere on the apron. The major advantage of the fuel truck over the hydrant system is its flexibility. The fueling system is relatively

economical. Its major disadvantage is the large number of vehicles that would be present during the fueling of large aircraft at the apron at peak periods as this would create a potential hazard of collision with personnel, other vehicles and aircraft. These trucks also constitute a potential fire hazard when moving around on an apron. The trucks are large and therefore take up valuable space in the operations area. An empty fuel truck must always return to the storage area for refuelling and therefore extra trucks must be provided for use when other trucks are being reloaded.

2.16.2 Fueling Pits

In this system, fuel is channelled from pits located at the gate positions on the apron through pipelines from a central fuel storage area located adjacent to the landing area. A fuel pit consists of a meter, air separator, hose reel and filter. Fuel is transferred to the pits by pumps located at the storage tanks and the pits are located relatively near the fuel intakes in the wings of the aircraft. The advantages of fuel pits are that a continuous supply of fuel is available at all times, it safely carried underground and trucking is eliminated from the apron. The disadvantages are that for each pit a separate meter filter and reel are required thus there is a duplication of equipment. A change in future operations at the airport may require a major change in installation. The maintenance cost for concrete-pad steel pit will be high due to intrusion of moisture. For fueling larger aircrafts, bulkier fueling pits are required.

2.16.3. Hydrant System

This consists of the same elements as the fuel pits except that the pit is replaced by a special valve mounted in a box in the pavement and flushes with the surface. The major advantages of the hydrant systems are the same as that of the fueling pit system. Additional advantages are

eliminating the need for duplicating the hose reel, meter and filter which are required in each pit, reducing possible collision damage to a minimum, eliminating the need for maintaining pits and providing flexibility as regards the dispensing of fuel to aircrafts. It is important to note that in all three cases, fuel is provided from a central fuel storage area located in the vicinity of the landing areas.

2.17. RUNWAY DESIGN

The design of the runway is done in the following order:

1. Runway orientation
2. Runway length calculations
3. Runway pavement
4. Runway marking
5. Runway lightings

The steps while designing is as follows:

1. RUNWAY ORIENTATION.

The number and orientation of the runways play an important role in the overall arrangement of various components of an airport. The number of runways will depend on the volume of air traffic while its orientation will depend on the direction of the wind and sometimes on the extent of area available for the airport development.

2. RUNWAY LENGTH CALCULATIONS.

The runway is designed to carry the takeoff and landing of the largest aircraft in the world A380. The categories of the runway and their corresponding length and width have defined by —INTERNATIONAL CIVIL AVIATION ASSOCIATION (ICAO). A380 falls under the category 4F and the minimum take-off run is 2700m and the width of the runway is 60m.

Figure 9: Umuleri Wind Rose

Source: www.meteoblue.com

The runway length is calculated under two constraints:

1. Basic runway length
2. Actual runway length

a. Basic runway length

Basic runway length is the length calculated under the following assumed conditions,

- a) Airport altitude is at sea level
- b) Temperature at the airport is standard
- c) No wind is blowing on the runway
- d) Runway is levelled in the longitudinal direction
- e) Aircraft is loaded to its full capacity
- f) Enroute temperature is standard
- g) No wind is blowing enroute to the destination

Basic runway length is determined from the take-off performance charts and is greater of either:

- a) **When one of the critical engines fails**, the pilot has an option to continue the run or abort the take off after attaining a certain speed called as the decision speed, if he aborts the takeoff then the takeoff run and the stop distance should be equal. If both the lengths are equal then the total length is called as the balanced field length. (Kaustubh et al. 2014)

Take off speed (v) = 280km/hr

The decision speed is less than or equal to the take off speed

Decision speed \leq Take off speed Hence decision speed, $V_f = 280\text{km/hr}$ Velocity = (280×

$1000)/3600 = 78\text{m/s}$ The acceleration is assumed as, $a=1\text{m/s}^2$

Time= $v/a= 78/1= 78$ s

Now, actual velocity is the difference between final velocity and initial velocity.

Hence, $V_a= (V_f - V_i)/2$

$= (78-0)/2 = 39\text{m/s}$

Hence, Total Distance (Take Off Run) = $39 \times 78 =$

3042 m... (1)

b) When all the engines are operating:

115% Of Take Off run = $(115 \times 2700) / 100$

$= 3100$ m... (2)

Taking maximum value of (1) and (2),

Hence, Take Off Run from aircraft's performance =

3100m

Now, the landing length requirement

Landing Run = 2050 m; Hence safe

Sources: Kaustubh, 2010

b. Actual Runway length:

Actual runway length is the length obtained after applying the corrections of temperature, elevation and slope. The actual runway length should be adequate to meet the operational requirements of the aircrafts for which the runway is designed and should not be less than the

longest length determined by applying the corrections for local conditions to the operations and performance characteristics of the relevant aircraft. Local conditions that have to be considered are temperature, elevation, slope and humidity and runway surface characteristics. The length is calculated as follows,

- i. The basic length selected for the runway should be increased at the rate of 7% per 300m elevation.**

Runway elevation at the aerodrome= 3m

Runway take off length corrected for elevation

$$= [\text{Take off run} \times .07 \times \text{Runway}/300]$$

$$= [3100 \times .07 \times (3/300)] + 3100$$

$$= 3102\text{m}$$

- ii.** The length of the runway determined should be further increase at the rate of 1% for every 1°C in the aerodrome reference temperature exceeds over standard atmosphere for the aerodrome. If however, the total correction for elevation and temperature exceeds 35% then the required correction should be obtained by means of specific study.
- iii.** The runway length is increased at the rate of 10% for each of 1% of the runway slope, where the runway length is greater than 900m.

3. WIDTH OF THE RUNWAY.

The width of the runway = 60m

Runway shoulders: Runway shoulders must be provided to ensure a transition from the full strength pavement to the unpaved strip of the runway. The paved shoulders protect the edge of the

runway pavement, contribute to the prevention of soil erosion by jet blast and mitigate foreign object damage to the jet engines.

Width of the runway shoulders = 7.5m on either side of the runway

4. RUNWAY PAVEMENTS.

The pavements in general are classified as flexible and rigid pavements according to their structural action. The black top pavement including gravel and water bound macadam follow the flexible group and the cement concrete pavement is the popular example of rigid pavement. Flexible pavements may consist of a relatively thin wearing surface built over a base course and sub base course, and they rest upon the compacted sub grade. Rigid pavements are made up of Portland cement concrete and may or may not have a base course between the pavement and sub grade.

5. RUNWAY MARKINGS

The markings on the runway help the pilot during the aircraft operations

a. Threshold Markings

Commence 6m from both sides of runway ends

2.1m from either side of edge of runway

Number of strips=16

Length of each strip=30m

Width of strip=1.80m

Gap between each strip=1.80m

b. Aiming Point Markings

One rectangular strip on either side of centre line

Distance from threshold=300m Length of each strip=50m Width of each strip=10m

Gap between strips=20m

c. Touchdown Zone Markings

Number of strip on both side=4

Length of each strip=25m

Width of strip=3m Gap between each strip=1.5m

Lateral spacing between strips on either side= 20m

d. Centre Line Markings

Length of each strip=40m

Width of strip=0.5m

Gap between each strip=35m

e. Runway Strip Markings

30m from centre line

Width = 1m

Sources: Kaustubh, 2010

Figure 10: Airport Runway Marking

Source: Kaustubh, 2010

6. RUNWAY LIGHTINGS.

- i. **Runway End Identification Lights (REIL):** Unidirectional (facing approach direction) or unidirectional pair of synchronized flashing lights installed at the runway threshold, one on each side.

- ii. **Runway end lights:** Pair of four lights on each side of the runway on precision instrument runways, these lights extends along the full width of the runway. These lights show green when viewed by approaching aircraft and red when seen from the runway.

- iii. **Runway edge lights:** White elevated lights that run the length of the runway on either side. On precision instrument runways, the edge-lighting becomes yellow in the last 2,000 ft (610 m) of the runway, or last third of the runway, whichever is less.

- iv. **Runway Centreline Lighting System (RCLS):** The lights embedded into the surface of the runway at 50 ft (15 m) intervals along the runway centreline on some precision instrument runways. White except the last 900 m (3,000 ft): alternate white and red for next 600 m (1,969 ft) and red for last 300 m (984 ft).

- v. **Touchdown Zone Lights (TDZL):** The rows of white light bar (with three in each row) at 30 or 60 m (98 or 200 ft) intervals on either side of the centreline for 900 m (3,000 ft).

Figure 11: Airport Runway Marking

Source: Kaustubh, 2010

2.18. RELATIVE LOCATION OF TERMINAL TO RUNWAYS

The key to connecting terminals to runways is for the aircraft to have the shortest possible taxiing distance;

- i.** For the single runway systems, it is desirable to locate the terminal around the middle of the runway with the distance secured for safety, if it is assumed that the number of take-offs and landings will be about equal in both directions.
- ii.** For the parallel runway system, the ideal terminal location is at the centre of the runway system.
- iii.** For the open-v runway system, the desirable location of the terminal will also be between the runway systems.

2.19. BASIC SOLUTIONS TO THE DESIGN OF AIRPORTS

The challenges associated with airport designs are that of planning in terms of the proper circulation of travellers and their luggage, as is the actual workability of the airport itself or its aesthetic appeal.

Almost every aspect of an airport design is motion-based. From the arrival to the departure, the challenges associated with the proper distribution of human and non-human activities can make the difference between a properly, functional and working airport design and one that's just a disaster waiting to happen.

Airport designs of modern day have been careful to note the defaults in the already existing ones to improve on the design problem that was either created as a result of improper analysis and study

of the workability of airport designs, or as a result of newly discovered problems that arose during the usage over time.

Airports as much as they differ in location and size all have similar challenges/problems of proper distribution of human and non-human traffics well as the esthetic appeal they bring to the urban landscape.

For proper analysis of the challenges or problems, the solutions that would be proffered to adequately contain and find a permanent solution would be to functionally design the units into which airports exist to make sure the activities within each unit does not run uncooperatively to that of another.

2.20. GENERAL DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

2.20.1 SAFETY REQUIREMENTS

The materials used in the construction of the airport terminal building must be resistant to fire hazards for some time. The materials must be incombustible, inherently non-flammable, or made flame-resistant by impregnation or proofing. Such building elements such as doors, windows, ramps, stairs and floor slabs must be adequately reinforced and the material of construction carefully chosen. It is also essential to provide many emergency exits and this is usually determined by the travel distance for evacuation, the number of persons the space/ building is required to accommodate with the standard number of persons required to use an exit at the same time, within a particular period. The doors to the emergency exits are required to swing outwards at an angle of 90° to ensure ease in the evacuation of the persons and goods. Exit widths are

calculated from the maximum capacity of the spaces within the terminal building using an assumed standard of 1.5m² per person.

It is also important that these escape routes are obvious to users of the building and positioned to allow the rapid dispersion of escaping people away from the fire hazards areas. The emergency exit area should well- lit artificially, generally equipped with emergency escape lighting and illuminated signage posted.

If lifts exist within the building, it is essential that the lift shafts be fire resistant and that wall-climber and feature lifts are constructed. For an airport terminal building, it is important that escape route, if in one direction, is no more than 18 meters while those in more than one direction are no more than 45 meters.

Exit widths required for various space sizes

Table 3: Exit Widths Required for Various Space Sizes

Number of persons	Minimum exit width (m)	Number of exits
Up to 200	1.1	2
200 to 300	1.2	2
300 to 400	1.4	4
400 to 500	1.6	4

Source: GLC (Greater London Council) Code of Practice: Means of escape in case of fire

2.20.2. VENTILATION

Ventilation is a phenomenon of nature that involves air movement or passage of air within an enclosure resulting in the exchange of stale air or used air with the fresh air within a building. It maintains and moderates the temperature of the building spaces as well as reduces the high level

of humidity within buildings. For a conducive and habitable environment within buildings, there has to be a constant exchange of air which can be achieved through cross ventilation of spaces as this will expel stale air from a space and replace it with fresh air. For an effective cross-ventilation process to occur there must be an inlet(s) and an outlet for the continual circulating fresh air. This process of ventilation can be carried out in 2 ways - naturally and artificially.

i. Natural Ventilation

Natural ventilation occurs when there is cross ventilation achieved with inlets and outlets as well as when there are differences in temperature. For proper cross-ventilation to occur the prevailing wind must exist over the site. The resultant in-equilibrium in air pressure outside the building allows for the extraction or suction of the air mass that was inside previously. This occurs by stack effect, cross ventilation, or by air passage through adjacent walls. To achieve proper ventilation within the airport terminal building, certain factors are to be considered. These include the following:

- **Orientation of building**

It is essential that the terminal building is oriented such that the longer sides face the north-east and south-west orientation to achieve maximum ventilation as the prevailing north-east trade wind and the south-west monsoon winds are directed towards these orientations. Because ventilation is not the only factor in determining orientation, other means of inducing ventilation should be provided. It is essential therefore that proper building orientation is achieved as in Nigeria; a building cannot function appropriately depending

on the unsteady power supply as this would make the building unusable in cases where a back- up supply of power is not available.

- **Size of opening**

The proper ventilation of the airport terminal building is also dependent on this factor as the larger the window opening, the more the inflow of air into the space and the sufficient exchange of air to achieve a habitable and conducive environment within the space.

The use of large inlet and outlet openings produces less air velocity through the openings and thereby creating a higher rate of airflow. Therefore, the best arrangement is a full wall opening on both sides with adjustable sashes or closing devices which can assist in channelling the airflow in the required direction following the change of wind direction.

- **Position of openings**

For effective ventilation of persons within the airport terminal building, the openings must be directed towards the body surface. This implies that the air movement must be ensured through the space mostly used by the occupants.

- **Distance between buildings**

For effective ventilation to be achieved there must be adequate space between buildings within the airport premise to avoid the unnecessary interruption or rerouting of airflow through the buildings.

- **Design of inlets**

Inlet designs affect effective cross ventilation as the way in which they are opened determines the amount of airflow through the spaces within the terminal building.

Irrespective of the type of natural ventilation adopted, it often may be defective. This is because the effective source of control over excessive natural ventilation is to shut out the passage of air. The relief arising from this control is only momentary before an extreme condition of this relief sets in, thereby causing bodily discomfort. As a result, there is a need for the installation of artificial ventilation equipment.

ii. Artificial Ventilation

This involves the use of mechanical devices such as air conditions, exhaust fans, ceiling fans, etc to effect or force the removal of air from a space. The use of these devices is to make effective what natural ventilation could not achieve on its own. Engineers estimate that for adequate ventilation the air in a room should be changed completely from one and a half to three times each hour, or that about 280 to 850 litres (about 10 to 30 cu ft) of outside air per minute should be supplied for each occupant. Providing this amount of ventilation usually requires mechanical devices to augment the natural flow of air.

The design should provide for sufficient ventilation of the spaces. Given the building size and capacity, the design of this facility should maximize effectively the use of natural ventilation, which would be complemented by artificial ventilation. Spaces enclosed by one or more external walls, where possible, should be naturally ventilated while those that are completely enclosed would resort to artificial ventilation.

Internal design temperature for the normal range of spaces should be from 23°C to 25°C in tropical climates. The standard recommended for spaces which need to cater for this purpose with control over the proportions of fresh to recycled is approximately 10-15 air changes per hour. For larger spaces used basically for lounges and waiting areas air change rates of 6-10 per hour is recommended. Air curtains may be provided over loading doors to prevent heat gains from outside for air-conditioned spaces. For efficient air distribution from high-level diffusers, high discharge velocities of 6 to 10ms-2 or 1000 to 2000ft per minute are involved and the degree of reverberation generated is not easy to regulate.

2.20.3. LIGHTING

Lighting is an integral part of architectural design of buildings. It is a major determinant of utilitarian (functional) as well as aesthetic (decorative) environment provided by the designer. It, therefore, requires proper and effective design consideration and planning. It is therefore important that adequate provision for lighting be made; daylighting sufficiently provided during the day and artificial lighting provided to support during the night.

Lighting, besides its primary function of aiding vision and illuminating spaces also boost the perception of building space. For this reason, it is required that extra care is taken in lighting to achieve the desired effect of a space.

The level of luminosity and its pattern helps direct attention to appropriate features as well as helps create a perceptive mood in an interior space. If the range of luminosity is small, the scene lacks attraction or focus and appears dull; if also the level is low, it will appear gloomy. A brightly lit interior with uniform lighting provides little emphasis or modelling. Variations in luminance are

used to provide interest and compel attention. The varying degrees of the lighting of a space are determinant on the building type and its location.

i. Daylighting

This, which is also referred to as natural lighting has its source as the sun. Daylighting is a constant occurring consideration in planning any building. It affects and defines each space individually and uniquely, depending on the function of each space and as a result, when skillfully employed, provides the architect with one of his most effective modes of aesthetic architectural expression. It can be used not only as a visual aid but also to show direction and create different scenic environments. To this effect, it is most necessary that the variation in the amount daylighting, the sun path movement, the site orientation, the exterior obstruction, climate and the adverse effects of glare is properly understood. The quality of daylight admitted into a building is dependent also on the type/design of the opening, its size placement, its operability and orientation.

- **Change and Variety**

Daylight is a constantly changing source, varying from time of day, the season of the year and the state of the weather, whether sunny or cloudy. Far from being a disadvantage, it is this variety, which provides a dynamic and appealing appearance to an interior. Change and variety are at the heart of daylighting, as is the medium through which it is delivered, the window. As mentioned earlier, the design of the window for size, type, orientation can bring about different appearances of interest to space.

Provisions for natural lighting should be made for the airport terminal building as it usually consists of large spaces which required to be adequately lit. The use of some

degree of natural lighting is encouraged for the lounges and waiting areas as it would improve the daytime working environments improve energy efficiency and drastically reduce energy costs. However, the proportion of natural lighting must be limited to avoid excessive heat gain in the building and this can be achieved by the used of automated shading devices, canopies as well as the positioning of windows away from direct solar rays to avoid glare.

ii. Artificial lighting

Just as daylight is a critical design issue, so too are artificial sources. Given today's preoccupation with daylight especially in Nigeria with regards to the epileptic power supply, it is certain that the initial decision on lighting has to relate to daylight and its interrelationship with the internal artificial lighting of the building. Artificial lighting is most widely used.

This is as a result of the fact that though natural lighting can be influenced to a certain extent with the use of shading devices, artificial lighting is completely at the mercy of the architect as it allows for control in the areas of illumination in a building space. It is essential, therefore, that artificial light sources are identified with their characteristics.

The most commonly used light sources are incandescent, fluorescent and high-density discharge.

▪ Incandescent

Incandescent lamps are available in a wide range of variety of sizes, shapes, and colour. Some standard shaped bulbs are available with a partial coating of silver to concentrate the light in one direction only. More efficient for this purpose, though, are the special inside-silver reflector lamps, available in spot (concentrated-beam) and flood type (wide-beam) projector lamps are similar but are of special construction that permits them to be used outdoors, exposed to the weather; they are

available in spot and flood types. The selection of artificial light source is controlled by the desired:

- o Color quality
- o Total output of light source
- o The life expectancy of the source
- o Amount of heat produced
- o Overall cost.

- **Fluorescent**

The fluorescent lamp is an electric discharge source in which light is produced predominantly by fluorescent powders activated by ultraviolet energy generated by a mercury arc. When the proper voltage is applied, an 'arc' is produced by current flowing between the electrodes through the mercury vapour. This discharge generates some visible radiation or light. Fluorescent lamps are available in several colours and no less than 14 'whites'.

- **High-intensity discharge lamps**

These include the groups of lamps commonly known as mercury, metal halide, and high-pressure sodium lamps. They resemble incandescent lamps in that they provide a point source light, but they are more closely related to fluorescent lamps since they are electric discharge lamps. They provide a point source of light of very high intensity (the entrance lobbies, ticketing and check-in area, exhibition and conference halls need this advantage) and with long-rated lives, excellent lumen maintenance and high efficacies, high-intensity discharge lamps are often the most economical (Exterior lighting for security and directional signs demand his advantage).

The height and character of the spaces determine the design of lighting fixtures within the spaces. This is required for the effective illumination of each space to different standard requirements for the spaces. The minimum service value of illumination should be 400lux (40 lumens per square foot) with switching facilities to reduce the illumination to about half if necessary. The colour corrected 1000w high-pressure mercury discharge lamps are most suitable to be in large spaces to compensate for the high-level fixing. Balanced fluorescent lighting (on battens or in suspended

luminaries) may sometimes be more appropriate. It is also very essential that separate lighting circuits be provided for each section of the spaces (especially in large spaces) to allow flexibility of control.

2.20.4. SECURITY AND COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS

In airport terminal buildings, adequate and efficient security and communication systems must be provided to ensure the safety of the passengers, their luggage as well as valuable items within the terminal building.

The bringing together groups of people who may represent valuable business interest, professional expertise, political authority, academic excellence and other sectors of influence, conferences and other meetings present a high degree of risk. Security must be provided for every user of the airport terminal building to ensure their safety, the safety of materials and equipment as well as the safety of the user's luggage.

The main areas to be considered are:

- i.** Car park and road network, which is overseen by security post.
- ii.** Controlled access and circulation in and out of the department.
- iii.** Staff entry and exit.

For this to be properly achieved, the main requirements stated and explained below should be ensured:

a) Security system

A control room is required to monitor activities within the terminal from the security cameras. This room is usually equipped with a sound control console and announcement facilities, closed-circuit television (CCTV) monitors, and fire indicator panels.

The closed-circuit television (CCTV) is to monitor activities within the terminal. The motorized cameras, mounted on swivel stands are best to ensure proper coverage of each space within the terminal building. The number of security cameras installed within spaces is dependent on the size and scale of the spaces.

Fire control equipment such as fire alarms, manual break glass units, heat and smoke detectors and automatic sprinklers must be installed. For large spaces such as the departure lounges and ticketing/waiting areas, sprinkler systems are practically essential and CO2 installation will also be required in electrical substations.

b) Communication system

This is most essential to effectively boost communication between the airline operations services and passengers, to boost communication between the airline operation services and the airport terminal staff as well as to boost effective communication between the airport terminal staff and the passengers within the terminal building. This would ensure the effective and efficient operation of the airport terminal activities. A public address system with loudspeakers should be zoned by area and adjusted for time and display balance to ensure efficient communication distribution.

2.20.5. ACCESS

All airports require good access for pedestrians, vehicles and maintenance equipment. Access routes for vehicles bringing in passengers, cargo and equipment should be adequately planned and provided. These routes should lead to the passenger parking area, to the cargo unloading docks and the maintenance areas without interference in their movement. Therefore adequate provision for parking should be provided for cars, buses, trucks, etc. It is essential also

that there exist, separate vehicular entry and exit accesses. These vehicle entries must be supervised to reduce congestion and provide some security control within the airport premise.

It is essential that doors (including entrance and exit doors), lobbies and corridors are provided headroom and width clearance. Doors may be in sections, where more sections can be opened to meet the sizes required for loading or unloading of goods, cargo and equipment as well as for emergency escape exits.

It is essential to install lifts and escalators within the terminal building to enhance ease and comfort in the transportation of passengers from one floor to another within the terminal building. It is also necessary that large, heavy-duty lifts be installed near the unloading docks at the cargo and maintenance areas for the easy movement of goods, cargo and equipment (especially heavy ones) from one floor to another. If transportation to other floors is required, must be installed for easy movement of heavy equipment and exhibition materials.

- **Access Requirements**

In planning premises which usually caters for large groups of persons, access, parking, circulation and reception requirements must be considered. For an airport, the peak arrival period preceding the activity is often very short extending over a 15-30 minutes in other regions (15-45 minutes in Nigeria). For an international airport, there is always a constant flow of high several arrivals and departures expected throughout the activity periods.

The provision of separate functional facilities and spaces for the arrival and departure activities is most essential for the effective organization of the passenger flow and effective decongestion of the passenger traffic flow within the airport terminal building. However, this should be achieved

to also allow for the quick and easy access of transit passengers from the arrival activity area to the departure activity area and vice versa.

- **Site Requirements**

In the initial stages of planning an international airport, special consideration must be given to the traffic flows along the streets adjacent to the airport premise, the possible congestion which could arise from access to the premises and feeder highways. This effect reduction of traffic congestion around the airport premise would be encouraged by the rerouting and isolation of airport traffic away from constantly congested highways and streets. Planning will normally take into account, the calculated traffic and environmental impacts.

- i. Visitor's Access**

The main access/entrance into the airport premise must be clearly emphasized and ease of recognition by visitors to the area. Car porch should be provided at the entrance of the building to allow and encourage the ease in dropping- off and picking- up of persons by cars and taxis. The route to the car porch (drop- off point) should be a one-way system of traffic flow to avoid unnecessary accidents and possible traffic congestion. Width of the carriageway must accommodate at least two vehicle lanes and a pedestrian walkway alongside. It is also necessary that additional parking is provided for VIPs and government Official.

- ii. Staff Access**

Separate staff entrance is required to restrict uncontrolled access into security-sensitive working areas. This is to ensure the safety of both staff personnel and staff facilities.

iii. Service Access

It is essential to provide separate entrances, roads and parking areas for delivery and service vehicles. This is not only to reduce traffic congestion and noise but also to screen unsightly services and activities from the visitors of the premise. Large access is therefore required to accommodate furniture vehicles, trucks, etc direct to unloading points giving easy entrance to the service areas. Space requirements for vehicle manoeuvring and waiting will depend on the scale of the service areas as well as the magnitude of the activity involved within these areas.

Services and facilities within the airport premise and the terminal building such as food, beverage, laundry, furnishings and equipment, maintenance services, cleaning, garbage and refuse disposal, gardening and landscaping etc will also require access.

2.20.6. CAR PARKING

Adequate parking facilities must be provided for vehicles entering the airport premise. Provision should also be made for both short and long term parking as persons require parking their cars within the airport premise and travel for some time. The amount of space allotted to parking is dependent on the availability of land within the airport premise and can be supported by the construction and provision of multi-storey parking buildings which would invariably reduce the area coverage of parking on the airport premise. For underground, rooftop and multi-storey car parks, elevators must also be provided along with and staircases for emergency use, both, within fire-protected lobbies, giving direct access to the main reception area. Proper kerbed footpaths, signposting and illumination for clear identification of routes to and from the car park and reception lobby must be provided.

2.20.7. CIRCULATION

In circulation planning, different public and visitor needs, the separate requirements of staff and servicing needs must be considered. Vertical and horizontal links must also be considered. Circulation is necessary for the effective distribution and movement of persons from one activity space to another.

i. The foyer

This is a circulation/ distribution space to other activity space located as the major entrance space into the airport terminal building. The foyer serves the same role as a lobby, as a break or rest when moving from one activity space to the other. The foyer should be a sound separating barrier for entry into the passenger concourse area of the airport terminal and therefore should have a high degree of sound absorption. The foyer may incorporate coffee and beverage services or small snack bars, fixed or portable, mini bookshops and should allow easy access for trolleys for the transfer of luggage from the terminal entry point to the luggage check-in area.

To provide for safety against the event of a fire outbreak, the construction must be incombustible or of low surface-flame spread and automated sprinkler system also be provided within the terminal building.

ii. Corridors

Long corridors and large areas of impersonal space should be avoided. Whilst the continuity of passages leading between areas must be maintained for direction purposes, some variations in space and finishes may be introduced.

Since these circulation spaces are provided within the airport terminal building to enhance movement, it should be properly lit artificially. It is therefore very important to provide extensive glazed areas within other activity space such as lounges, restaurants, and offices if achievable. Corridors and foyers will usually form an intermediary zone and should be provided with a wide range of light variation from daylight conditions reducing to about 50 percent at night. In larger circulation spaces, interior landscaping may be used to create features of interest and reduce exhibition fatigue.

2.20.8. ESCAPE ROUTES

Corridors, lobbies, staircases and landings must satisfy the loading requirements of means of escape from the building. In most cases, additional emergency escapes will need to be installed to evacuate the large numbers of people likely to be involved and to provide alternative routes of escape from the spaces and other parts of the building. Exit requirements are generally based on a unit width of 560mm for a person with a minimum of two units. Standards laid down by the Greater London council are typical.

Table 4: Standards for Escape Routes

Space capacity	Minimum number of exits	Minimum width of each exit and corridor	
		m	in
Up to 200	2	1.1.	43
200 to 300	2	1.2	47
300 to 400	2	1.4	55

400 to 500	2	1.6	63
500 to 750	3	1.6	63
750 to 1000	4	1.6	63

Source: GLC Code of Practice- Means of Escape in Case of Fire

The following notes should also be considered

- The width of the corridors must not be less than the aggregate width of the corridors they serve.
- Ceiling heights of corridors and passages leading to escape route must not be less than 2.06m.
- Constructional requirements for protected corridors and staircases which serve as fire escapes include standard fire-resistance (generally specified as one hour) and the use of non-combustible linings.
- All potential escape routes must have continuously maintained lighting supplied from an emergency source.
- Exits must clearly indicate the standard signs.
- In most cases, automatic sprinkler systems should be installed lobby along escape routes. The sprinklers operate at a set temperature (57°C to 71°C) and are normally fitted at intervals of about 3.6 to 4.3m.
- Additional precautions against fire include automatic smoke and gas detection linked to an alarm system, manual alarm- usually with break glass ‘mechanisms and hose reels with hydrants.
- There must be no obstructions to reduce the width of the corridor or landing. Equipment such as hose reels will need to be recessed into the walls.

- Fire-resisting doors, opening in the direction of travel are required at all points of entry and additional smoke control doors may be needed at intervals along the corridors. Such doors must be self-closing although electromagnetic door holders may be allowed to hold the doors open for normal use.

1. Staircases

Staircases should be designed with reference to design standards specified in codes and regulations to allow easy and safe escape. GLC requirements stipulate that stairs must be in straight flights with no more than 16 risers and no more than three sets of risers per flight. Clear landings of the same width of at least equal length must be provided to the top and bottom of each flight, with no more than two successive flights of ten steps (or one of more than 12 steps) without a turn. The minimum headroom (vertical) is 2.06m. Stair treads should be 300mm wide, including nosing and risers no more than 150mm high. Handrails up to 1.0m high should be provided on each side of the stairs and balustrades of 1.1m high should be provided at the landings.

2.20.9. ACOUSTICS

Like all other building types, the airport terminal building requires acoustic considerations. Acoustic must be considered in other activity spaces within the airport terminal and these spaces the lounges, galleries, lobbies and restaurants.

Every acoustical situation can be described in terms of a source of the sound, a path for transmission of sound, and a receiver of the sound. Sometimes the source strength can be increased or reduced, the path can be made less or more effective, and the receiver made more attentive by removing distractions, or can be more tolerant of the disturbance.

In an airport premise, the airport terminal building has a directional noise source from the airside and as a result, more tolerant functions should be used as a barrier for the more sensitive functions which should be located at a greater distance from the noise source. For an overhead noise source like aircraft, more sensitive rooms should be located below screening spaces and roof overhangs.

There are special acoustic phenomena associated with the following:

- **Room zoning**

Quiet rooms must be located remote from noisy rooms with fenestration not directed towards any external noise sources and with buffer circulation or ancillary spaces used to protect them from internal or external noise. Noisy rooms should be grouped to reduce the disruptive effect on the rest of the accommodation.

- **Size of rooms**

The size of space should be allotted with relation to volume per occupant and consideration of proportion- length: width: height. The reverberation times and other attributes should be considered with surfaces angled to avoid focusing or flutter echo problems when allotting spaces within the terminal building.

- Shape of rooms

Architecturally, acoustic is largely determined by the shapes and sizes of the rooms. Because of the reflective sound flow of walls, the texture and structure of the surfaces play very important functions. When not in proper check, reflected sounds can cause echo defects and others such as sound foci, dead spots and room flutter.

2.20.10. ECHOES

Sound that reaches a listener in a room by a path involving reflections from its boundaries always travels a greater distance than does sound that comes by the direct path; if the difference in these two path lengths is as great as 65ft, which corresponds to a time difference of about 0.06 second, the delay in the arrival of the reflected sound is sufficient to enable a listener to hear it as a separate sound. This separate sound which the delay reflection produces is called echo.

Delayed reflections are most detrimental when they are concentrated or focused by a highly reflective concave surface. In contrast, they are least damaging when diffused by convex surfaces. In other words, if these delayed reflections are sufficiently attenuated through absorption or divergence, their blurring effects become negligible.

Reverberation within spaces

Reverberation is the gradual decay of sound in a room after the source of sound has been shot-off. The time between the cessation of the source of the sound and the instant the loudness has fallen below the audible limit is known as the time of reverberation. This time of reverberation depends on the volume of space and of sound absorption within it. It will, therefore, serve best to have an absorbent chamber to make the time of reverberation as short as possible. However, if it becomes very absorbent, space will be very fatiguing to speak in, for the sound is disturbed and absorbed so rapidly that it is difficult to maintain an overall loudness. Reflecting surfaces not only prolong the duration of the sound, but they also add to the general intensity while the source is still in action.

i. Reverberation within spaces

The size of space should be allotted with relation to volume per occupant and consideration of proportion- length: width: height. The reverberation times and other attributes should be considered with surfaces angled to avoid focusing or flutter echo problems when allotting spaces within the terminal building.

ii. Absorption of sound

It is, therefore, necessary that a compromise should be struck with regards to the amount of absorption that should be introduced into the space within the airport terminal building to reconcile the two conflicting interests. Apart from the absorption aided by padded chairs, members of the surface of the walls, ceilings, end floors, should carry and contain sound-absorbent materials.

It is also apparent that a hall of large volume ought to have more absorption than a small one, for the sound wave have further to go between each reflection and suffer fewer reflections in a given time, and consequently are absorbed at a slower rate in a large hall, other things being equal.

iii. Noise control

The duct silencers are installed to help reduce inherent noise problems from electrical equipment such as air- conditioning systems which comprise of small ducts (duct- borne sound) and fans (airborne sound)

Vibration isolation works are required to eliminate or reduce structure-borne sound and this can be achieved either by dry friction (coulomb effect, viscous damping (shearing effect), energy lost

in a body of stressed material, or hysteresis damping. There are different types of anti-vibration mounts for equipment required to ensure vibration isolation and these include:

- Solid elastic materials used in combination with concrete inertia blocks.
- Glass fibre isolators which consist of a pre-compressed glass fibre pad enclosed in a neoprene envelope. Air pockets between the glass fibre strands provide a useful degree of damping.
- Neoprene separating pad incorporated in steel springs to ensure that there is no metal-to-metal connection.

Air springs which consist of an air-filled bag which acts as a spring between the two halves of the device

iv. Selection of materials

Materials used in finishes should be considered for their value in absorbing sound while bearing in mind other criteria such as fire hazard or hygiene. The thickness of the material, as well as its texture, will affect this characteristic. All surfaces in a space absorb sound to a greater or lesser extent. The choice of materials to finish these surfaces gives tremendous scope for controlling the acoustics of a space. Absorbent materials can be deliberately introduced. They can be divided into three main categories:

- **Porous absorbers**

This category consists of granular or fibrous materials made reasonably compact by pressing, weaving or adding suitable adhesives. Commercial products are usually manufactured from glass or mineral fibres. The absorption coefficient is usually high even at low frequencies and can be

increased both by spacing the absorbent from a rigid backing and by increasing its thickness; both of these changes also improve the low-frequency performance.

i. Panel or Membrane absorbers

This consists of a thin panel, usually plywood over air space and in front of a rigid backing. Any slab or layer of porous material in such an arrangement will tend to operate to some extent as a panel absorber. This form has a high proportion at low frequencies centred on the resonant frequency of the panel backed by the spring stiffness of the air. The absorption is increased and extended over a wider range of frequency by introducing a layer of porous material into the cavity.

ii. Cavity or Helmholtz absorbers

This consists basically of an enclosed volume of air connected by a narrow neck to the surrounding air. High absorption is obtained at the resonant frequency of such a resonator, falling off at frequencies on either side of resonance.

An extension of the Helmholtz resonator principle can be seen in porous absorbers which are covered by a thin panel in which many holes have been drilled or slots cut. Such multiple resonators are not so selective in its absorption. The introduction of the porous material is important because it reduces the spikiness of the resonance absorption and also spreads the absorption frequencies higher than resonance, particularly when the holes represent a substantial proportion of the total area.

It is therefore essential that acoustic absorption materials be installed or placed within spaces which require the absorption and neutralization of acoustic sound. These materials include thick carpets, plants upholstery in screens and seats, acoustic banners and sound-absorbing

suspended ceiling. The use of perforated fascia panels backed with sound-absorbent mineral wool quilting.

In commercial buildings, curtain walling or profiled cladding should be used for external finished to reduce or eliminate the sound insulation terminal building spaces as curtain walling have a rating of 30dB for 10mm glazing.

iii. Sound reinforcement system

These are used to amplify sounds which are otherwise insufficiently loud, either because of distance or intrusive sound or to overcome shortcomings in the acoustics of the space. A system should be considered for

Public address- several modest size speakers local to sections of the audience, with a time delay on rear loudspeakers.

iv. Light entertainment

Column wall or free-standing large speakers with powerful output, for background music, discos, etc The need for a system should be checked against the quality of hearing for direct listening and sound amplification, once the volume of the space is established. The elements to be considered in this regards are microphones and loudspeakers- position, number, direction, range of use.

Reinforcement is usually necessary for large waiting areas and lounges, lecture theatres, large assembly halls, etc.

2.20.11. DRAINAGE

An adequate drainage system for the removal of surface and subsurface water for runway surfaces is vital for the safety of aircraft and the longevity of the pavement. Improper drainage leads to the formation of puddles on the pavement surface which can be hazardous to aircraft taking-off and landing as this can result in the early deterioration of pavements.

Airport facilities must acquire airport drainage system as these will help in the following ways:

- i.** The interception and diversion of surface and groundwater flow originating from lands adjacent to the airports.
- ii.** Removal of surface runoff from the airport.
- iii.** Removal of subsurface flow from the airport.

1. SURFACE DRAINAGE

The grade of the storm drain should be such as to maintain a minimum mean velocity on the order of 2.5ft per second to provide sufficient scouring action so that silting will not become a problem. To maintain an adequate cross-section for flow at all times, the diameter of the storm drain should not be less than 12inches.

Water from a drainage area should be collected into the storm drain through inlets. The inlet structure consists of a concrete box, the top off which is covered with a grate made of cast iron, cast steel, or reinforced concrete. The grate must support aircraft wheel loads and therefore should be designed for contact pressures for the aircraft which will be served by the airport.

On long tangents, drain inlets are usually placed at intervals varying from 200ft to 400ft. The location of the inlet depends on the configuration of the airport and of the grading plan. If there is a taxiway parallel to the runway, the inlets are placed in a valley between runways and

taxiways. If there is no parallel taxiway, the drains are placed near the edge of the runway pavement or at the toe of the slope of the graded area.

On aprons, inlets should be placed in the pavement proper. This is the only way a large apron area can be drained. All grates should be securely fastened to the frames so that they will not be jarred loose with the passage of traffic. Adequate depth of cover should be provided over the pipes so that they can support traffic.

2. SUB-SURFACE DRAINAGE

This is normally required where frost action occurs in the subgrade beneath a pavement, where the groundwater is expected to rise to the level of the base course and where the pavement is subject to frequent inundation and the sub-grade is highly impervious.

The subgrade is therefore desirable at locations where the water may rise beneath the pavement to less than 1ft below the base course.

Intercepting drainage is highly desirable where it is known that that subsurface water from adjacent areas are seeping towards the airport pavement.

The basic functions of this type of drainage are:

- To remove water from the base course.
- To remove water from the subgrade beneath a pavement.
- To intercept, collect and remove water flowing from springs or previous strata.

2.20.11.1. METHODS OF DRAINING SUBSURFACE WATER

Subgrades are drained by pipes installed along the edge of the pavement, and in some instances, where the groundwater is extremely high, underneath the pavements. The centre of the

subsurface drain should be placed no less than 1ft below the level of the groundwater. When subgrade drains are installed along the edges of the pavement, they may also serve for draining the base course.

Intercepting drainage can be accomplished using open ditches well beyond the pavement areas. If it is not practical, then sub- drains can be used.

2.20.11.2. TYPES OF PIPES

The following types of pipes have been used for sub-drainage:

- **Perforated metals, concrete or vitrified clay pipes.**

The joints are sealed. The perforations normally extend over about $\frac{1}{3}$ of the circumference of the pipe. The perforated area is usually placed adjacent to the soil.

- **Bell- and- spigot pipes.**

These are laid with the joints open. Vitrified clay, cast iron and plain concrete are used in the manufacture of bell-and-spigot pipes.

- **Porous concrete pipes**

These collect water by seepage through the concrete wall of the pipe. This type of pipe is laid with the joints sealed.

- **Skip pipe**

This manufactured of both vitrified clay and cast iron is a special type of bell- and- spigot pipe which slots at the belts.

Pipe sizes and slopes

A 6-inch diameter drain is adequate unless extreme groundwater conditions are encountered. The recommended minimum slope for sub-drains is 0.15ft in 100ft. A minimum thickness of 6 inches of filter material should surround the drain.

- **Utility holes and risers**

For cleaning and inspection, utility holes and risers are often installed along the drains. It is recommended that utility holes be placed at intervals not more than 1000ft, with one riser approximately midway between the holes. The function of the riser is to be able to insert a hose for flushing the system. The function of the utility hole is to permit inspection of the pipes.

- **Gradation of filter materials**

Filter material applies to the granular material which is used as backfill in the trenches where sub-drains are placed. To permit free water to reach the drain, the filter material must be many times more pervious than the protected soil. Yet, if it is too pervious, the particles of soil to be drained will move into the filter material and clog it. A single gradation of filter material is preferred for simplicity of construction.

Filter materials tend to segregate as they are placed in trenches. To minimize this tendency, the material should not have a coefficient of uniformity greater than 20. For the same reason, filter material should not be skipped- graded. Filter material should always be placed in a moist state. The presence of moisture tends to reduce segregation.

2.21. SPECIAL DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

2.21.1. AIRCRAFT CONSIDERATION

2.21.1.1. DESIGN CONCEPT RELATED TO AIRCRAFT OPERATIONS

Advances in aircraft technology have led to improvements in the system performance of air transportation. The technical advances in speed, range and operating systems have greatly contributed to the high growth rate of the industry.

As one of the major components in air transportation systems, the airport should be able to accommodate any future changes in design and performance associated with overall improvements of the system performance.

Airlines expect the freedom to operate any type of aircraft that has low direct costs and to serve the market needs properly. Consequently, while airlines choose such aircraft types to operate to maximize their economic efficiency, the airport needs to provide landing fields for the airlines while maximizing operational safety and efficiency. Furthermore, increasing concern for environmental factors are influencing airport designs, partly through their influence on aircraft technology.

2.21.1.2. RELATIONSHIP OF AIRCRAFT DATA TO AIRPORT DESIGN

The various types of aircraft must be studied in detail to their specific characteristics in the effective design of runways, taxiways, aprons, etc. Important aircraft characteristics include:

- i.** Aircraft space.
- ii.** Runway length.
- iii.** Aircraft size.
- iv.** Weight

- The aircraft space is determined by the aircraft size. This aircraft size is determined by the passenger or cargo capacity of the various aircraft. This makes for effective planning of facilities within and adjacent the terminal building by the architect for peak hour traffic as well as adequate accommodation space for various aircraft.
- The runway lengths usually determine the standard of the airport. It also influences the extent of land required to be acquired for the construction and development of the airport.
- The dimensional criteria of aircraft are related to its fuselage length and its wingspan. These two-dimensional criteria issues (the aircraft size) determine the width of runways, taxiways, minimum distances between these traffic ways, the configuration of terminal buildings, and the size of parking aprons and aircraft hangars.
- The weight of the aircraft in use affects the thickness of the runways, taxiways and apron pavements. This also affects the choice of materials used for such construction. The greater the weight of the aircraft, the stronger and more resilient the material used in the construction of the runway.

2.21.1.3. COMPONENTS OF AIRCRAFT WEIGHT

Since weight is one of the major factors that govern the length of a runway, it is important to also understand the basic components which make up the weight of an aircraft during take-off and landings. The various weights which are referenced in airline operations are listed as follows:

- i.** Operating Empty Weight.
- ii.** Zero Fuel Weight.
- iii.** Payload.
- iv.** Maximum Structural Payload.

v. Maximum Ramp Weight.

vi. Maximum Structural Take-off Weight.

vii. Maximum Structural Landing Weight

- **Operating Empty Weight** is the basic weight of an aircraft, including the crew and all the necessary gear required for flight, excluding the payload and fuel. This is not a constant for passenger aircraft as the seating configuration of aircraft vary.
- **Zero Fuel Weight** is the weight above which all additional weight must be fuel so that when the aircraft is in flight, the bending moments at the junction of the wing and fuselage do not become excessive.
- **Payload** refers to the total revenue-producing load. This includes the weight of the passengers and their baggage, mail, express and cargo.
- **The Maximum Structural payload.** Theoretically, the maximum structural payload is the difference between the zero fuel weight and the operating empty weight. The maximum payload carried is usually less than the maximum structural payload because of space limitations. This especially true for passenger aircraft, in which seats and other items consume a considerable amount of space.
- **Maximum ramp weight** is the maximum weight authorized for ground manoeuvre, including taxi and run-up fuel. As the aircraft taxis between the apron and the end of the runway, it burns fuel and consequently loses weight. The difference between the maximum structural take-off weight and the maximum ramp weight is very nominal, only a few thousand pounds.

- **The maximum structural take-off weight** is the maximum weight authorized at brake release for take-off. It excludes taxi and run-up fuel and includes the operating empty weight, trip, reserve fuel and payload.
- **The maximum structural landing weight** is defined as the structural capability of the aircraft in landing. Normally, transport aircraft are structurally designed for a weight less than the maximum structural take-off weight. This is so because an aircraft loses weight en-route by burning fuel. This loss in weight is considerable if the journey is long.

Table 5: Average Payload of Transport Aircraft

AIRCRAFT	PAYLOAD, TONS
DC-3	2.40
DC-4	7.00
DC-7	9.00
B707-120	17.90
DC -9-80	20.10
DC -8-61	22.00
B757- 200	26.60
DC -10-10	33.00
B767- 200	34.90
A-310	35.20
B747	44.00
L 1011- 500	48.90

Source: Planning and Designing of Airports, pg.67

2.21.1.4. EFFECT OF AIRCRAFT PERFORMANCE ON RUNWAY LENGTH

Runway lengths continually increased up until the 1960s to accommodate faster and larger aircraft. In recent times, the improvements in aircraft engine techniques (like the turbofan engine aircraft) led to the stabilization and even decrease of the runway lengths in the 1980s and the 1990s. Until the 1960s, airlines had not selected the type of aircraft to operate with consideration for economic efficiency of low operating costs.

Generally, long-range aircrafts influence the land area required at an airport as it requires longer runways for taking-off and landing. The required field length for each aircraft types is determined on the basis of the aircraft's design capability, its weight and by the safety regulations.

The required strength of the landing field is determined by the weights of operated aircrafts which include the operating empty weight, the payload, trip fuel and fuel reserve. The landing weight of an aircraft is the sum of the operating empty weight, the payload and the fuel reserve which should not exceed the maximum structural landing weight of the aircraft. The take-off weight of an aircraft is the sum of the landing weight and the trip fuel and should not exceed the maximum structural take-off weight of an aircraft.

The distribution of the load/ weight between the main gear and the nose gear depends on the type of aircraft and the location of the centre of gravity of the aircraft and the data related to the weight of each aircraft type such as maximum structural take-off weight, maximum landing weight, operating empty weight, zero fuel weight, etc is usually published by airport manufacturers.

The field length of a runway includes both actual landing length and the safety margin which both consists of the full- strength pavement, the partial- strength pavement or stop way and the clearway- whose upward slope should not exceed 1.25%.

2.21.1.5. AIRCRAFT SIZES

The sizes of aircraft and their relevant dimensions and operative variables are important factors in the design of runway lights, aprons, runways, taxiways, and other aircraft handling facilities. The aircraft size determines the width of runways and taxiways and the distances between these traffic ways, and it affects the required turning radius on pavement curves.

Therefore, the aircraft dimensions, defined by the wingspan and the fuselage length, influence the size of the aircraft movement area and the configuration of the terminal building. The length of the fuselage is the factor that determines queuing distances and the spacing of pre-take-off waiting areas.

The following states the important characteristics of some major aircraft in use today.

These characteristics are:

- i.** Passenger capacity.
- ii.** Minimum turning radius.
- iii.** Positions of important technical installations.
- iv.** Aircraft general dimensions.
- v.** The specific type of aircraft.

Table 6: Gate Lounge Sizes Required by Each Aircraft

GATE LOUNGES	SIZE (M2)
B-747	1828.80
L-1011	1219.20
DC-10	1219.20
B2702	1219.20
DC-8	1066.80
B-707	1066.80
B-737	609.60
B-727	609.60
DC-9	457.20

Source: Time- Savers Standard for Building Types, pg.946

Plate 2.15: F50 Aircraft Size

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas Walliman,

pg. 447

Plate 2.16: B727-200 Aircraft Size

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas Walliman, pg.

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Plate 2.17: B757-200 Aircraft Size

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas Walliman, pg.

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Plate 2.18: DC-10/30 Aircraft Size

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas Walliman, pg.

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Plate 2.19: B747-400 Aircraft Size

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas Walliman, pg.

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2.21.1.6. TURNING RADII

The medium radius swept by the extremity of the aircraft determines the size of the apron and parking space. In determining aircraft positions on the apron adjacent to the terminal building and establishing the paths of aircraft at other locations on the airport, it is important to understand the geometry of aircraft movement when taxiing.

Turning radii area functions of the use-gear steering angle, and depends on the aircraft size and configuration. The larger the nose-gear steering angle, the smaller the radii. From the centre of rotation the distances to the various parts of the aircraft, such as the wingtips, nose, or tail, result in a number of radii; the largest radius is the most critical factor from the standpoint of clearance to buildings or adjacent aircraft.

The minimum turning radius corresponds to the maximum nose-gear steering angle specified by the aircraft manufacturers. The maximum angles vary from 60° to 80°. Minimum turning radii are not used in practice very often because the manoeuvre produces excessive tire wear and in some instances result in surfing of the pavement surface. The width of taxiways is influenced by the track width between the wheels and the spacing of taxiways is determined mainly by the wingspan.

The chart below gives the maximum turning radii for some aircraft.

Table 7: Typical Passenger aircraft Turning Radii

AIRCRAFT	MAXIMUM Steering angle°	Wing Tips (RADII M2)	Nose (RADII M2)	Tail (RADII M2)
DC-9-32	82.00	16.92	18.66	5.94
B727-200	78.00	21.67	24.23	24.38
DC-8-63	67.00	33.65	30.18	33.44

DC-10-10	68.00	34.26	31.88	30.79
B747A	70.00	42.67	33.22	41.76

Source: *Planning and Design of Airports*, pg.81

Plate 2.20: Aircraft Dimensions and Turning Radius Requirements

Source: *Planning and Design of Airports* by Robert Horonjeff & Francis X. McKelvey, pgs.

59,384

2.21.1.7. DESIGN CONCEPT FOR SAFETY AND SECURITY

The objective of aviation safety in the airport consists of two elements. These are:

- i. To reduce the frequency of accidents.
- ii. To reduce the severity of each accident.

To achieve these objectives, an extended runway safety area or clear zone should be constructed and maintained since it is recognized that most airport accidents occur within 150 meters of the runway centreline and 900 meters of the end of the runway. Ashford and Wright (1992) insisted that the runway end safety area should be extended to 600 meters in width at the boundary. Many pilots and air safety experts have recommended that the longitudinal gradient of the runway should be limited to 1% and a runway crown of 1% to 1.5% should be provided to provide adequate drainage under adverse weather conditions.

It is also necessary to maintain a fire department to reduce the severity of accidents. A fire station should be located close to the midpoint of the runway and should be designed according to governmental regulations, with alarm systems and elevated watching office.

2.21.1.8. DESIGN CONCEPT FOR ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

To ensure that the airport has a sustainable future, the environmental problems related to airport operations should be considered in the designing stage of the airport development.

Various regulatory systems are usually operated by the government to protect their people from environmental hazards which would include the preparation of an environmental impact statement by the airport developer.

If it is determined that the airport development would not have a significantly negative effect on the environment, then the document would be made available to the public on request.

The environmental impact statement should include the temporary impact related to the construction process as well as the permanent impacts related to the future airport operation and its surrounding environment. This statement is frequently required to describe the area of potential disruption and the impact on sea and wildlife sanctuaries, scenic and recreation areas, historical sites, etc.

The probable environmental disruption in and around the airport are noise, air pollution, water pollution and waste. There are general countermeasures available to lessen the undesirable effect of noise in the vicinity of airports. They include aircraft technology, aircraft operation in and around the airport, airport planning and design, and land use in the airport vicinity.

Air pollution results from the emissions from aircraft and vehicles, fugitive emissions from fuel farms, etc. Water pollution is mainly caused by a de-icing product, herbicides, effluent from aircraft and vehicle maintenance and sewage from the terminals. The wastes produced in an airport are caused by aircraft waste, engineering and construction waste and waste from the terminal.

2.22. AIRPORT CONFIGURATION- AIRSIDE DESIGN

The globalization of the economy relies increasingly on air transport with airports acting as the main technical support. The growth of air traffic in terms of passengers and freight has placed increased pressure on existing airport terminals. Existing airport terminals have been expanded while the new passenger terminals have been constructed to replace airports no longer able to cope with the increased traffic flow in airports. The sizes and capacity of such new airports

to be constructed can be determined by several factors. It is, therefore, necessary that primary factors influencing the size of an airport are determined. These factors include:

The performance, characteristics and size of aircraft expected to use the airport.

- i. The anticipated volume of traffic.
- ii. Meteorological conditions.
- iii. The elevation of the airport site.

2.22.1 AIRPORT CAPACITY

This is an operational problem concerned with two aspects of capacity; the provision of adequate runways, and terminal capacity. Until recently, most studies took runway capacity as the key measure, but the advent of wide-body jet airliners such as the Boeing 747 or the Lockheed Tristar has enabled a larger number of passengers to be handled for the same number of aircraft movement. This aircraft movement has tended to rise at a slower rate than passenger numbers, making terminal capacity more critical.

Airport capacity is an index of the performance and capability of an airport. For planning purposes airfield capacity has two main definitions; one states that capacity is the number of aircraft operations during a specified interval of time corresponding to a tolerable level of average delay; the other states that capacity is the maximum number of aircraft operations that an airfield can accommodate during a specified interval of time when there is a continuous demand for service.

- i. **Freedom of Maneuver:** This is a rather elemental item in capacity analysis, freedom of manoeuvre for approach and departure in the vicinity of the airport.

- ii. **Effect of Turn-offs:** This is another important factor, though not enough is known about its effect on capacity. If runways are to achieve maximum capacity they must be designed with a taxiway system which will permit aircraft to clear the runway promptly, leaving the exits free for succeeding aircraft. With close parallel runways, there must also be adequate space to permit taxiing between the runways and holding to cross the second runway.
- iii. **Crosswind runway:** One problem to capacity operations is the inadequate design of crosswind runways. An adequate design provides substantially the same capacity in the crosswind direction as in the major direction of operation in the airport.

The airport capacity would help in the proper definition of the scale of airports and the required capacity they can accommodate. Therefore, the geography of air terminals is embedded at two scales: The domestic scale and the international/regional scale. For this thesis, emphasis shall be laid on the international/ regional scale.

2.22.1.1. INTERNATIONAL/ REGIONAL SCALE

At this scale, the airport site represents its role and function in the international and regional urban system. As a component of the global air transport system, the location of an airport expresses its centrality (being an origin and destination of air traffic) and intermediacy (a hub or gateway between destinations). This consideration is strategic and linked with future growth in passengers and freight traffic. An international airport should have a standard runway of about 4000 meters (13000ft).

This also concerns the level of accessibility of the airport over the metropolitan area of services. Such considerations are mainly operational and linked with daily flows of planes, passenger, and freight to and from the airport terminals.

Site requirement is extremely important for air terminals as its two major components, the airfields and the terminals. Each component has specific requirements:

i. AIRFIELD (LAND SIDE)

The airfield is defined as the system of components on which aircrafts operate. This is the physical site of the airport concerned with servicing aircrafts, which include the runways and parking areas. The runways must be long enough to adequately accommodate the taking- off and landing of commercial planes. A Boeing 747 requires about 3300 meters (11000 ft) of runway for effective take-off and landing. Other features such as the slope, (less than 1%), the altitude (influences the length of runways because of air density) and meteorological conditions (temperature, precipitation, prevailing wind, visibility, etc) also influence site selection.

About 32 movements (landing and take-offs) per hour are possible on a commercial runway under optional conditions.

ii. TERMINAL (LAND SIDE)

The terminal is composed of freight and passenger transit infrastructures as well as infrastructures for aircraft accommodation. They also link the local transport systems, which often involves such terminals as a passenger rail station within or adjacent the airport terminals.

Airports require very large sites not only for landing and taking-off of aircrafts for terminals, but also as a buffer between the adjacent urban areas to limit the noise generated. Parking areas in airports located in car-dependent cities are also substantial and may take more space than the terminal themselves. The minimum sizes for an international airport site should be

about 500 hectares. This consideration has two direct effects on the international airport location. These include:

a. PERIPHERAL SITES

Airports are sited at the periphery of urban areas because it is at these locations that sufficient quantities of land are available. The more recently an airport was constructed, the more likely this airport is to be located far from the city centre of the metropolitan area it services.

b. EXPANSION AND RELOCATION

This is extremely difficult for airport facilities. Most airports have grown at locations chosen in the 1950s and 1960s, at sites that were then on the urban fringe. Since then, airports have served as growth poles drawing commercial, industrial as well as residential developments to those sectors of the city. This results in the fact that most airports are now surrounded with limited possibilities for expansion. The only sites available for new airport development are frequently so far from the urban core that even for planning permission to be obtained to develop these sites, it would lead to very significant diseconomies because of the distance from the business and demographic cores of the city.

Table 8: Main Configuration of Terminal According to Size and Capacity

Regional	Up to 1 million passengers per year.	Single deck road, single or 1½ level terminal, apron access to aircraft.
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National	1-5 million passengers per year	Single deck road, double level terminal, elevated access to aircraft.
International	Over 5 million passengers per year	Double deck road, 2-4 storey terminal, elevated access to aircraft.

2.23. PASSENGER FLOW

The passenger flow within the airport terminal follow basic directions which enable the efficient transit of passengers from the airport terminal (ground access system) to the aircraft (air transportation system) and these are as follows:

i. ENTRANCE PORCH AND FOYERS

These are located along the car porch and serve as weather buffer for passengers entering and leaving the building terminal and therefore are found at the entrance of departure halls and exit of arrival halls. The size of an entrance porch or foyer is dependent on its intended usage. As entrances and exits they may be relatively small while as sheltered public waiting areas, they should be large enough to meet the airport standard needs as these facilities are designed to process both passengers and visitors during peak hours. The physically handicapped must be considered in the design of these units.

ii. THE CONCOURSE/ TERMINAL LOBBY AREA

From the entrance porch, the passengers or visitors move into the concourse or terminal lobby area. This is a large space where people can gather in the terminal building. It accommodates other functions which are most important to the air traveler. The functions which this space accommodate for the passenger departure include the passenger ticketing area, the passenger and visitor waiting area and baggage check-in claim facilities, airline offices, flight insurance concessionaries, porter 's room and common facilities. It also usually has such amenities as the baggage trolley and wheel chairs available as well as departure information board.

The concourse for the passenger arrivals also requires preferably a separate visitor's area, airline counters and offices, taxi and hotel reservation facilities (which could be desk or direct telephone services), entertainments, tourist information agencies and porter's room. It also usually has such amenities as baggage trolley and wheel chairs available, message board, arrivals information board, customs enquiry office as well as common facilities.

iii. AIRLINE TICKET COUNTER AND TICKET OFFICE SPACE

This is the area within the concourse, at the airport where airline and passenger make final ticket transactions and check in baggage for a flight. This includes the airline ticket counter, the airline ticket agent service area, the outbound baggage- handling device, and the support office area for the airline ticket agents.

There are three (3) types of ticketing and baggage check- in facilities and they include the linear, the pass- through and the island type facility.

For the linear counter, the ticket transaction takes place at the ticket counter, which is usually a stand- up desk. To the left and right of the ticket counter position, a low shelf is provided to deposit,

check in, tag and weigh baggage if necessary for the flight. Subsequently, the baggage is passed by the agent to an outbound baggage conveyance device located near the counter. The total number of ticket counter positions required is dependent on the level of peak- hour originating passengers, the type of facilities provided, i.e., multipurpose, express baggage check- in, ticketing only, and the queues and delays acceptable to the airlines. The sizing of the counter length depends on the mix of position types.

The pass-through and island counters, are similar in counter lengths and the number of positions but are different in geometric arrangement. In pass- through ticketing and baggage check- in facilities, queuing is along the length of the counter while in the island ticketing and baggage check- in facilities, queuing is in lines at the various ticketing positions.

The support area of the concourse area may be consisting of smaller areas for the operations and functions of accounting and safekeeping of the tickets, receipts and manifest, communications and information display equipment and personnel areas for rest, personal grooming and training. On the wall behind the ticket agents, information displays are posted for the latest airline information on arriving and departing flights.

iv. COMMON FACILITIES

These are facilities which are usually found within the concourse include 24-hour banking and currency exchange, public toilets, catering (restaurant, buffer, bar, coffee lounge), public telephones, cyber café facilities, airline and club lounges, etc.

v. VERY IMPORTANT AND THE COMMERCIALY IMPORTANT

PASSENGERS 'FACILITIES

These include such facilities as the nursery, general sitting and waiting area, first- aid medical facilities, car rental- return office, lost property room, place of worship, newsreel and television rooms, airport information desk, luggage lockers, writing desks, public address systems, clocks and direction signs and concessionaries (hairdresser, news agent, chemist, florist, shoe repair and shine, souvenirs, vending machines, advertising, etc).

vi. VISITORS' FACILITIES

In addition to the above facilities, viewing galleries and lounges should be included in the airport terminal facilities.

vii. SECURITY

The passengers move from the concourse area to the security area as security screening of all airline passengers is an extremely important function to be carried out in an airport terminal. Security screening of passengers and hand luggage is performed prior to entering the pre- flight assembly area and prior to boarding airline aircraft (i.e.in corridors leading to gates or/ and at the boarding gate). The pre- flight assembly area is also called sterile area.

viii. IMMIGRATION AND CUSTOMS CONTROL

The passengers move from the security area to the immigration and customs are where the validity of their passport and identity of each passenger are verified as well as the content of their luggage identified and certified. There are usually such facilities as the immigration desks and associated

offices, detention room(s), and amenities, customs desks and associated offices, secure store and amenities.

ix. PRE- FLIGHT ASSEMBLY AREA/ DEPARTURE LOUNGE

From the immigration and customs area, the airline passengers move to the departure lounge. This serves as an assembly area for the passengers waiting to board a particular flight and also as the exit passageway for deplaning passengers. It is usually designed to accommodate the number of boarding passengers expected to be in the lounge 15 minutes prior to the scheduled departure time. Space to accommodate seating for the passengers as well as space for airline processing, passenger queuing and an exit way for deplaning passengers are usually provided. The airline-processing area usually provide at least two (2) positions for narrow- body aircraft and up to four (4) positions for wide- body aircraft to minimize queuing lengths extending into the corridor.

Table 9: Departure Lounge Area Space Requirement

DEPARTURE LOUNGE AREA, SQUARE METERS			
Boarding Load Factors			
Aircraft Seating Capacity	35-45%	55-65%	75-85%
	(M ²)	(M ²)	(M ²)
Up to 80	33	48	63
81 to 110	56	79	102
111 to 160	79	109	139
161 to 220	111	149	186
221 to 280	139	186	232
281 to 420	204	279	353

Source: Time- Savers Standards for Building Types, pg.958

x. **AIRCRAFT**

When aircraft boarding begins, the passengers move from the departure lounge through a corridor to the aircraft.

It is necessary to not that corridors/ lobbies which are an integral part of the terminal design are used to provide passenger and visitor circulation between the departure lounge and the central terminal areas. They should therefore be designed to accommodate physically handicapped persons during the peak periods of high- density flow.

For the deplaning passengers all passenger flow as described above occurs in a reverse manner (i.e. from the aircraft to the health area, to immigration area, to baggage re-claim, to customs area to the concourse and then the entrance porch).

xi. **HEALTH AREA**

The deplaning passengers enter the health area immediately they step into the terminal building. In this area, they are briefly questioned and quickly tested to verify the non- existence of any form of disease in the bodies.

xii. **BAGGAGE RECLAIM AREA**

In this area, the deplaning passengers claim their luggage in order to be properly cleared when they arrive at the customs area.

It is also necessary to note that for international airports, it operations require space for the inspection of passengers, aircrew, baggage, aircraft and cargo respectively and that the area required for customs, immigration, agriculture and public health services may be in a separate facility or within the terminal building.

Plate 2.21: Enplaning Passenger Flow Diagram

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas Walliman, pg.

Plate 2.22: Deplaning Passenger; Flow Diagram

Source: Neufert Architects' Data (Third Edition) by Bousmaha Baiche & Nicholas Walliman, pg.

2.24. AIRCREW FLOW

The following principles govern the flow process of aircrew in the terminal and these include:

- i. The spaces where airlines require crew members to report before or after flight should be closely located to other aircrew activity spaces, preferably at ground level on the airside of the building and readily accessible from the apron.
- ii. Facilities for briefing aircrew and filing flight plans should be easily accessible to the aircraft stands. Operating crew members should not be required to report personally to the meteorological or air traffic service office, particularly during short transit stops, but, if the need arises, a communications link with these offices should be available to crew members near their gate position.
- iii. The government control clearance section for aircrew (if required) should be arranged to permit rapid processing of crews through controls and should not interfere with passengers' clearance section.

2.25. BAGGAGE HANDLING SYSTEM

This operation entails the collection, sorting and distribution of baggage. There should be adequate facilities to allow an easy conveyance of baggage to arriving passengers.

For the enplaning baggage the activities include:

- i. The conveyance from baggage check-in points to the central sorting area.
- ii. The sorting of the baggage according to the aircraft on which it departs.
- iii. The conveyance of sorted baggage to the appropriate aircraft position.
- iv. Loading of the baggage into aircraft.

For deplaning baggage, the activities include:

- i. Unloading baggage from aircraft.
- ii. Conveyance from aircraft gate position to central sorting area.
- iii. Sorting to identify transfer and claim baggage.
- iv. Conveyance of arriving baggage to baggage claims halls, where passengers collect their luggage.

There are several mechanized systems of processing baggage. The conveyance of baggage to aircraft is mainly by use of wheel container dollies or baggage carts. Baggage claim facilities vary in sophistication and complexity depending on the volumes of passenger and baggage to be handled.

This baggage reclaim facility include the following:

- i. Circular carousel baggage facility.
- ii. Oval carousel baggage facility.
- iii. Race track baggage facility.
- iv. Linear track baggage facility.

In planning for baggage claim area sufficient space need be provided to facilitate easy claim while passengers assemble and wait for their baggage. Therefore, in providing space for a baggage handling system, the architect must have a complete understanding of each airline operation and the relationship of all the airlines combined.

There are criteria for effective baggage handling. These include the following:

- i. Avoid baggage flows crossing passenger flows.
- ii. Place baggage sorting alongside apron area.

- iii. Avoid turns and level changes.
- iv. Keep conveyor slopes below 15°
- v. Minimize the number of handling operations.
- vi. Provide for safety and security at each.

Plate 2.23: Circular Carousel Baggage Reclaim System

Source: New Metric Handbook edited by Patricia Tutt & David Adler, pg. 66

Plate 2.24: Oval Carousel Baggage Reclaim System

Source: New Metric Handbook edited by Patricia Tutt & David Adler, pg. 66

Plate 2.25: Racetrack Baggage Reclaim System

Source: *New Metric Handbook* edited by Patricia Tutt & David Adler, pg. 66

Plate 2.26: Linear Track Baggage Reclaim System

Source: *New Metric Handbook* edited by Patricia Tutt & David Adler, pg. 66

2.26. CARGO HANDLING SYSTEM

At a large airport, where the cargo volume is very high, it is usually processed at a cargo terminal that is separate from the passenger terminal. However, the increase in large jet aircraft operations has led to a rise in the occurrence of mixed passenger and cargo operations. This is as a result of the fact that large jet aircraft have high cargo-carrying capacities in excess of what is needed to carry passengers and baggage. Cargo is composed of both the air freight and the airmail.

- i. Air Freight: This is conveyed between the aircraft and the cargo terminal either by the carrier or by an air-freight forwarder.
- ii. Airmail: This is also conveyed by the carrier to a central airport airmail terminal facility.

Cargo handling is dependent on the type and volume of cargo handled (i.e. The size, percentage of loose freight, percentage containerized) as well as the type of aircraft in use (i.e. whether single deck, double deck, or combinations).

Incoming air freight carried on board a passenger-carrying aircraft is usually unloaded at the gate and transported to the cargo terminal while the outgoing air freight will be conveyed from the 644 terminal before the scheduled departure and has to be stored in designated areas for convenient loading when the aircraft is ready. The basic activity area for a cargo handling system area is the landside access: vehicle loading or discharge, landside terminal operation, airside terminal operation and airside access: aircraft loading or discharge. Some principal factors need to be considered while selecting a site for cargo terminal building:

- i. Road access for land vehicles or other landside transport systems.
- ii. Space for cargo aprons with expansion capability.
- iii. Minimum taxiing distances for aircraft to runways.
- iv. Airside road access to the passenger terminal aircraft stands.

- v. Airside taxing and vehicle access to the maintenance areas.

There is a basic requirement which would facilitate the cargo- handling operations. These are as follows:

- i. The provision of a large apron adjacent to the gate.
- ii. The construction of roadways which would facilitate the movement of cargo trucks between apron- gate area and the cargo terminal.
- iii. The provision of efficient loading equipment which would enhance loading and unloading of aircraft cargo.
- iv. Space for the cargo terminal buildings with expansion possibility.
- v. Adequate landside road system to the rest of the airport.

Except for documentation procedures, the principal cargo movement or operations are:

2.26.1. Export/Outbound

This involves the unloading from landside vehicles, identification and checking, weighing, measuring and labelling.

For Domestic cargo, there is pre-freight assembly and storage to freight assembly container, pallet or free-staging for dispatch and loading into aircraft. For international cargo, it is the same with domestic, except that customs clearance, and loading after initial sorting of cargo for passenger and cargo aircraft is separated in flight assembly area or staging area.

2.26.2 Import/Inbound

This involves aircraft off-loading-by vehicle from passenger terminal to the holding pre-check in, sorting and check-in area (if non-cargo aircraft).

For domestic cargo, there is a pre-delivery holding area and then delivery to landside vehicles. For international cargo, there is land storage, custom examination and clearance, pre-delivery holding area and delivery to landside vehicles.

2.28. AIRPORT TERMINAL OPERATION

The airport terminal operation is guided by its airport administration. This is only achieved with the provision of adequate administrative facilities as well as the proper training of the administrative staff. There are various departments, each of which handles specific functions or activities within the airport. These departments are subdivisions of the airport terminal facilities and they include the following

1. The operations department
2. Fire and Rescue department
3. Aviation security department
4. Medical department (aviation medical services)
5. Commercial department
6. Electrical/ Mechanical Engineering department
7. Civil and building department
8. Land, water and survey department
9. Accounts department
10. Human Resources department
11. Public affairs department
12. Meteorological department

13. Transportation department
14. Navigational aids department
15. Aeronautic Information department
16. Air traffic service department, etc.

2.29. AIRPORT TERMINAL FACILITIES

The airport terminal facilities, of which the various departments have been grouped under, are divided into the following:

- i. Airport administration facilities.
- ii. Airlines operations facilities.
- iii. General terminal support (management) facilities.

It should be noted that all airport administrative facilities need not be located within the terminal building itself; an office block can be located within the airport site, as in the case of Port Harcourt International Airport.

2.30. AIR TRAFFIC CONTROL AND TELECOMMUNICATION SYSTEMS

2.30.1. The Air Traffic Control Tower

The air traffic control tower is among the most prominent and distinctive structures at the airport. Their function is to control the skies around the airport, to organize the take-off and landing movements, and to ensure the efficient taxiing of aircrafts on the runways. Air traffic control towers need height, unobstructed views and good radar communication. Since they address only aircraft movement, air traffic control towers are positioned within the airside zone, with good visibility of the terminal building(s).

Organizationally, there are two main elements: the control room at the top of the tower circulatory means of getting to the tower- lifts, stairs, fire escapes, etc. Column free space and glare-free visibility are essential for operational efficiency. Angled glass is normally employed to reduce solar glare and sunlight reflection which may interfere with pilot sightlines. The air traffic control tower is the facility which supervises, directs and monitors the traffic at the airport and in the immediate airspace, arrivals and departure up to about 8km from the airport. Therefore, it provides visual control of takeoffs, landings and movement of all aircraft on the ground. It is also responsible for issuing clearance to all arriving and departing aircraft, providing pilots with information on wind, temperature, barometric pressure, and operating conditions at the airport; and the control of all aircraft on the ground except in the manoeuvring area immediately adjacent to the aircraft parking positions. This manoeuvring is called the ramp area. The size and facilities required will depend upon local requirements. During its construction, the height to the distance from runways and angles of vision over local obstruction should be taken into consideration. The possible extensibility of terminal if the control tower is located adjacent to it.

2.30.2. The Flight Service Stations

These are located along the airways and at the airport. The principal functions for the flight services stations are:

- i. To brief pilots before the flight and in flight, on weather, navigational aids, airports that are out of commission, and changes in procedures and new facilities.
- ii. To monitor navigational aids.

A secondary function is to relate traffic control messages between aircraft and the appropriate control facilities on the ground.

2.30.3. The Air Route Traffic Control Center (ARTCC)

The Air Route Traffic Control Centers have the responsibility of controlling the movement of en-route aircraft along the airways, routes and other parts of the airspace. Each centre has control of a definite geographical area which may be greater than 160900 km in size. The control centre is concerned primarily with the control of aircraft operating under instrument flight rules (IFR). Air traffic control centres need not be located at airports since their functions have nothing to do with the airport operations. The air route traffic control centre's geographical area is further broken down into sectors.

There could be high altitude or low altitude sector manned by one, two or three controllers depending on the volume and complexity of traffics. The average number of aircraft that each sector can handle depends on the number of people assigned to the sector, the complexity of traffic and the degree of automation provided.

Each sector is usually provided with long-range radar which covers the entire sector and allows for monitoring of separations of aircraft in the sector. Also, each sector has information on the identification of the aircraft, destination, flight plan route, estimated speed and flight altitude. These sector information details may be posted on small pieces of papers called shrimp boats or may be superimposed on the radarscope adjacent to the blips which identify the position of the aircraft.

At present, communication between pilot and controller is by voice, therefore, each Air route traffic control centre is assigned several radio communication frequencies and the controller, in turn, assigns a specific frequency to the pilot.

2.30.4. The Approach Control Facilities

This facility has the responsibility of controlling air traffic (arrivals and departures) from the boundary area of the air traffic control tower to a distance of 40 to 80km from the airport. Principally the facility receives aircraft from the Air Route Traffic Control Center and guides them to one of several airports, and by so doing performs the function of metering and sequencing aircraft to provide uniform and orderly flow to the airports. There are various degrees of automation in approach control facility and this is dependent on the volume of traffic it is handling. The area of the facility is also divided into sectors to equalize the workload of the controllers. This facility works hand- in- hand with the airport traffic control tower as this facility hands an arriving aircraft to the airport control tower when it is lined up with the runway about 8km from the airport and vice versa.

2.30.5. The Navigational Aids

The aircraft is aided in its flight operations by numerous navigational aids. These are meant to guide their respective ranges, the altitude at a particular distance, and distance from aircraft as well as position from the airport. The pilot maintains a level of communication with the airport operators who serve in different navigational departments. The communication is important if air mishaps are to be avoided or more realistically reduced to the barest minimum. For this purpose, a lot more things are installed.

The aids of aerial navigation can be classified into two main groups. These include:

- i. External aids: These are those that are located on the ground.
- ii. Internal aids: These are those that are installed in the cockpits

Some aids can be applied to flights over a landmass, there are others that can be applied to flights over the oceans, while there are those that can be used over either land or water. Some aids are used only during the en-route portion of the flight while others are used in the terminal areas or near airports.

Figure 12: Classification of Navigational Aids

Source: Planning and Design of Airports, pg. 126

2.30.6. The Telecommunication Services

The travelling passengers expect to be informed of their flight schedules, delays, times and gates to be boarding aircraft, and baggage collection points are all operated by electronic devices. This service is handled by the information services of the airport. Announcements are made from the announcement room which is addressed to the passengers. These address systems have multiple input points with speakers in every passenger activity space.

These speakers are usually concealed in the ceiling or walls and conform with the acoustic requirements of each space within which it exists. Airports are being used by people of all races

and by this, languages differ. This has encouraged the adoption of the use of signs as this is meant to help direct passengers within the airport complex. Essentially, the telecommunication facilities comprise of the following:

- i. Ground plane communication system integrated into the air traffic control system.
- ii. Point-to-point communication system integrated into the communication system of the adjacent air traffic control centres.
- iii. Multiplex carrier system for telephone outlet to or from the urban network.
- iv. Coverage system by radar for surveillance of the air terminal and main air routes
- v. Radio navigation aids for en-route and landing purposes.
- vi. The communication system in UHF for fixed mobile and portable communication utilizing time-sharing channels.
- vii. Meteorological radar system.
- viii. Tele facsimile system for meteorology.
- ix. Closed-circuit TV system for internal vigilance

2.30. STRUCTURAL CONSIDERATIONS.

2.24.1 STRUCTURAL SYSTEM

This refers to a system of holding components of a building and transferring the load through the members of a structure to provide stability and durability. This proposed airport shall consist of a skeletal frame structural system at the core and a post and beam structural systems at the wings.

2.30.2. Wind Load

This refers to the lateral load acting on the building, in this case, the wind load. The Airport will handle this load by transferring load from the cantilevered roof to the ground thereby allowing the structure to stay stable avoiding vortex and overturn.

2.30.3. Materials

The proposed airport terminal shall consist of structural steel and tempered glass as glazing to achieve a sense of openness and lightness. As well as precast concrete for roof slabs.

2.31. AIRPORT SERVICES

2.31.1. Rescue and Fire Fighting Services

Fire precaution is an important part of an airport's services. For this reason, the airport in totality is designed with fire control in mind first as a preventive measure then as a follow-up measure. As a preventive measure, it should be ensured that the materials used for the construction of building elements within the airport complex are fire-resistant while as a follow-up measure, fire stations containing rescue and firefighting equipment should be conveniently located at a strategic location within the airport premise.

It is intended that the fire station housing these rescue and firefighting equipment be normally located on the airfield. Alternately both private and public organizations suitably located and equipped may also provide the rescue and firefighting service.

At present, there is a whole range of purpose-built fire-fighting equipment availability ranging from small, rapid intervention vehicles (RIVs) to very large multi-wheel appliances.

The type and number of firefighting facilities provided at an airport depend on:

- i. The size of the airport.
- ii. The number of aircraft movement within the airport premise.
- iii. The take-off weight of the aircraft.

The location of the firefighting facilities should be such that there is:

- i. Unobstructed view and access to all airport areas.
- ii. All weather response times – 3 minutes to crash site anywhere on the airport;

It is important for personnel to be accommodated close to the fire fighting vehicles, and for staff amenities such as changing rooms to be provided. Facilities for maintenance and repair work on fire equipment should be provided.

2.31.2. Service Response Time

This is the interval between the observations of the need for immediate fire-control and the actual start of the activities by the fire- fighting crew. The operational objective of the rescue and fire-fighting services should be to achieve response times not exceeding 160 seconds and preferably between 100-120 seconds. It should also be ensured that during the design of the fire service building, provision should be made for firefighters and the rescue vehicles to leave the bays from both sides.

This response time must be achieved in all visibility and surface conditions. The response is directed to any portion of the airport including the runways, taxiways, bays, aprons, terminal buildings, etc therefore, the airport should be designed to ensure easy accessibility in times of emergency to all parts of the airport in maximum response time. Particular attention should also be given to the provision of emergency access roads in approach areas.

2.31.2.2 SERVICE EQUIPMENT

The service equipment building is associated with a group of operational services provided by airport management for planning purposes. Three principal considerations should determine the location of these functional groups of operation buildings:

- i. It must be close to the heart of airport operations for control of maintenance and service activities.
- ii. It must be accessible to airport service roads, particularly the airport perimeter road, to facilities the reach to all operational areas of the airport by the equipment without having to cross active runways.
- iii. It must be centrally located to airport pavement areas, particularly air carrier aircraft passenger loading aprons, to other public loading and servicing aprons and to landing area facilities.

2.31.2.3. SPACE REQUIREMENTS

A consideration affecting space requirements and space relationships is the advantages offered by combining facilities designed to meet airport operational needs. Sometimes it may be necessary to consolidate the housing for fire and rescue apparatus, and maintenance and service equipment, into a single building. Whichever method, however, there are always over-riding factors, such as siting and accessibility, that must be economical and satisfactory only if facilities can be made available for total needs, and other requirements met.

A full degree of isolation of facilities in different spaces within a building is essential for security reasons and functional efficiency. Therefore, a total separation of the fire departmental and equipment functional areas by full partition is necessary. Office and storage space to satisfy the needs of the fire department should be separated from similar facilities provided for service equipment operations.

- **EQUIPMENT AND SERVICE STALLS**

This houses the service equipments as storage for the servicing and maintenance of airport facilities- both movable and immovable. These stalls should wide enough to accommodate any typical service equipment. Provision should be made for such door to be wide and high enough to ensure the proper movement of facilities and service equipment during the maintenance. Stalls may be arranged to provide tandem storage of vehicles and therefore provide enough allowance between each vehicle. This would ensure the reduction of stall space occupied and create adequate space for the servicing and maintenance activities within the stalls. Functional spaces should also be provided for the following:

- **STORAGE SPACE**

This houses tools and service equipment for facility maintenance. The storage space for these tools and equipment should be adequately provided adjacent to the stall area where service of the equipment is done as this would ensure the ease in movement of such tools and equipment between the service stall and the storage area.

- **PERSONNEL ACCOMMODATION**

There should also be adequate provision for the following functional space as they complement the equipment and services stalls. These include:

- Office Space: This should be provided to ensure the presence of personnel during duty hours. This should accommodate desk(s), a few chairs, and a file cabinet.
- Locker room facilities for each maintenance and service employee: This provides a defined enclosed space for each personnel to store their personal effects or baggage as well as provides changing room facilities.
- Toilets, lavatory and shower facilities: These should be provided based on the total number of personnel.
- A multipurpose room: This could serve as employee lunchroom and lounge when off-duty or on a lunch break within the airport complex. This is circumstantial

2.32. AIRPORT MAINTENANCE

The general repair and maintenance of an airport is essential for its safety, economy, and beauty and therefore, the essence of airport maintenance should be based on a preventive repair.

A proper maintenance schedule should be worked out so that both the terminal building and attendant facilities (runways, control tower, etc) are kept in a condition which does not impair the safety, regularity or efficiency of airport facilities.

The airport maintenance can be grouped as civil, mechanical, and electrical airport maintenance. As regards civil maintenance, the surfaces of both runways and taxiways should be free from mud, dust, water, sand, oil, rubber despoites, and other contaminants which if present, should be removed as rapidly and completely as possible. Therefore, they should be maintained to retain a good and effect-coefficient of friction in wet conditions.

As regards electrical maintenance, a system of preventive maintenance of visual aids should be employed to ensure lighting and marking system reliability, transportation equipment as well as telecommunication equipment functionality. The control tower with other instrument landing devices should be continually checked for defects. As regards mechanical maintenance, the transportation equipment such as the baggage handling system and the passenger conveyor systems- escalators, the lifts should be properly maintained. The greater its sophistication the greater the maintenance skill required.

2.33. POWER AND WATER SUPPLY

The electricity consumption comes directly from the National grid power supply. In the airport it is necessary to provide a main electrical powerhouse which will contain:

- i. The main distribution board for the airport.
- ii. Airfield lighting equipment.
- iii. Emergency supply plant which should supply a power equivalent to 700- 100k.A. This may involve about 3-4 sets of generators.

In airports, the electricity supply is normally 3-4 phase which serves different portions of the airport complex. Emergency power should be in constant function and should be connected to the most essential systems to avoid possible accidents or damages both on the airside and landside.

Generally, it is important to connect the emergency power system to:

1. Intercom systems
2. Telephone PADB
3. Public address system
4. Fire alarm system
5. Airfield lighting
6. Air-conditioning tower
7. Sewage treatment plant
8. Entire air traffic control equipment
9. Pump for fire fighting
10. One-third of the total installed lighting system

Electricity is required in the apron for both servicing of engines and might also be required for starting of engines. Power can be supplied by mobile units or fixed installations. The use of fixed instalment is preferred to avoid noise and vehicular movement of mobile units. The conduits for fixed installations are buried under the apron with supply points along the conduit.

As regards water consumption, the design of the supply building should be such suited to keep the airport with constant water supply to the sanitary areas, kitchen areas, and most importantly, supply for firefighting. The building is featured with a separation between both the water tanks and the pump room. The water serves such purposes as;

- i. Fire fighting
- ii. Drinking
- iii. Sanitation
- iv. Catering

In the case of fire-fighting, the idea is to supply enough water for two to three hours of firefighting. This involves two separate reservoirs of 72m² which suffices the use of four hydrants simultaneously, while in the case of drinking water the tanks should have as net storage of 2 to 3 times the daily demand.

2.34. ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN AIRPORTS.

Approximately 70% of the energy consumed in airport terminal buildings is used for heating, cooling and air conditioning purposes; this rate is higher in countries with cold climates. Thus, the building envelope has great importance in the energy amount used, especially for heating and cooling. Some critical components for decreasing energy consumption used for heating and cooling purposes include:

- Determination of the optimum insulation thickness through life cycle cost (LCC) assessment to decrease the thermal loss under cold climate conditions (from the walls, roof and ground);
- Low thermal transmittance and high-performance windows with a suitable solar heat recovery coefficient;
- Roofs and walls with reflective surfaces for warm climates;
- A sealing level in the structure that prevents infiltration;
- Minimization of the thermal bridges on the building envelope; and
- Passive solar design.

Thermal insulation is one of the most important factors in decreasing energy usage in buildings, especially for heating and cooling purposes. Determining the optimum thickness of the insulation for the building envelope is important in terms of environment, energy saving and cost.

Insulation in the buildings is a simple yet very important energy-efficient method that can be applied in all residential, commercial and industrial areas. Thermal insulation materials have high thermal resistance to decrease the thermal flow rate of a material or composite material.

Airports consume very large amounts of energy for reasons such as the increasing number of passengers, increased airport capacities and the comfort requirements of terminal buildings in parallel to the development of aviation. There are numerous studies on energy efficiency and sustainability at airports. Balaras et al. determined that installing thermal insulation on external walls and roofs and replacing single-glazed windows with double-glazed windows in 29 airports in Greece considerably reduced the energy used to heat and cool the terminal buildings, and the initial investment cost would be returned economically within a short time period. Mardaljevic examined a roof-shadowing system installed on the 3rd Terminal building of Changi Airport and studied the maximum utilization due to daylight. Cardona et al. examined the compliance of combined heating and cooling power (CHCP) systems in terminal buildings of three existing airports in Italy in terms of energy savings.

2.34.2 Factors that affect energy consumption at airports

Factors that affect energy consumption at airports are as follows:

- Airport size (area and volume of conditioned spaces)
- Airport architecture (compact, pier finger terminals, satellite terminals, and remote satellite terminals)
- Airport location climate (average temperature, humidity, HDD, and CDD)
- Operational hours
- Terminal building insulation
- HVAC system and control unit
- Passenger and employee behavior
- Energy management

- Airport maintenance level
- Aircraft maintenance facility's Capacity
- Daylight utilization
- Solar heating utilization during winter
- Traffic density
- Passenger number
- Proper mechanical and electrical systems operations

2.34.3. Energy Renewable Sources

Renewable technologies are considered as clean sources of energy and the optimal use of these resources minimizes environmental impact, produces minimum secondary wastes and is sustainable based on current and future economic and social needs. Airports are located in optimal locations for the installation of renewable energy sources, allowing at least partial supply of their energy needs, and ensuring compliance with the highest international standards of safety. Most of the practical experiences and scientific texts define a series of renewable energy technologies that could be used in airport facilities. They are as follows:

i. Solar Energy

Solar energy is obtained directly from the Sun and the incident radiation can be harnessed through photovoltaic cells to produce electricity directly or through thermal systems to produce heat, usable for in situ electricity generation or hot water systems.

Airports are usually large, isolated and shading-free, presenting the perfect platform for the use of solar energy. The smartest way to use this type of renewable energy is found in the field of architectural integration because conventional external building materials can be replaced.

The experiences in this field are positive regarding the use of photovoltaic modules as an additional envelope element. The possibilities for the installation locations are varied: roofs, walls, carports, curtain walls, etc.

As for the possible reflections of sunlight from solar panels that may affect the vision of cabin crews or control towers, Barret et al. conclude that their effects are less dangerous than other surfaces existing at airports or surrounding areas (large groups of cars, lakes, etc.). Other studies show that deeply textured glass covers can solve this important issue.

Studies to determine the exact location of the solar panels must identify the location of the radio navigation systems to exclude unsuitable places that could block, reflect or disturb the electromagnetic signals. It is also important to study the maximum height that solar panels can reach. The location must also comply with the regulations regarding safety distances and recommendations related to areas of aircraft operations.

The effect of solar panels on biodiversity is studied by DeVault due to the potential risk of attracting birds. The author proposes a bird hazard index and concludes that this kind of safety risk is not high, and therefore it is feasible to install solar panels at airports.

The energy demand patterns at airports in sunny and warm regions correlates well with solar generation profiles during the morning. Nevertheless, the main problem with this type of energy in airports, as shown in the results of simulations in Brazilian airports by Braun et al. is the mismatch between the production of photovoltaic energy and electricity consumption in the

evening hours. Thus, the photovoltaic system is not able to cover the peak load of the network at night. To support these peaks is necessary to consider some form of energy storage technology.

The potential of this type of renewable energy is huge, and could lead to the emergence of economies of scale that could lower installation costs. Furthermore, this use at airports could generate a worldwide demand for large amounts of photovoltaic modules, which could represent a solar energy market worth billions of euros.

Wind Energy

Wind energy is potentially a very useful source of renewable energy for airports, due to the fact that airports typically contain large unoccupied areas. Examples of this type of energy source can be found at Gran Canaria Airport or at Burlington International Airport. However, airports have severe limitations on the placement of obstacles that may restrict the practical location of wind turbines near the airport, because the turbine is regarded as a physical barrier and a possible interference to radio navigation systems.

Analyzing in more detail the conditions for the implementation of wind energy in airports, it is mandatory in all cases to conduct a study of air traffic safety and radio navigation interferences, in order to choose the best location for wind turbines within the airport confine. This study will require approval by the corresponding national aviation authority. Ortega also described a general approach regarding physical dimensions of the wind turbine for the implementation of wind power in airports, proposing the best solution to use the electricity produced (i.e., as a primary source synchronized with the commercial grid). This option allows self-sufficient use of wind energy, and if the power generated is not sufficient to supply the airport it could be complemented by power supplied from the grid.

Hydroelectric Energy

This type of renewable energy source uses water power to produce energy. A typical hydroelectric scheme is not possible in the context of airports unless the airport is near a large body of water that contains usable kinetic energy potential. However, the environmental impact of developing a hydropower system near airports would make it unsuitable for most airport situations.

Geothermal Energy

Geothermal technologies utilize heat from the Earth. Airports have not been a viable source for conventional geothermal projects due to the specific geographic requirements and the focus on utility-scale electricity generation development due to its potential to be more cost effective. On the other hand, geothermal energy based on heating and cooling takes advantage of the relatively uniform surface temperature of the ground, and thus can be used as a heat sink or source.

At an airport, large amounts of land available without interaction with aircraft could be used to implement such facilities. At present, some examples of studies of geothermal energy are located at the Juneau Airport and Portland Jetport in Maine or at the Thessaloniki airport in Greece.

Biofuels

Biofuels are produced from biomass, and it is possible to utilize them in internal combustion engines, which could be used for transportation vehicles on the airside of the airport, such as the luggage transportation vehicles at Munich airport.

Biomass

Biomass is organic material that comes from plants and animals. It can be gathered by the airport (such as food waste) and recycled at the site as an energy source, for example through gasification for CHP plants, or for obtaining hot water through boilers, as at the Stansted airport [36]. Such schemes could even be extended to include the collection of waste from surrounding areas and spontaneous way, heat cool buildings or water.

Biogas

Biogas is produced from the anaerobic digestion of biomass in a natural and spontaneous way, and could be used at airports as an alternative to natural gas to heat or cool buildings or water.

2.34.4 Renewable energy sources and global efforts.

With the present trend of increased growth in the aviation industry, the conventional energy resources are depleting and emphasis has been laid by the airport operators to use renewable energy. The technology has been widely spread and the state policy support is also being extended to use these energy resources. The potential of availability of these energy resources depends on the geographical and climatic conditions available.

The interest towards the renewable energy has been shown across the globe irrespective of the country's economic position. Renewable energy Statistics states that about 200 Billion Dollars has been spent across the globe, towards new investment in renewable energy (Source: UNEP, Bloomberg New energy finance) and the difference of the investments towards renewable energy sources, from the richer to developing countries has dropped down to 17% from 250% in past 6 years.

A number of airports have taken the initiative in using the renewable energy sources. To state a few, Denver International Airport has implemented a renewable energy project that consists of a two megawatt solar panel system designed to generate over three million kilowatt hours of clean electricity annually. The London Heathrow terminal 2 has produced less than 40% less carbon emission than its predecessor by installing the photovoltaic solar panels on the roof to assist in decreasing the airports dependence on non-renewable energy supplies. A few airports purchase a portion of their electricity from renewable sources, including wind generation at Portland, renewable sources at Oakland, solar and geothermal at Zurich and solar at Austin-Bergstrom.

2.34.5. Challenges towards sustainability

Having numerous options available towards energy saving practices, implementation of the same by the airport operators is not feasible in specific to aviation sector at times owing to the below constraints .

1. High capital investment

The financial implications certainly hold the major share in initiating the energy saving concepts. This mainly happens with the smaller airports, in sense, where the total enplanements are less than 25,000. Complete optimization of the systems or the huge initial investment towards energy savings wouldn't be feasible in driving the energy efficient systems.

Measures to be implemented

- i. Energy audits and awareness programs shall be conducted.
- ii. Operations and Management assessment need to be made yearly for the effective maintenance practices.
- iii. The design of building to be taken into consideration for best available natural resource options.
- iv. Retrofits shall be used as a first step with minimum payback periods. Select optimal upgrade initiatives.

2.34.6. Regulatory requirements and policy frame work

Aviation is controlled by the regulatory bodies in terms of safety and security and is tighter in aviation than in most sectors around us.

New amendments from a large variety of the regulatory bodies, including the aviation authorities, national and local governments, put pressures on airport operations. Safety and security costs have risen to almost 60 to 70 percent of airport operating costs. The regulatory requirements shall provide clear direction which needs to be approached effectively during the planning stage for ensuring a balance between energy management and compliance requirements.

Role of Global regulatory bodies and airport operators

The regulatory bodies across the world shall collaboratively work in for a better results and common understanding between different parts of the world. Airport operators should demonstrate their commitment and collaborate with manufacturers for compliant with their requirement and implement adoption of more energy efficient systems by getting the approval from the regulators.

2.34.7. Airport image and expectations

The objective of the airport operator is to provide the facilities to passenger in terms of service, ambience, and support and enhance his overall his experience till he leaves the airport. The brand image of the airport and the raised people expectations are the challenges which are a difficult scenario to deal with. The growing competition tends the operator to compromise on the sustainable concepts.

Probable measures

- i. Creating the awareness among the passengers during implementation of the sustainable and energy efficient practices in the airport.
- ii. Customer feedback management services shall be initiated to address the concerns of the passenger
- iii. Advertising the sustainable practices and making the passengers to understand the importance of energy management. Common platform shall be established that only the energy which is being wasted is saved and not which is paying for. BIA is successful in making the stake holders and passengers to understand the energy conservation programs with stakeholders, vendors and suppliers.

2.34.8. Geographical constraints

The local conditions and the physical geometry of the airport location wouldn't be appropriate to use certain energy management practices. The renewable energy solutions for the same are minimal, owing to the constraints of the location of the airport.

What are the possible solutions?

Operation and maintenance practices to be managed effectively using energy efficient systems which could have a significant impact on the overall energy consumption.

- i. The use of technology which is critical component for facilitating the business transformation could be great help in initiating the energy management processes in these cases.
- ii. If the airport is in the design phase strategy need to be worked to identify better location of airport where one or the other renewable sources of energy is available. Technical experts view to be taken in this juncture.
- iii. Alternative renewable solutions shall be looked into.

2.34.9. Airport master plan development concepts

The energy efficient systems may not contribute to the future energy demand completely. It could only adjourn the circumstances. The only potential for successful future development is to generate the energy within the airport premises using the natural resources and then to manage them efficiently. Further support could be extended to the local communities thereby contributing to the social needs.

There is high potential for generation of renewable energy from various sources- wind, solar, biomass, and small hydro and cogeneration plants. Karnataka, India is the second main state where the maximum potential of the renewable sources are found. To speak in particular about the airports, the master planning of the airport is estimated to be almost four times of the immediate usage of the airport. In general airports would be located in several acres of land, out of which the

immediate usage would be very minimum. It would take a minimum of 20-30 years in turning out the master plan into reality. Huge potential of energy savings and abundant land resources wouldn't be used for many years. The vacant portion shall be assessed for cultivation of those trees/plants which could be used to generate energy, also not creating any safety breach, based on the prevailing soil conditions. The concept of green initiatives, non-polluting and renewable energy sources shall be evaluated and included in the master planning options based on the geographical and meteorological conditions. These areas to be reserved during the planning stage itself and need to be effectively integrated into existing or evolving energy systems. Natural energy resources such as solar, wind and bio mass would be a feasible step to start with the collaboration of nearby communities. This would also give the financial stability in crisis as the operation and maintenance costs would be considerably reduce by using these.

2.34.9. Energy Saving Strategies

2.34.9.1. Architectural Passive Elements

- High performance glazing
- Roof
- Daylight harvesting for terminal and piers

2.34.9.2. Mechanical & Electrical Elements

- CO2 Sensor Ventilation Strategies
- Baggage handling system
- Lighting Power Density (LPD)

- High Fan Efficiency and Electrostatic Precipitation Air Filters
- Daylight Sensors

2.34.9.3. Water Saving Strategies

- Rainwater Harvesting
- Air Conditioner Condensates
- Water Efficient Fittings

2.34.10. Conclusion

Efficient management of energy at airports significantly contributes towards sustainability and growth in the present depleted global environmental scenario. Every airport, be it large, medium or small has the potential to save and manage energy in a more efficient manner and implement sustainable practices. The first step is to realize the impact, understand the gaps and ‘get going green’ with the many available options. Situational awareness, technical knowhow and understanding the impact on future generation would kick start the process at all levels. This will not only benefit the airports but also contribute towards overall global economic and environmental standards. After fulfilling the energy management practices for sustainability, we have to focus on renewable energy practices and tap the biofuel resources. Necessary ‘Research and Development’ will provide better alternatives in energy efficient practices and products. Innovative and promising technology would help the aviation sector in managing energy efficiently. Many International airports have already led path towards this and set examples and high standards.

CHAPTER THREE

CASE STUDIES

3.1. CASE STUDY 1

3.1.1. MURTALA MUHAMMED INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT

Figure 13: Murtala Muhammed international airport

Source: gettyimages.com

3.1.2. General Information

Airport type

Public

Owner/Operator

Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria (FAAN)

Location

Ikeja, Lagos State, Nigeria

Hub for

- Aero Contractors
- Arik Air
- Azman Air
- Med-View Airline
- Air Peace
- Dana Air
- Ibom Air

Elevation AMSL

135 ft / 41 m

Coordinates

06°34'38"N 003°19'16"E/ 6.57722°N 3.32111°E

Runways

Direction Length Surface	Length	Surface
18R/36L	3,900m	Asphalt
18R/36R	2,743m	Asphalt

Statistics (2015)

Passengers: 6,801,623

Passenger change 2014–2015: Decrease by 7.8%. (MMIA, 2013)

Economic impact (2011): \$711 million. (MMIA, 2013)

Social impact (2011): 123.3 thousand. (MMIA, 2013)

(Sources: Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria, 2016)

3.1.3. Introduction

Murtala Muhammed International Airport (MMIA) (IATA: LOS, ICAO: DNMM) is an international airport located in Ikeja, Lagos State, Nigeria, and is the major airport serving the entire state. The airport was initially built during World War II and is named after Murtala Muhammed, the 4th military ruler of Nigeria.

The airport at Ikeja near Lagos was built during World War II. West African Airways Corporation was formed in 1947 and had its main base at Ikeja. De Havilland Doves were initially operated on WAACs Nigerian internal routes and then West African services. (Sykes, 1973) Larger Douglas Dakotas were added to the Ikeja-based fleet from 1957. (Gradidge, 2006)

Originally known as Lagos International Airport, it was renamed in the mid-1970s, during construction of the new international terminal, after a former Nigerian military head of state Murtala Muhammed. The international terminal was modelled after Amsterdam Airport Schiphol. The new terminal opened officially on 15 March 1979. It is the main base for Nigeria's largest airline, Arik Air.

Murtala Muhammed International Airport consists of an international and a domestic terminal, located about one kilometre from each other. Both terminals share the same runways. This domestic terminal used to be the old Ikeja Airport. International operations moved to the new international airport when it was ready while domestic operations moved to the Ikeja Airport, which became the domestic airport. The domestic operations were relocated to the old Lagos domestic terminal in 2000 after a fire. A new domestic privately funded terminal known as MMA2 has been constructed and was commissioned on 7 April 2007.

Figure 14: Murtala Muhammed international airport

Source: gettyimages.com

During the late 1980s and 1990s, the international terminal had a reputation of being a dangerous airport. From 1992 through 2000, the US Federal Aviation Administration posted warning signs in all US international airports advising travelers that security conditions at Lagos Airport did not meet ICAO minimum standards. In 1993, the FAAN suspended air service between Lagos and the United States. During this period, security at LOS continued to be a serious problem. (FAAN, 2015) Travelers arriving in Lagos were harassed both inside and outside of the airport terminal by criminals. Airport staff contributed to its reputation. Immigration officers required bribes before stamping passports, while customs agents demanded payment for nonexistent fees. In addition, several jet airplanes were attacked by criminals who stopped planes taxiing to and from the terminal and robbed their cargo holds.

Following Olusegun Obasanjo's democratic election in 1999, the security situation at Lagos began to improve. Airport police instituted a "shoot on sight" policy for anyone found in the secure areas around runways and taxiways, stopping further airplane robberies. Police secured the inside of the terminal and the arrival areas outside. The FAA ended its suspension of direct flights to Nigeria in 2001 in recognition of these security improvements. By 2010, the FAA had granted the airport its highest safety rating. (FAAN, 2015).

Recent years have seen substantial improvements at Murtala Muhammed International Airport. Malfunctioning and non-operational infrastructure such as air conditioning and luggage belts have been repaired. The entire airport has been cleaned, and many new restaurants and duty-free stores have opened. Bilateral Air Services Agreements signed between Nigeria and other countries are being revived and new ones signed. These agreements have seen the likes of Emirates, Ocean Air, Delta and China Southern Airlines express interest and receive landing rights to Nigeria's largest international airport.

3.1.4. Passenger Airlines and destinations

Table 10: Passenger Airlines and destinations of Murtala Muhammed International Airport

Airlines	Destinations	Terminal
Aero Contractors	Accra	INTL
Aero Contractors	Abuja, Asaba, Benin City, Calabar, Enugu, Kano, Owerri, Port Harcourt, Uyo	MMA2
Africa World Airlines	Accra	INTL

Air France	Paris-Charles de Gaulle	INTL
Air Peace	Abuja, Akure, Asaba, Benin City, Calabar, Enugu, Ibadan, Ibom, Kebbi, Owerri, Port Harcourt–NAF, Port Harcourt–Omagwa,	MMA2
Air Peace	Accra, Banjul, Dakar–Diass, Freetown, Monrovia, Sharjah	INTL
Arik Air	Abidjan, Accra, Banjul, Cotonou, Dakar, Douala, Freetown, Libreville, Luanda, Monrovia	INTL
Arik Air	Abuja, Asaba, Benin City, Calabar, Enugu, Jos, Kaduna, Kano, Owerri, Port Harcourt, Uyo, Warri	MMA1

ASKY Airlines	Douala, Libreville, Lomé	INTL
Azman Air	Abuja, Kano	MMA2
British Airways	London-Heathrow	INTL
Dana Air	Abuja, Port Harcourt, Uyo	MMA2
Dana Air	Accra	INTL
Delta Air Lines	Atlanta	MMA2
Discovery Air Nigeria	Abuja	MMA2
EgyptAir	Cairo	INTL
Emirates	Dubai-International	INTL
Ethiopian Airlines	Addis Ababa	INTL
Etihad Airways	Abu Dhabi	INTL
First Nation Airways	Abuja, Port Harcourt	MMA2
Kenya Airways	Nairobi-Jomo Kenyatta	INTL
KLM	Amsterdam	INTL
Lufthansa	Frankfurt	INTL
Med-View Airline	Accra, London-Gatwick, Jeddah	INTL
Med-View Airline	Abuja, Enugu, Port Harcourt, Yola, Kano	MMA2
Meridiana	Milan-Malpensa	INTL
Middle East Airlines	Milan-Malpensa	INTL
Overland Airways	Asaba, Ibadan, Ilorin	MMA1

Royal Air Maroc	Casablanca	INTL
Rwandair	Kigali	INTL
South African Airways	Johannesburg-O.R. Tambo	INTL
Turkish Airlines	Istanbul–Atatürk	INTL
Virgin Atlantic	London-Heathrow	INTL

Source: FAAN, 2015

3.1.5. Cargo Airlines and Destinations

Table 11: Cargo airlines and destination of Murtala Muhammed International Airport

Airlines	Destinations
Air France Cargo	N'djamena, Paris–Charles de Gaulle
Allied Air	Ostend/Bruges
Cargolux	Luxembourg
DHL Aviation operated by ABX Air	Accra, Bamako, Brussels
Emirates SkyCargo	Dubai–Al Maktoum
Ethiopian Airlines Cargo	Accra, Addis Ababa, Kigali, Liège, London–

	Heathrow
Etihad Cargo	Abu Dhabi, Nairobi–Jomo Kenyatta
Lufthansa Cargo	Frankfurt, Johannesburg–O.R. Tambo
Qatar Airways Cargo	Accra, Doha
Saudia Cargo	Dubai–Al Maktoum, Jeddah, Nairobi–Jomo Kenyatta, Riyadh, Sharjah
Turkish Airlines Cargo	Dubai–Al Maktoum, Istanbul–Atatürk

Source: FAAN (2015)

3.1.6. Other facilities

The airport includes the headquarters of the Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria. (FAA, 2010) It also houses the head office of the Accident Investigation Bureau. The Lagos office of the Nigerian Civil Aviation Authority is located in Aviation House on the grounds of the airport. (NAAN, 2010)

Arik Air's head office is in the Arik Air Aviation Center on the grounds of the airport. (Arik Air, 2007) Aero Contractors has its head office in the Private Terminal of the Domestic Wing at Murtala Muhammed International Airport. At one time Nigeria Airways had its head office in Airways House on the airport property. Prior to its disestablishment Afrijet Airlines had its head office in the NAHCO Building on the grounds of the airport.

Figure 15: Art Works at Murtala Muhammed international airport

Source: www.mma2.com

3.1.7. Statistics

These data show number of passengers movements into the airport, according to the Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria's Aviation Sector Summary Reports.

Table 12: Aviation Sector Reports (2010–2013, 2014, Q3-Q4 of 2015, and Q1-Q2 of 2016,)

Year	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Passengers	3,817,338	3,848,757	4,162,424	5,136,920	5,644,572	6,273,545	6,746,290	6,879,286	7,261,178	7,374,507	7,164,169
Growth (%)	▲ 6.74%	▲ 0.82%	▲ 8.15%	▲ 23.41%	▲ 9.88%	▲ 11.74%	▲ 7.54%	▲ 1.97%	▲ 5.55%	▲ 1.56%	▼ 2.8%

Source: Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria (FAAN).

3.1.8. Design Approach

Even though the Murtala Muhammed International Airport (MMIA) wasn't planned through the aerotropolis concept, it has the potentials of becoming one of the leading aerotropolis in Africa.

The Airport consists of a large enough terminal that accommodates all required activities.

The terminal has separate floors for arriving and departing passengers, overcrowding is therefore not an issue. The only obvious fault with the facility is its questionable appearance.

Figure 16: Murtala Muhammed international airport Site Layout

Source: google.com

Figure 17: Murtala Muhammed international airport Check-in Concourse

Source: www.mma2.com

Figure 18: Murtala Muhammed international airport Airlines offices floor plan

Source: www.mma2.com

Figure 19: Murtala Muhammed international airport Departure Concourse

Source: www.mma2.com

3.2. CASE STUDY 2

3.2.1. Introduction NNAMDI AZIKIWE INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT, ABUJA

Figure 20: Nnamdi Azikiwe international airport, Abuja

Source: www.google.com

3.2.2. General Information

Airport type

Public

Owner/Operator

Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria (FAAN)

Location

Abuja, in the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria

Hub for

- Arik Air
- Air Peace
- Overland Airways
- Ibom Air

Elevation AMSL

1,123 ft / 342 m

Coordinates

9°00′24″N 7°15′47″E

Runways

Direction Length Surface	Length	Surface
04R/22L	3,610m	Asphalt

Statistics (2015)

Passengers 3,462,830

Passenger change 16–17 Decrease 18.14%

(Sources: Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria, 2016)

Figure 21: Nnamdi Azikiwe international airport, Abuja

Source: google.com

3.2.3. Introduction

The airport site location is at airport road, at the outskirts of Abuja town, far from human habitation and activity environment. The Nnamdi Azikiwe International Airport, Abuja was designed and constructed with facilities to meet the required international standards for an international airport.

The terminal building was designed to accommodate 22,000 passengers daily. The airport has only 1 hangar that can accommodate the aircraft sizes not larger than the Boeing 737 aircraft (wing span- 28.35 meters, length- 30.48 meters) and the BE35 aircraft respectively.

3.2.4. DESCRIPTION OF THE AIRPORT

A toll gate is located at the entrance of the airport site for persons driving into the airport premises. At the toll gate, the drivers are required to pay a fixed amount depending on the type of vehicle they enter the premise with and another gate for persons driving out of the airport premises. This is used to control the movement of cars in and out of the airport premises as well as to generate revenue for the airport.

Within the Nnamdi Azikiwe International Airport, Abuja, the international airport terminal building exists separately from the domestic airport terminal building and is therefore not located at comfortable walking distances between each other. There are no existing circulation space links between the domestic and international wings of the airport and there are also no circulation space links between the terminal building, the cargo handling buildings or the technical offices such as the Aeronautical Information Service, the air force command and the Communication offices. The parking lot is located close to the terminal building and quite a distance away from the entrance gate. The parking lot location close to the terminal building allows for easy and convenient movement from the parking lot to the terminal building without much obstruction or delay. The international terminal building is surrounded by the control tower, fire service station, the runways, the cargo- handling building, the technical building and the parking lot, etc. The airport runway has a dimension of (3600 ×60) meters.

The international terminal is a centralized linear terminal building which is located not far from the open- to air parking lot. The terminal building consists of the following:

- An entrance porch into the terminal building.
- A general waiting hall for visitors as well as arrival passengers who are leaving the terminal building and departure passengers who are yet to checked- in to proceed with their trip.

- This waiting area also comprises within its space, an information point, shops, conveniences and airline ticket purchase stalls. The entire space on the 1st, 2nd and 3rd floors, right above the waiting area, is void.
- There is a spiral stair case as well as 2 elevators just behind the information/ inquiry point which leads to the 1st, 2nd and 3rd floors respectively.
- The spiral stair/ elevators lead to the 1st floor which is the cafeteria/ bar section. There is also a small gift shop and photocopying service right at lobby opposite the elevator doors.
- The spiral stair/ elevators also lead to the 2nd floor which lands at the passenger concourse area. This floor also consists of the arrival and departure lounges, the executive lounge, the first class airline lounges, shops, control points (security, customs), airline ticketing area, conveniences and the arrival and departure gates.
- The spiral stair/ elevators also lead to the 3rd floor which consists of airport management offices, and restaurants (both public and passengers).
- Just behind the general waiting area at the ground floor, are activities which have been divided into arrival and departure systems.
- The departure area behind the general waiting area at the ground floor, consists of aviation security offices, first aid office, control points (security, customs, immigration), check-in facilities and stairs leading passengers to the departure lounges at the 2nd floor from which the passengers board their flight.
- The arrival area behind the general waiting area at the ground floor consists of aviation security offices, first aid office, control points (security, customs), baggage claim area and stairs from which the passengers that deplaned the aircraft come down through to the arrival area just explained above.

- The cargo building is situated far away from the international airport building terminal and has no form of link between them.
- There is a power house which houses generators to provide power supply when required and this building also has a workshop for the proper maintenance of the generator equipments.
- A fire and rescue building which contains washing and locker facilities, a cafeteria and kitchen, offices, a control room, and a lecture room.

3.2.5. Passenger Airlines and destinations

Table 13: Passenger airlines and destination of Nnamdi Azikiwe International Airport

Airlines	Destinations
Aero Contractors	Lagos, Owerri, Port Harcourt-Omagwa, Sokoto, Uyo, Yola
Africa World Airlines	Accra
Air Côte d'Ivoire	Abidjan
Air France	Paris–Charles de Gaulle, Port Harcourt-Omagwa

Air Peace	Accra, Asaba, Calabar, Enugu, Kebbi, Lagos, Owerri, Port Harcourt-Omagwa, Yola
Air Senegal	Dakar–Diass, Niamey
Arik Air	Asaba, Bauchi, Benin, Calabar, Enugu, Gombe, Ibadan, Ilorin, Kano, Lagos, Maiduguri, Owerri, Port Harcourt-Omagwa, Sokoto, Uyo, Warri, Yola
ASKY Airlines	Lomé, N'Djamena, Yaoundé
Azman Air	Kano, Lagos, Yola
British Airways	London–Heathrow
Dana Air	Lagos, Port Harcourt-Omagwa, Uyo
Discovery Air Nigeria	Lagos
EgyptAir	Cairo
Emirates	Dubai–International

Ethiopian Airlines	Addis Ababa
Ibom Air	Uyo, Lagos
Lufthansa	Frankfurt
Med-View Airline	Jeddah, Lagos, Yola
Overland Airways	Akure, Asaba, Bauchi, Calabar, Dutse, Ibadan, Ilorin, Jalingo, Jos, Kano, Katsina, Lagos, Minna
RwandAir	Accra, Kigali
Turkish Airlines	Istanbul

Source: FAAN, 2015

Statistics

These data show number of passengers movements into the airport, according to the Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria's Aviation Sector Summary Reports.

Table 14: Aviation Sector Reports (2010–2016,)

Year	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Passengers	2,126,645	2,011,320	2,190,398	2,651,282	3,196,438	3,922,547	4,216,147	3,679,224	3,945,897	4,169,676	4,341,637
Growth (%)	▼ 3.09%	▼ 5.42%	▲ 8.90%	▲ 21.04%	▲ 20.56%	▲ 22.72%	▲ 7.48%	▼ 12.73%	▲ 7.25%	▲ 5.67%	▲ 4.12%

Source: Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria (FAAN).

3.3.6. MATERIALS OF CONSTRUCTION

The basic materials used for the construction of the units are reinforced concrete roof decks, glass, concrete wall partitions.

Figure 22: Nnamdi Azikiwe international airport Level 0 floor layout

Source: Author

Figure 23: Nnamdi Azikiwe international airport Level 1 floor layout

Source: Author

Figure 24: Nnamdi Azikiwe international airport Level 2 floor layout

Source: Author

Figure 25: Nnamdi Azikiwe international airport Level 3 floor layout

Source: Author

3.3. CASE STUDY 3

3.3.1 Seymour Galapagos Airport.

Figure 26: Seymour Galapagos Airport.

Source: google.com

3.3.2. General Information

Airport type

Public/Military

Owner/Operator

ECOGAL

Location

Isla Baltra, Galápagos Archipelago, Ecuador

Hub for

- Avianca Ecuador
- LATAM Ecuador
- TAME

Elevation AMSL

207 ft / 53 m

Coordinates

00°27'14"S 90°15'57"W

Runways

Direction Length Surface	Length	Surface
14/32	2,401	Asphalt

Statistics (2015)**3.3.3. Introduction**

Seymour Airport, also known as Galapagos Ecological Airport, is the world's first green airport. It is located in Isla Baltra, one of the Galápagos Archipelago islands in Ecuador. It is also one of the main gateways for tourists travelling to the Galápagos Islands.

The new green airport was opened in December 2012. It is one of the only two airports serving the archipelago. It is operated by ECOGAL, a subsidiary of Corporación América, which operates 53 airports in Latin America and the Caribbean. Airlines including Avianca Ecuador, LAN Ecuador, TAME and Aerogal operate from the Seymour Airport. The airport handles approximately 300,000 passengers a year. The airport was awarded LEED Gold certification by the USGBC in July 2015.

3.3.4. Seymour Airport history

Figure 27: Seymour Galapagos Airport.

Source: google.com

The airport, earlier known as Seymour Island Airfield, was used by the United States Army Air Force (USAAF) to secure the South American coastline and the Panama Canal from Japanese submarines during World War II. First US troops arrived at the airport in April 1942.

Most of the troops were, however, withdrawn from the airport by September 1945. The military facility was deactivated in April 1946, and a communications unit was inactivated in February 1948. The base was handed over to the Ecuadorian government after the end of World War II in 1948. The base infrastructure that remained at the location was used for the commercial aviation activities that began in 1963.

3.3.5. Seymour Airport development

The Ecuadorian Government opened an international bidding for the construction, operation and management of the Seymour Airport in July 2008. Corporación América was preferred for the development of the \$35m airport project. ECOGAL was awarded a 15-year concession by the government of Ecuador in April 2011 to operate the airport.

The design and construction of the new airport considered the surroundings to create a minimal impact on the ecosystem, thus abiding by the regulations of the US Green Building Council (USGBC). The construction was divided into three phases. The first phase involved the construction of the new terminal structure, an air traffic control tower (ATCT) and a technical block. The demolition of the old terminal, expansion of the aircraft platform, renovation of the fire station block, and relocation of existing hangars and the cargo terminal were carried out during the second phase. The final phase involved runway reconstruction.

3.3.6. Terminal features of Galapagos Ecological Airport

The new terminal was built using the recycled steel tubes recovered from oil drilling activities in the Amazon region. The terminal, which covers an area of 6,000m², was completed at a cost of about \$24m.

The VIP lounges in the Galapagos Ecological Airport are operated by VIP Airport Club, which offers exclusive services to more than 50 airports across the world. The lounges offer a pleasant and sustainable environment, personalized assistance, and internet access, free and unlimited non-alcoholic beverages and snacks, as well as a wide range of cocktails, wines and speciality dishes.

3.3.7. First in Latin America and the Caribbean to be carbon neutral.

The Galapagos Ecological Airport became the FIRST in Latin America and the Caribbean to be Carbon Neutral and the second in the entire American continent.

This achievement is certified by the ACI, Airports Council International, through its Airport Carbon Accreditation program, the only institutionally endorsed system that allows the evaluation and recognition of the efforts of the participating airports to manage, reduce and offset their emissions of GHG, greenhouse gas.

The Level 4 “Neutrality” accreditation (Neutral Carbon) was received on December 18th, 2017, marking an important precedent in the region that allows us to determine the direction that all airports in the world should follow, confirming that it is possible to take care of the environment without abandoning the quality of the airport operation. The certification process began in 2014

and since then, it has been possible to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by operating the airport in a sustainable manner.

Also, it is the first in the world to operate 100% with renewable energy (solar and wind).

3.3.8. Sustainability of the terminal

The new terminal building uses green technologies such as solar and wind power, as well as seawater desalination to achieve energy savings. Approximately 75% of the materials from the old terminal were reused by the new building. The airport employs several measures to reduce energy consumption by approximately 40%.

Most of the rooms within the terminal building lack air conditioning; hence a bioclimatic design was integrated to maintain comfortable conditions throughout the year. The orientation of the new terminal, and the optimization of natural light and natural ventilation further minimize the energy requirements. Almost 100% of the energy required to operate the airport is produced through renewable sources.

3.3.9. RUNWAYS

The airport has a single runway, which is designated 14/32. The asphalt-surfaced runway is 2,401m long and 35m-wide and handles landings/take-offs only during the day.

3.3.10. GREEN DESIGN/ENERGY EFFICIENCY STRATEGIES

The Seymour Airport exposes the worldwide growing demand to incorporate sustainability criteria in new projects and assess specific aspects that reduce the environmental impact in the built habitat and protect the natural habitat, particularly in sensitive sites with high heritage value as is the case of the Galapagos Islands. It was conceived, designed, and built, in its entirety, as a green building, to become the World's First Ecological Airport.

STRUCTURE

- i. The terminal is 6,000 m². and has an umbrella-type roof that covers 10,000 m².
- ii. The modern structure is supported by twelve-inch steel pipes, recycled from the oil extraction fields in the Ecuadorian Amazon.
- iii. This building has light-coloured walls and an open covering that indirectly allows the entry of natural light.
- iv. The terminal is located at an angle of forty-five degrees at a safe distance from the runway, thus complying with international safety standards and ensuring that gas emissions from aircraft do not enter the building while reducing the noise levels indoors.

ILLUMINATION AND VENTILATION

- i. The airport works with 100% renewable energy by using photovoltaic panels and wind energy provides the Ecuadorian government Wind Farm.

- ii. The large windows are supported by two sets of skylights which are located into the checkroom and the centre of the building; they work as a light entry and air circulation.
- iii. The roof skylights have an inclination and a height that allows the renovation and extraction of air.
- iv. Each one of the mechanical louvres works automatically by sensors, according to the rise of air temperature. The new airport features a modern photovoltaic power system.
- v. The solar panels are located on the roof of walkaways and provide electrical energy to the terminal.

WATER USAGE

- i. This airport has its desalination plant. It captures seawater and once treated, it is taken to storage tanks located next to the main building.
- ii. The desalinated water enters the terminal and once it is used, it is collected, treated, and recycled, preventing the generation of wastewater and contributing to saving water.
- iii. The water in the toilets and sinks is recovered, treated, and reused. It is not suitable for human consumption, but appropriate for toilets.
- iv. Its colour (yellowish) responds to the treatment process in place and not to filth or damage.
- v. The urinals are dry to avoid water consumption and wastewater generation. They do not generate any pollution.

MATERIALS

- i. The materials used in the work were selected based on criteria of reducing the environmental impact. SEALS.
- ii. Materials from local sources such as local stone aggregates quarries were used in the concrete structure. CONCRETE ROADS.
- iii. The volcanic rock of the island was used as a coating for external walls of the terminal, suiting it with the environment and achieving lower impact.
- iv. Wood and metal structures have been reused and recycled from the old terminal.
- v. Several pieces of furniture from the airport have environmental certifications in wood and materials from responsible sources; as well as the process for their preparation are friendly to the environment. CHAIRS WITH SEAL
- vi. The floor used on walkways and driveways is concrete, not only for being a friendlier environment material, but its light grey colour absorbs less heat than asphalt or coating colour, avoiding the colour island effect.
- vii. The material used for airport signage is ecological stainless steel with printing on vinyl with eco-solvent inks.
- viii. The shop area has been built -fully- with materials recovered from the old terminal: wood and metal. These were made by local craftsmen in Santa Cruz.

Figure 28: Seymour airport Google Maps snapshot

Source: googlemaps

3.4. CASE STUDY 4

3.4.1. Boston Logan International Airport

Figure 29: Boston Logan International Airport

Source: google.com

3.4.2. General Information

Airport type

Public

Owner/Operator

Massachusetts Port Authority (Massport)

Location

East Boston and Winthrop, Massachusetts, U.S.

Hub for

- Cape Air
- Delta Air Lines

Elevation AMSL

20 ft / 6 m

Coordinates

42°21'47"N 071°00'23"W

Runways

Direction Length Surface	Length	Surface
4L/22R	2396	Asphalt
4R/22L	3050	Asphalt
9/27	2,134	Asphalt
14/32	1,524	Asphalt
15L/33R	779	Asphalt
15R/33L	3,073	Asphalt

Statistics (2018)

Aircraft operations 424,024

Passengers 40,941,925

Source: FAA, Massport.

3.4.3. Introduction

Boston Logan International Airport in East Boston is the focal point of what connects Boston to the rest of the world. The airport is situated in East Boston - 3 miles' drive from Downtown Boston. Hundreds of international and American flights depart from Logan every day almost everywhere in the world because it has many destinations such as Europe, Asia, the Middle East, Latin and North America. Its name is abbreviated as BOS Airport. It covers 2,384 acres of land; it has six runways and four passenger terminals, and also it has almost 16,000 employees.

It is considered to be the largest airport in the New England region, and also in 2015, it was named as 17th-busiest airport in the USA with 25.5 million total passengers. The Massport stated an 8.5% increase in passenger traffic in 2016 comparing to 2015, having a total of around 27.7 million passengers. But in 2017, the passengers' amount increased and become 38,412,419 million, and it gave the BOS Airport the rank of 16th-busiest airport title in the United States. BOS Airport operates as a hub for Azores Airlines, Delta Air Lines, as well as Cape Air. It is considered to be a focus city for JetBlue. Also, American Airlines operates from BOS Airport. The airport manages domestic and international flights, and its' busiest routes considered to be Chicago, San Francisco, Atlanta, LA, New York, Washington, Baltimore, Orlando, Philadelphia, and Newark.

The airports' carriers are served by a total of 56 airlines, including 12 foreign flag carriers, 21 U.S. certified air carriers, 12 commuter airlines and 11 cargo carriers. The top of the carriers is considered to be Delta, American Airlines etc. All major US air carriers offer flights from Boston to all or most of their primary and secondary nodes. The airport is managed by the Massachusetts Port Authority (Massport). It is governed by a board with seven members, they are appointed by the Governor of the Commonwealth for each of them to seven-year terms.

3.4.4. Facilities

Logan International Airport has four-lettered passenger terminals, A, B, C, and E, and 102 gate positions total. Except for of flights from destinations with U.S. Customs and Border Protection preclearance, inbound international flights arrive at Terminal E for customs screening since the other terminals do not have customs screening facilities. All terminals are connected by pre-security shuttle buses and by the SL1 branch of the MBTA Silver Line BRT, as well as between Terminals A, B, and E via pre-security moving walkways. Moving walkways also connect the terminals to a central parking garage designed for consolidated service between all four terminals and the garage itself.

Terminal A

Terminal A, which replaced a 1970s-era building once occupied by the now-defunct Eastern Air Lines (and later by its successor Continental Airlines until closed for demolition in 2002), opened to passengers on March 16, 2005. The terminal is primarily used by Delta for its hub operations and is divided into a main terminal and a satellite terminal, which are connected

via an underground pedestrian tunnel under the ramp. The new redesigned Terminal A was developed under a special facility lease between Massachusetts Port Authority and Delta. On September 14, 2005, six months after opening, Delta filed for bankruptcy and consequently had to reduce the number of gates it leased. Terminal A features two Delta Sky Clubs. One is located on the third floor of the satellite building, and a newer one opened at the site of the former Continental Presidents Club in the main terminal building.

The building is the first airport terminal in the United States to be LEED certified for environmentally friendly design by the U.S. Green Building Council. Among the building's features are heat-reflecting roof and windows, low-flow faucets and waterless urinals, self-dimming lights and stormwater filtration.

In December 2018, Delta announced an expansion of routes to take effect in 2019, which resulted in Southwest moving to Terminal B, and Delta regaining all of Terminal A (other than one gate subleased to WestJet, itself a codeshare airline with Delta). As a result, Delta has declared Logan to be one of their hubs as of June 2019.

Terminal B

Terminal B, designed by John Carl Warnecke & Associates and Desmond & Lord, Inc., opened in 1974. Pier B was completed for US Airways in 1974 and Pier A for American in 1975. The terminal remained largely unchanged until US Airways expanded its operations at Logan in 1979 and improvements designed by HNTB were constructed in 1980. From 1980 until 2000, numerous small projects including passenger seating area improvements, concessions expansions and passenger lounges were completed at both piers. American's facilities were renovated in 1995

and redesigned by Gresham, Smith & Partners, and US Airways' facilities were renovated in 1998 and 2000 and redesigned by URS Corporation with Turner Construction serving as the construction manager.

Figure 30: Terminal B of Boston Logan Airport

Source: Wikipedidia.com

Until 2014, Terminal B was split into north and south buildings, with a parking garage between the two buildings. The gates of the south building are divided into three groups. The gates of the north building are divided into two groups. Air Canada, American, Southwest, Spirit and United operate out of Terminal B. United and American both operate lounges in the terminal for their customers.

Between 2012 and 2014, Terminal B underwent a \$160 million renovation, which was completed in April 2014. It created a post-security walkway that connects Terminal B North to Terminal B South. The renovation also included 24 new ticket counter spots, eight new departure

lounges, new concession space, and a new baggage carousel.[50] United, formerly located in Terminals A and C, began operating all flights out of Terminal B effective April 2014.

Terminal C

Terminal C opened in 1967 and was designed by Perry, Shaw, Hepburn and Dean. It underwent renovations in 1987, 2002 and 2005. Continuing the renovations of Terminal C, a post-security connection between Terminal C and Terminal E opened in Summer 2016, allowing for seamless connections between the two terminals, part of Massport's plan to ultimately connect all terminals post-security. The terminal serves Aer Lingus, Alaska Airlines, Cape Air, JetBlue, and Sun Country, with TAP Air Portugal only having departures take place out of the terminal.

The former Terminal D gates (the three gates at the north end of Terminal C) were renumbered and labelled as part of Terminal E in February 2006. These three gates were used, as part of Terminal E, by Southwest until their move to Terminal A. In 2016, following the construction of an airside connector between Terminals E and C, these three gates were renumbered again.

The airport's USO Lounge is located in the baggage claim area of Terminal C, lower level. It offers the most typical amenities as other markets as major as Greater Boston. Military ID is mandatory.

Terminal E

Terminal E serves as the international terminal for Logan and therefore houses the majority of its international arrivals (excluding flights from an origin that has U.S. border preclearance). Also, most non-U.S. carriers excluding Aer Lingus, Air Canada, TAP Air Portugal, and WestJet depart from Terminal E. The terminal was completed in 1974 and designed by Kubitz & Papi, Inc. and

Desmond & Lord, Inc. Massport completed the "Terminal E Modernization" project in August 1997 which improved the passenger facilities. The International Gateway Project, designed by Skidmore, Owings and Merrill and DMJM Aviation, added 410,000 square feet to the terminal in 2003 and the entire project was completed in 2008.

Terminal E has a total of 12 gates. All gates within the terminal are designated as common-use, meaning gates are assigned mostly based on an operational need and no specific airline claims ownership of any of those gates.

The third level of Terminal E is used for departures, the second for passport control via U.S. Customs and Border Protection, and the ground level for arrivals and customs, also via U.S. Customs and Border Protection. The Federal Inspection Station located in Terminal E is capable of processing over 2,000 passengers per hour. Terminal E underwent a \$100 million renovation which started in 2014 and includes a post-security connector between Terminals E and C (opened summer 2016), improved immigration and passport control kiosks, and gates capable of serving the Airbus A380. The Terminal E expansion was completed in late January 2017.

3.4.5. BOSTON LOGAN INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT FLIGHT PATTERNS

Table 15: Flight patterns of Boston logan airport (2018)

Wind from	Preferred Runways		Percentage of operations
	Departures	Arrivals	

NE	4L, 4R, 9	4L, 4R	18%
SW	22L, 22R	22L, 22R, 27	28%
NW	33L, 27	33L, 32, 27	37%
SE	15R, 14, 9	15R, 15L	17%

Source: wikipedia.com

GROUND TRANSPORTATION

Boston Logan International Airport has the accolade of "Easiest Airport to Get To" in a 2007 article on aviation.com because of the variety of options to/from the airport. These options include cars, taxis, the MBTA Blue and Silver lines, regional bus services, shared-ride vans, ferries, limousines and an in-house airport operator (Massport) intercity bus common carrier service offered by few U.S. airports, Logan Express, which is essentially Massport's equivalent to services such as Greyhound Lines, and can transport people from all four terminals at Logan to Back Bay, Braintree, Framingham, Peabody, or Woburn, or vice versa. Logan is 2.5 miles (4.0 km) northeast of Back Bay, a short distance compared with airports relative to their distance to an equivalent downtown in other major U.S. cities.

3.4.6. AIRLINES AND DESTINATIONS.

PASSENGERS

Table 16: Passenger destination from Boston Logan airport (2018)

Airlines	Destinations
Aer Lingus	Dublin, Shannon
Air Canada	Seasonal: Calgary (begins June 22, 2020), Toronto–Pearson, Vancouver
Air Canada Express	Halifax, Montréal–Trudeau, Ottawa, Toronto–Pearson
Air France	Paris–Charles de Gaulle
Alaska Airlines	Los Angeles, Portland (OR), San Diego, San Francisco, Seattle/Tacoma
Alitalia	Rome–Fiumicino
American Airlines	Austin (begins April 7, 2020), Charlotte, Chicago–O'Hare, Dallas/Fort Worth, London–Heathrow (resumes March 29, 2020), Los Angeles, Miami, New York–JFK, New York–LaGuardia, Philadelphia, Phoenix–Sky Harbor, Washington–National

American Eagle	Harrisburg, Rochester (NY), Syracuse
Azores Airlines	Ponta Delgada, Terceira
Boutique Air	Massena
British Airways	London–Heathrow
Cabo Verde Airlines	Praia, Sal
Cape Air	Augusta (ME), Bar Harbor, Hyannis, Lebanon, Martha's Vineyard, Nantucket, Portland (ME), Provincetown, Rockland, Rutland, Saranac Lake/Lake Placid
Cathay Pacific	Hong Kong
Copa Airlines	Panama City
Delta Air Lines	Amsterdam, Atlanta, Austin, Bermuda, Cincinnati, Detroit, Fort Lauderdale, Fort Myers, Las Vegas, London–Gatwick (begins May 21, 2020), London–Heathrow, Los Angeles, Miami, Minneapolis/St. Paul, New York–JFK, New York–LaGuardia, Orlando, Paris–Charles de

	Gaulle, Raleigh/Durham, Salt Lake City, San Francisco, Seattle/Tacoma, Tampa, West Palm Beach
Delta Connection	Buffalo, Charleston (SC), Chicago–O'Hare, Cincinnati, Cleveland–Hopkins, Columbus–Glenn, Indianapolis, Jacksonville (FL), Kansas City, Milwaukee, Nashville, Newark, New York–JFK, New York LaGuardia, Norfolk, Philadelphia, Pittsburgh, Raleigh/Durham, Richmond, Savannah, Washington–National
El Al	Tel Aviv
Emirates	Dubai–International
Frontier Airlines	Orlando, Raleigh/Durham, San Juan (begins April 23, 2020) Seasonal: Denver, Miami
Hainan Airlines	Beijing–Capital, Shanghai–Pudong
Hawaiian Airlines	Honolulu
Iberia	Madrid

Icelandair	Reykjavík–Keflavík
Japan Airlines	Tokyo–Narita
JetBlue	Aruba, Atlanta, Austin, Baltimore, Barbados, Bermuda, Buffalo, Burbank, Cancún, Charleston (SC), Charlotte, Chicago–O'Hare, Cleveland, Dallas/Fort Worth, Denver, Detroit, Fort Lauderdale, Fort Myers, Havana, Houston–Intercontinental, Jacksonville (FL), Las Vegas, Long Beach, Los Angeles, Mexico City (ends January 9, 2020), Minneapolis/St. Paul, Montego Bay, Nashville, Nassau, New Orleans, New York–JFK, New York–LaGuardia, Newark, Orlando, Philadelphia, Phoenix–Sky Harbor, Pittsburgh, Punta Cana, Raleigh/Durham, Richmond, Rochester (NY), Salt Lake City, San Diego, San Francisco, San Jose (CA), San Juan, Santiago de los Caballeros, Santo Domingo–Las Américas, Savannah, Seattle/Tacoma, Syracuse, Tampa, Washington–National, West Palm Beach
KLM	Amsterdam
Korean Air	Seoul–Incheon
LATAM Brasil	São Paulo–Guarulhos

Level	Barcelona
Lufthansa	Frankfurt, Munich
Norwegian Air Shuttle	London–Gatwick
Porter Airlines	Toronto–Billy Bishop
Qatar Airways	Doha
Royal Air Maroc	Casablanca
Scandinavian Airlines	Copenhagen
Southwest Airlines	Baltimore, Chicago–Midway, Columbus–Glenn, Denver, Fort Lauderdale, Houston–Hobby, Nashville, St. Louis
Spirit Airlines	Atlanta, Fort Lauderdale, Las Vegas, Myrtle Beach, New Orleans, Orlando, Raleigh/Durham, San Juan

Swiss International Air Lines	Zurich
TAP Air Portugal	Lisbon, Ponta Delgada (resumes June 4, 2020)
Tradewind Aviation	White Plains
Turkish Airlines	Istanbul
United Airlines	Chicago–O'Hare, Denver, Houston–Intercontinental, Los Angeles, Newark, San Francisco, Washington–Dulles
United Express	Chicago–O'Hare, Newark, Washington–Dulles
Virgin Atlantic	London–Heathrow
WestJet Encore	Toronto–Pearson

Source: wikipedia.com

Cargo

Logan Airport is a medium-sized airport in terms of cargo, handling 684,875 tons of freight in 2012, making it the 10th busiest airport in the U.S. in terms of cargo. It handles many U.S.-based cargo airlines, including DHL Aviation, FedEx Express and UPS Airlines. It also has cargo offices for many international cargo carriers, including British Airways World Cargo, Cathay Pacific Cargo, China Airlines Cargo, EVA Air Cargo, LATAM Cargo Chile and Saudia Cargo. It has two cargo complexes: The North Cargo Terminal, located near Terminal E, and South Cargo, located near Terminal A. Given the airport is the 10th busiest cargo facility in the country, with many companies operating at the airport, it has been recognized that future expansion of cargo from Logan is limited due to constrained physical space for expansion.

TOP DESTINATIONS

Busiest domestic routes from BOS

(October 2018 – September 2019)

Table 17: Busiest domestic routes to and from BOS (2018)

Rank	Airport	Passengers	Airlines Served
1	Atlanta, Georgia	971,190	Delta, JetBlue, Southwest, Spirit

2	Chicago–O'Hare, Illinois	928,030	American, JetBlue, Spirit, United
3	Los Angeles, California	755,000	Alaska, American, Delta, JetBlue, United
4	Washington–National, D.C.	734,210	American, Delta, JetBlue
5	San Francisco, California	700,880	Alaska, Delta, JetBlue, United
6	Philadelphia, Pennsylvania	664,720	American, Delta, JetBlue
7	New York–LaGuardia, New York	656,250	American, Delta, JetBlue
8	Orlando, Florida	629,950	Delta, JetBlue, Southwest, Spirit
9	Baltimore, Maryland	572,370	JetBlue, Southwest, Spirit
10	Charlotte, North Carolina	527,340	American, JetBlue

Source: wikipedia.com

Busiest international routes to and from BOS (2018)

Table 18: Busiest international routes to and from Boston Airport (2018)

Rank	City	Passengers	Carriers
1	London–Heathrow, United Kingdom	849,443	British Airways, Delta, Virgin Atlantic
2	Toronto–Pearson, Canada	467,692	Air Canada, WestJet
3	Paris–Charles de Gaulle, France	405,882	Air France, Delta, Norwegian Air Shuttle
4	Dublin, Ireland	402,523	Aer Lingus, Delta
5	Reykjavík–Keflavík, Iceland	326,767	Icelandair
6	Amsterdam, Netherlands	270,930	Delta, KLM
7	Frankfurt, Germany	266,470	Lufthansa
8	Dubai–International, United Arab Emirates	225,613	Emirates

9	Toronto–Billy Bishop, Canada	208,763	Porter Airlines
10	London-Gatwick, United Kingdom	208,156	Norwegian

Source: wikipedia.com

19115
AIRPORT DIAGRAM

GENERAL EDWARD LAWRENCE LOGAN INTL. (BOS)
AL-58 (FAA)
BOSTON, MASSACHUSETTS

19115
AIRPORT DIAGRAM

BOSTON, MASSACHUSETTS
GENERAL EDWARD LAWRENCE LOGAN INTL. (BOS)

Plate 3.1: Runway Map of Boston Logan Airport (2018)

Source: wikipedia.com

BOSTON LOGAN INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT (BOS)

- | | | |
|----------------------|--------------------|---------------|
| 1 Short-stay parking | 4 Disabled parking | 7 Bus station |
| 2 Long-stay parking | 5 Taxi rank | 8 Hotel |
| 3 Other parking | 6 Car hire | Drop-off area |

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Figure 31: Site Map of Boston Logan Airport

Source: massport.com

Map Legend

Restrooms	Baggage Claim	Automated External Defibrillator
Women's Restroom	Telephone	Parking Pay Station Pay at Parking Pay Station before returning to car.
Men's Restroom	Security Check	MBTA Ticket Machine
Assisted Care	Designated Smoking Area	Ticket Counter
Elevator	Petport	Post Security
Escalator	Mailboxes	Trauma Kit
Information	Open 24hrs	
	ATM/Cash Machine	

Ground Transportation

Rental Car Center Shuttle	Passenger Pick-up/Drop-off	Logan Express/Sheduled Bus
Airport Shuttle	Taxi	Shared Van/Courtesy Bus
Silver Line	Limos	Charter Bus
		App Ride/TNC

Massachusetts State Police
Troop F | 617-568-7300

Massport Fire Rescue/Medical Emergency
617-567-2820

Airport Services		Food		Shops	
Delta Baggage Claim Office	8	Auntie Anne's	33	Bead Factory	65
Car Rental Telephone	10	Cumtito	38	Be Relax	75
Classic Shoe Shine	2	Dunkin' Donuts	37	BookLink	63
Currency Exchange-Travellex	1	Dunkin' Donuts	22	Brookstone	70
Currency Exchange-Travellex	4	Dunkin' Donuts	28	International Shoppes	72
Delta Service Center	3	Friendly's	21	InMotion Entertainment	67
Delta Sky Club	6 11	Fresh City	26	Johnston & Murphy	73
Hotel Information	9	Game On! Sports Cafe	29	L'Occitane	68
Kidport	5	Harpoon Tap Room	32	Massachusetts State Lottery	74
Southwest Baggage Claim Office	12	La Baguette Marche Express	27	New England Collections	62
TSA PreCheck Center	7	La Baguette Marche	20	NewsLink	74
		Legal Test Kitchen	25	NewsLink	60 61 64
		Lucky's/Lucky's Express	24	NewsLink	66 69 71
		Market Kitchen	30		
		Sbarro	36		
		Starbucks	34		
		Wendy's	23		
		Vino Volo	31		

(Last Revised: 6/2018)

Figure 32: Arrival floor Map of Terminal A Boston Logan Airport

Source: massport.com

Level 2 (L2) Ticketing & Gates

Map Legend

Restrooms	Baggage Claim	Automated External Defibrillator
Women's Restroom	Telephone	Parking Pay Station Pay at Parking Pay Station before returning to car.
Men's Restroom	Security Check	MBTA Ticket Machine
Assisted Care	Designated Smoking Area	Ticket Counter
Elevator	Petport	Post Security
Escalator	Mailboxes	Trauma Kit
Information	Open 24 hrs	
	ATM/Cash Machine	

Ground Transportation

Rental Car Center Shuttle	Passenger Pick-up/Drop-off	Logan Express/Shared Bus
Airport Shuttle	Taxi	Charter Bus
Silver Line	Limos	App Ride/TNC

Massachusetts State Police
Troop F | 617-582-7300

Massport Fire Rescue/Medical Emergency
617-567-2020

Airport Services	
Delta Baggage Claim Office	8
Car Rental Telephone	10
Classic Shoe Shine	2
Currency Exchange-Travellex	1
Currency Exchange-Travellex	4
Delta Service Center	3
Delta Sky Club	6 11
Hotel Information	9
Kidport	5
Southwest Baggage Claim Office	12
TSA Pre-Check Center	7

Food	
Auntie Anne's	33
Currto	38
Dunkin' Donuts	37
Dunkin' Donuts	22
Dunkin' Donuts	28
Friendly's	21
Fresh City	26
Game On! Sports Cafe	29
Harpoon Tap Room	32
La Baguette Marche Express	27
La Baguette Marche	20
Legal Test Kitchen	25
Lucky's/Lucky's Express	24
Market Kitchen	30
Sbarro	36
Starbucks	34
Wendy's	23
Vino Volo	31

Shops	
Bead Factory	65
Be Relax	75
BookLink	63
Brookstone	70
International Shoppes	72
InMotion Entertainment	67
Johnston & Murphy	73
L'Occitane	68
Massachusetts State Lottery	74
New England Collections	62
NewsLink	74
NewsLink	60 61 64
NewsLink	66 69 71

Figure 33: Departure floor Map of Terminal A Boston Logan Airport

Source: massport.com

3.5. CASE STUDY 5

3.5.1. Singapore Changi Airport

Figure 34: Singapore Changi Airport

Source: safdiearchitects.com

3.5.2. General Information

Airport type

Public/Military

Owner/Operator

- Changi Airport Group (CAG)
- Civil Aviation Authority of Singapore (CAAS)
- Republic of Singapore Air Force (RSAF)

Location

Changi, East Region, Singapore

Hub for

- Jetstar Asia Airways
- Scoot
- SilkAir
- Singapore Airlines
- Singapore Airlines Cargo
- FedEx Express

Elevation AMSL

6.66 m / 22 ft

Coordinates

01°21'33"N 103°59'22"E

Runways

Direction Length Surface	Length	Surface
02L/20R	4,000	Asphalt

02C/20C	4,000	Asphalt
02R/20L	4,000	Asphalt

Statistics (2018)

Passenger movements Increase 65,600,000

Air freight movements (tons) Increase 2,150,000

Aircraft movements Increase 386,000

3.5.3. Introduction

Singapore Changi Airport, commonly known as Changi Airport, is a major civilian airport that serves Singapore and is one of the largest transportation hubs in Asia. It is currently rated the World's Best Airport by Skytrax for the seventh consecutive year since 2013. It is also the first Airport in the world to do so for seven consecutive years and is one of the world's busiest airports by international passenger and cargo traffic. The airport is located in Changi, at the eastern end of Singapore, approximately 20 km (12 mi) from Marina Bay (Singapore's Downtown Core), on a 13-square-kilometre (5.0 sq mi) site. The airport is operated by Changi Airport Group and it is the home base of Singapore Airlines, Singapore Airlines Cargo, SilkAir, Scoot, Jetstar Asia Airways and BOC Aviation.

Figure 35: Aerial view of Changi of Airport (2018)

Source: safdiearchitects.com

As of 1 March 2019, Changi Airport serves more than 100 airlines flying to 400 cities in around 100 countries and territories worldwide. Each week, about 7,400 flights land or depart from Changi, or, about once every 80 seconds.

For the 2018 full-year figures published by the airport, the airport handled 65,600,000 passengers (a 5.5% increase over the previous year), the most in its 37-year history. This made it the seventh busiest airport by international passenger traffic in the world and the third busiest in Asia. In December 2018, Changi Airport registered a total of 6.13 million passenger movements, the highest the airport has ever achieved in a month since it opened in 1981. Its daily traffic movement record was also broken on 21 December 2018, with 221,155 passengers passing through

during that day. In addition to being an important passenger hub, the airport is also one of the busiest cargo airports in the world, handling 2.150 million tonnes of cargo in 2018. The total number of commercial aircraft movements increased by 3.4% from the previous year to 386,000 in 2018.

Changi Airport has five main passenger terminals arranged in an elongated inverted 'U' shape with Jewel in the centre of the 'U' shape. Currently, the airport has a designed total annual handling capacity of 85 million passengers.

- Terminal 1, opened on 1 July 1981, is located at the northern end. This terminal was renovated in 2019.
- Terminal 2, opened on 22 November 1990, is located at the eastern end.
- Terminal 3, opened on 9 January 2008, is located at the western end.
- Terminal 4, opened on 31 October 2017, is located on the southern side, at the site of the former budget terminal.

There is also a privately run luxury terminal called the JetQuay CIP Terminal. It is similar to the Lufthansa First Class Terminal at Frankfurt Airport but is open to all passengers travelling in all classes on all airlines with an access fee.

3.5.4. AIRLINES AND DESTINATIONS

Passenger

Table 19: Passenger destination from Changi airport (2018)

Airlines	Destinations
Air China	Beijing–Capital, Chengdu, Yinchuan
Air France	Paris–Charles de Gaulle
Air India	Chennai, Delhi, Mumbai
Air India Express	Bengaluru, Chennai, Coimbatore, Kochi, Madurai, Tiruchirappalli
Air Mauritius	Kuala Lumpur–International, Mauritius
Air New Zealand	Auckland Seasonal: Christchurch
Air Niugini	Port Moresby

<p>Air Timor operated by Druk Air</p>	<p>Dili</p>
<p>AirAsia</p>	<p>Ipoh, Kota Kinabalu, Kuala Lumpur International, Kuching, Langkawi, Miri, Penang</p>
<p>AirAsia X</p>	<p>Kuala Lumpur–International</p>
<p>All Nippon Airways</p>	<p>Tokyo–Haneda, Tokyo–Narita</p>
<p>Asiana Airlines</p>	<p>Seoul–Incheon</p>
<p>Bangkok Airways</p>	<p>Bangkok–Suvarnabhumi, Koh Samui</p>
<p>Batik Air</p>	<p>Jakarta–Soekarno-Hatta</p>
<p>Biman Bangladesh Airlines</p>	<p>Dhaka</p>

British Airways	London–Heathrow, Sydney
Cathay Pacific	Bangkok–Suvarnabhumi, Hong Kong
Cebu Pacific	Cebu, Clark, Davao, Iloilo, Manila
China Airlines	Kaohsiung, Surabaya, Taipei–Taoyuan
China Eastern Airlines	Changchun, Changsha, Hangzhou, Kunming, Quanzhou, Shanghai–Pudong, Yantai
China Southern Airlines	Guangzhou
Chongqing Airlines	Chongqing
Druk Air	Bangkok–Suvarnabhumi, Guwahati, Paro
Emirates	Brisbane (ends 30 March 2020), Dubai–International, Melbourne
Ethiopian Airlines	Addis Ababa, Kuala Lumpur–International

Etihad Airways	Abu Dhabi
EVA Air	Taipei–Taoyuan
Fiji Airways	Nadi
Finnair	Helsinki
Garuda Indonesia	Denpasar/Bali, Jakarta–Soekarno-Hatta, Surabaya
GoAir	Bengaluru, Kolkata
GX Airlines	Nanning
Hainan Airlines	Haikou
IndiGo	Bengaluru, Chennai, Delhi, Kolkata, Mumbai, Tiruchirappalli
Indonesia AirAsia	Bandung, Denpasar/Bali, Jakarta–Soekarno-Hatta, Semarang, Yogyakarta– Adisucipto
Japan Airlines	Tokyo–Haneda, Tokyo–Narita

Jetstar Airways	Denpasar/Bali, Perth
Jetstar Asia Airways	Bangkok–Suvarnabhumi, Clark, Da Nang, Darwin, Denpasar/Bali, Haikou, Hefei, Ho Chi Minh City, Hong Kong, Jakarta–Soekarno-Hatta, Jieyang, Kuala Lumpur–International, Manila, Medan, Naha, Osaka–Kansai, Penang, Phnom Penh, Phuket, Sanya, Siem Reap, Surabaya, Taipei–Taoyuan, Xuzhou, Yangon
Jetstar Pacific Airlines	Ho Chi Minh City
Jeju Air	Busan
Juneyao Airlines	Shanghai–Pudong
KLM	Amsterdam, Denpasar/Bali
Korean Air	Seoul–Incheon
Lion Air	Jakarta–Soekarno-Hatta

LOT Polish Airlines	Warsaw–Chopin
Lufthansa	Frankfurt, Munich
Malaysia Airlines	Kuala Lumpur–International, Kuching
Malindo Air	Kuala Lumpur–International
Myanmar Airways International	Yangon
Myanmar National Airlines	Yangon
Philippine Airlines	Manila
Philippines AirAsia	Cebu

Qantas ^[58]	Brisbane, London–Heathrow, Melbourne, Perth, Sydney
Qatar Airways	Doha
Regent Airways	Dhaka
Royal Brunei Airlines	Bandar Seri Begawan
Saudia	Jeddah
Scoot	Amritsar, Athens, Balikpapan (begins 30 June 2020), Bangkok–Don Mueang, Bangkok–Suvarnabhumi, Berlin–Tegel, Cebu, Changsha, Chennai (ends 24 May 2020), Chiang Mai, Clark, Coimbatore, Denpasar/Bali, Fuzhou, Gold Coast, Guangzhou, Haikou, Hangzhou, Hanoi, Harbin, Hat Yai, Ho Chi Minh City, Hong Kong, Hyderabad, Ipoh, Jakarta–Soekarno–Hatta, Jeddah, Jinan, Kaohsiung, Kota Bharu, Kota Kinabalu, Krabi, Kuala Lumpur–International, Kuantan, Kuching, Kunming, Langkawi, Luang Prabang, Macau, Makassar (begins 16 June 2020), Manado (begins 5 May 2020), Manila, Mataram–Lombok (begins 14 July 2020), Melbourne, Nanchang, Nanjing, Nanning, Ningbo, Osaka–Kansai, Palembang, Pekanbaru, Penang, Perth, Phuket, Qingdao, Sapporo–

	Chitose, Semarang (begins 2 June 2020), Seoul–Incheon, Shenyang, Surabaya, Sydney, Taipei–Taoyuan, Thiruvananthapuram, Tianjin, Tiruchirappalli, Tokyo–Narita, Vientiane, ¹ Visakhapatnam, Wuhan, Wuxi, Xi'an, Yogyakarta–Adisucipto (begins 20 May 2020), Zhengzhou
Shandong Airlines	Jinan
Shenzhen Airlines	Nanchang, Shenzhen
Sichuan Airlines	Chengdu, Nanning
SilkAir	Balikpapan (ends 29 June 2020), Bandung, Bengaluru, Cairns, Cebu, Chengdu, Chennai, Chongqing, Colombo–Bandaranaïke, Da Nang, Darwin, Davao, Denpasar/Bali, Hanoi, Hiroshima, Hyderabad, Kathmandu, Kochi, Koh Samui, Kolkata, Kuala Lumpur–International, Makassar (ends 15 June 2020), Malé, Manado (ends 4 May 2020), Mataram–Lombok (ends 13 July 2020), Medan, Penang, Phnom Penh, Phuket, Semarang (ends 1 June 2020), Shenzhen, Siem Reap, Surabaya, Xiamen, Yangon, Yogyakarta–Adisucipto (ends 19 May

	2020) Seasonal: Mandalay
Singapore Airlines	Adelaide, Ahmedabad, Amsterdam, Auckland, Bandar Seri Begawan, Bengaluru, Bangkok–Suvarnabhumi, Barcelona, Beijing–Capital, Brisbane, Brussels (resumes 25 October 2020), Busan, Canberra, Cape Town, Chennai, Christchurch, Colombo–Bandaranaike, Copenhagen, Delhi, Denpasar/Bali, Dhaka, Dubai–International, Düsseldorf, Frankfurt, Fukuoka, Guangzhou, Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Hong Kong, Houston–Intercontinental, Istanbul, Jakarta–Soekarno-Hatta, Johannesburg–O.R. Tambo, Kolkata, Kuala Lumpur–International, London–Heathrow, Los Angeles, Malé, Manchester, Manila, Melbourne, Milan–Malpensa, Moscow–Domodedovo, Mumbai, Munich, Nagoya–Centrair, Newark, New York–JFK, Osaka–Kansai, Paris–Charles de Gaulle, Perth, Phuket, Rome–Fiumicino, San Francisco, Seattle/Tacoma, Seoul–Incheon, Shanghai–Pudong, Stockholm–Arlanda, Surabaya, Sydney, Taipei–Taoyuan, Tokyo–Haneda, Tokyo–Narita, Wellington, Yangon, Zürich Seasonal: Sapporo–Chitose
Spring Airlines	Shanghai–Pudong

SriLankan Airlines	Colombo–Bandaranaike
Swiss International Air Lines	Zürich
Thai AirAsia	Bangkok–Don Mueang, Krabi, Phuket
Thai Airways	Bangkok–Suvarnabhumi
Thai Lion Air	Bangkok–Don Mueang
Turkish Airlines	Istanbul
United Airlines	San Francisco
Urumqi Air	Urumqi, Wuhan
US-Bangla Airlines	Dhaka
VietJet Air	Da Nang, Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City

Vietnam Airlines	Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City
Vistara	Delhi, Mumbai
XiamenAir	Dalian, Fuzhou, Xiamen, Xi'an

Source: wikipedia.com

3.5.5. CHANGI JEWEL

Jewel represents an innovation in the world of lifestyle/retail design, with a one-of-a-kind relationship between garden and marketplace. Also, nowhere in the world has a building been constructed that integrates the public realm with an airport facility so closely. The building extends Changi Airport’s principal function as a transit hub, to a public gathering space for Singaporeans and international travellers, establishing a new model for airports as discrete destinations for shopping, entertainment, and social activity.

What exactly is the Jewel?

Containing over 280 retail and food/beverage outlets, Jewel Changi Airport could easily be written off as a beautiful shopping mall filled with dramatic green spaces that just happens to be connected to an airport. After all, it's not an airport terminal -- there are no boarding gates or arrival halls, and anyone can visit.

But the new Changi addition serves multiple purposes for travellers. In addition to linking Terminals 1, 2 and 3 (passengers heading to and from Terminal 4 need to take a shuttle bus), offerings include early check-in services and baggage storage facilities as well as a 130-cabin YOTELAIR Singapore Changi Airport hotel. There's also the Changi Lounge, designed to complement a new intermodal transfer service that improves air-sea connectivity for cruise passengers. Beyond expected amenities like free Wifi, Jewel offers a few little nice touches like power bank loans -- free for 12 hours.

There are plenty of diversions for travellers stuck in Changi on a long layover, too, including an 11-cinema IMAX theater. Jewel's Shiseido Forest Valley is a four-story garden filled with walking trails set amid more than 235,000 square feet of landscaping, all surrounding the Vortex waterfall. Rainwater is collected and it becomes a part of the Vortex as well.

A Skytrain, which connects Changi terminals 1, 2 and 3, cuts through the middle of the Jewel, passing by the Vortex and adding to the photogenic scene. On the top floor is the 14,000-square-meter Canopy Park, which has several restaurants and themed gardens.

Conceived to serve the people of Singapore and travellers equally, the building is directly connected to the Changi Bus Terminal and the airport's Terminal 1. It is also accessible from Terminals 2 and 3.

Figure 36: floor plan and section of Changi Jewel (2018)

Source: safdiearchitects.com

Figure 37: Site Map of Airport (2018)

Source: www.wikipedia.com

T3

PUBLIC AREAS

- Dining
- Shopping
- Car Park
- Skytrain
- Taxi Queue
- Train to City
- Automated Teller Machines (ATM)
- Baby Care Room
- Clinic
- GST Refund
- Immigration
- Information
- LFPs
- Money Changer
- Postal
- Public Phone
- Tickets
- Unaccompanied Baggage / Left Baggage

Figure 38: floor plans of Changi Airport, Terminal 3 (2018)

Source: google.com.com

3.6. CASE STUDY 6

3.6.1. Oslo International Airport

Figure 39: Oslo international Airport

Source: google.com

3.6.2. General Information

Airport type

Public

Owner/Operator

Avinor

Location

Gardermoen, Ullensaker, Akershus

Hub for

- Norwegian Air Shuttle
- Scandinavian Airlines
- Widerøe

Elevation AMSL

681 ft / 208 m

Coordinates

60°12'10"N 011°05'02"E

Runways

Direction Length Surface	Length	Surface
01L/19R	3,600m	Asphalt
01R/19L	2,950m	Asphalt

Statistics (2015)

Passengers 28,518,584

International 16,513,229

Domestic 12,005,355

Aircraft movements 259,697

Cargo (metric tonnes) 181,265

3.6.3. Introduction

Figure 40: Oslo international Airport airport

Source: google.com

Oslo Airport, alternatively spelt as Oslo Gardermoen Airport or simply Gardermoen Airport is the main international airport serving Oslo, Norway, the capital and most populous city in the country. A hub for Norwegian Air Shuttle, Scandinavian Airlines and Widerøe, it connects to 26 domestic and 152 international destinations. 28.5 million Passengers travelled through the

airport in 2018, making it the second-busiest commercial airport in the Nordic countries, and the nineteenth-busiest in Europe.

Terminal

The passenger terminal covers 265,000 square metres (2,850,000 sq ft). The airport has 72 gates, of which 44 are bridge-connected and 28 are remote stands. Domestic gates are located in the west and north pier (gates A, B, C), while gates for international flights are in the east and north pier (gates D, E), with gates for non-Schengen area flights at the end of the east pier (gates F). Four gates near the end of the east pier are flexigates where doors can be opened or closed to switch between Schengen and non-Schengen flights. EU controllers have been somewhat sceptical of the Schengen/non-Schengen flexigates, and there were a few incidents where the wrong doors were opened so that passengers who should have gone through the border control did not.

The terminal was recently expanded. Nordic Office of Architecture recently completed the world's greenest airport terminal with their new 115,000-square-meter extension that's doubled the size of Oslo Airport. As the world's first airport building to achieve the BREEAM Excellence sustainability rating, the renovated Oslo Airport boasts an array of energy-efficient strategies as well as on-site energy harvesting systems. The most notable energy-saving measure is the airport's collection and storage of snow for reuse as a coolant during the summer.

The recent expansion is a continuation of Nordic's work on the Oslo Airport, which the architecture firm designed in 1998. The Oslo-based design studio's 300-meter-long extension preserves the building's simple and iconic appearance while increasing airport capacity from 19 million to an anticipated future capacity of 30 million. New design elements also improve the

passenger experience, such as the reduction of walking distances to a maximum of 450 meters, and the overhaul of the existing train station at the heart of the airport. Artificial lighting is minimized in favour of natural lighting to improve passenger comfort and reduce energy demands.

In addition to the use of natural lighting and the reuse of snow as a summer coolant, the architects reduced the airport's carbon footprint by 35 percent with the use of environmentally friendly and recycled materials. The new pier is entirely clad in timber sourced from Scandinavian forests, while additional natural materials, green walls, and water features, can be found throughout the interior. Recycled steel and concrete mixed with volcanic ash were also used. Improved insulation has helped the building achieve Passive House-level performance standards and, coupled with on-site energy harvesting, slashed energy consumption by over 50 percent as compared to the existing terminal.

Art

The main art on the landside of the airport is Alexis, consisting of six steel sculptures in stainless steel created by Per Inge Bjørlo. On the airside, Carin Wessel used 30,000 metres (98,000 ft) of thread to make the impression of clouds and webs, named Ad Astra. Anna Karin Rynander and Per-Olof Sandberg cooperated in making two installations: The Marathon Dancers, located in the baggage claim area, is a set of two electronic boards that show a dancing person. Sound Refreshment Station, of which six are located in the departure areas, are sound "showers" that make refreshing sounds when a person is immediately under them. Sidsel Westbø etched the glass walls. In the check-in area, there are small boxes under the floor with glass ceilings that contain curiosities. As well as the custom-made art, several existing sculptures and paintings were bought.

Figure 41: Interior Art design at the Oslo international Airport airport

Source: google.com

At the National Road 35 and European Route E6 junction, Vebjørn Sand built a 14-metre (46 ft) statue named the Kepler Star. It consists of two internally illuminated Kepler–Poinsot polyhedrons, appearing like a giant star in the sky after dark.

Figure 42: Site Map of Oslo international Airport

Source: google.com

ANKOMST ARRIVALS

OSLO LUFTHAVN

Figure 43: Arrival floor plan of Oslo international Airport

Source: google.com

Figure 44: Departure floor plan of Oslo international Airport

Source: google.com

CHAPTER FOUR
ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

4.1. Study Area

4.1.1. Site Location

The proposed site for the International Airport project is located at Umuleri village, in Anambra East Local Government Area, Anambra-State, Nigeria.

SITE LOCATION MAP

<p>ABU I. MICHAEL AAI/SPS/FES/ARC/17/MSC/03390 ARC 799 MEMBER: ARC, M.E.O. OMATSONE</p>	<p style="color: blue; font-style: italic;">Proposed</p> <p style="font-size: 2em; font-weight: bold; letter-spacing: 0.5em;">INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT</p> <p style="font-size: 1.5em; font-style: italic; color: blue;">Umuleri, Anambra State</p>	
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Figure 45: Proposed Site Location

Source: Researcher's field work

4.1.2. Geographical location of Anambra state.

Anambra is a state in the south-eastern region of Nigeria. It is located between latitudes 6°N and between longitudes 6°E. It has a land area of 4,844km² is ranked 35th out of 36 in state land area within Nigeria. Its state theme is "home for all". Its boundaries are formed by Delta State to the west, Imo State to the south, Enugu State to the east and Kogi State to the north. Anambra state has a total estimated population of 2,980,800. The indigenous ethnic groups in Anambra state are the Igbo; 90% of the population.

Figure 46: Map of Anambra state.

Source: www.legit.ng

The main towns of Anambra state are: Awka, Agulu, Aguluezechukwu, Onitsha, Nnewi, Ogidi, Obosi, Ihiala, Amichi, Uga, Uli, Abagana, Alor, Anambra, Atani, Nkpor, Eziowelle, Oba, Omor, Ichi, Ojoto, Oraifite, Ozubulu, Umuawulu, Umuoji, Umunachi, Umudioka, Unubi, Umunya, Umuleri, Ogbunike, Aguleri, Ekwulobia, Igbo-ukwu, Ichida,,Ihembosi Akwaukwu, Uke, Ukpor, Okija, Oraukwu, Osumenyi, Otu-ocha, Nnobi, Ideani, Adazi-Nnukwu, Adazi-Enu, Umuanaga, Adazi Ani, Nanka, Nneni, Nnewi, Nmiata-Anam, Awkuzu, Ebenebe, Enugwu-Ukwu, Enugwu-Agidi, Umueze-anam, Nawfia, Amawbia, Nri, Nando, Amansea, Amanuke, Achalla, Mgbakwu, Ugbenu, Ugbenne,Umuchu,Umuomaku, Isuaniocha, Akwaeze,Omogho

There are 21 local government areas in the state and they are as follows:

- Aguata Local Government Area
- Awka North Local Government Area
- Awka South Local Government Area
- Anambra East Local Government Area
- Anambra West Local Government Area
- Anaocha Local Government Area
- Ayamelum Local Government Area
- Dunukofia Local Government Area
- Ekwusigo Local Government Area
- Idemili North Local Government Area

- Idemili South Local Government Area
- Ihiala Local Government Area
- Njikoka Local Government Area
- Nnewi North Local Government Area
- Nnewi South Local Government Area
- Ogbaru Local Government Area
- Onitsha North Local Government Area
- Onitsha South Local Government Area
- Orumba North Local Government Area
- Orumba South Local Government Area
- Oyi Local Government Area

4.1.3. History of Anambra State

The Old Anambra state was created in 1976 with its capital as Enugu. The reorganization of the country's states led to the division of the old Anambra state into two states- The New Anambra state and Enugu state. The new Anambra state was created on the 27th day of August 1991. The origin of the name Anambra was derived from the Omambala River - which is easily

called Anambra River. The river is on the northern part of Anambra state and stretches to the famous River Niger. During the state creation, Awka was made its capital. Awka, the capital of Anambra state is a centre of considerable antiquity. It has an oil-centre location in the state, lying quite close to the Middle Eastern border.

4.1.4. Anambra East

Anambra East is a Local Government Area in Anambra State in the south-eastern part of Nigeria. The towns that make up the local government are Umuleri, Igboariam, Nnando, Nsugbe, Aguleri, Otuocha, Ezi Aguluotu, Mkpunando, and Umuoba Anam. In Anambra East, Oil and Gas were found in large quantity on the bank of Omambala river and the first private housing estate is about to be sited in Umuleri by the Orient Petroleum Resources PLC.

4.1.5 Historical Background: Umuleri, Anambra East Local Government Area, Anambra-State, Nigeria.

Umueri, also known and pronounced as Umuleri, is an ancient town in the Anambra State of South-eastern Nigeria. The people of Umueri belong to the Igbo ethnic group, and the town has an estimated population of 342,000. It is located within the Anambra Valley, bordered by the Anambra River (Omabala River) and Anam communities in the north, Nteje to the south, Aguleri and Nando in the east and Nsugbe in the western flank. Umueri from antiquity has been noted as the centre of the civilisation of the peoples of the Omambala basin. The forebears are widely acknowledged as the first settlers to settle in Omambala valley.

4.1.5.1. History

The origin of Umueri is sourced from the natives of the town who believe in the oral tradition (as a customary mode of transmission of knowledge in antiquity) that their clan was founded by Children of a man named Eri. (The name Umueri means Children of Eri) This Oral tradition passed from generation to generation indicates that Umueri ancestors are a group of migrating clan from an unknown place, though of late research on their habitats, cultural practices and artifacts they left behind suggest a connection with the fleeing Israelites of post Exodus era. The Settlers that infiltrated into the land settled at a place called Eri-aka and founded a clan called “Umueri”. Though the exact date, that they settled on the land was not known, many scholars were of the view that it occurred around 940AD

4.1.5.2. Division and administration

Traditionally, Umueri is broadly divided into 3 clans: Ezi, Ikenga, Ivite. The clans are further divided into villages and sub-villages. But with the advent of colonialism and modernization, the town has consciously grown and governed just like other Igbo Communities. The three traditional clans of Umueri are written down below with their corresponding Villages:

- **Ezi:** Belongs to Nneyi Village which is also divided into further sub-villages
- **Ikenga:** Comprises Ugume, Umudiana, Umunchezi, etc.
- **Ivite:** Umuatuolu, Ogbu and Mgbede

The pre-colonial Umueri government was a republican but with influence of the Bini Kingdom in that part of Igboland, it changes to Monarchical in nature in which the Eze resided in Ivite. The Prime Minister (Onowu) & Ajie in Ikenga and Ezi respectively. Modern administration since

colonization relegated this system and enthroned the Igwe Dynasty which is prevalent Institution till date.

The Igwe dynasty has come to stay including but not limited to the performance of basic traditional rites. The Ofala festival is traditionally performed by one who holds the Title of Oke-ebo, the traditional ruler. The New Yam festival is performed by the Onowu, Ajie and ``Igwe Oke-ebo`. Below is the Structure of Present Umueri Administration:

1. Igwe in-Council - The Traditional Ruler and his Cabinet[Igwe Cabinet]
2. Council of Elders [Ndichie] - The Elders of the Community
3. Umuotu - An Elite Age Grade that helps in implementing laws in the Community
4. Town Union - Umueri General Assembly [UGA]
5. Policing Age Grade - An Age grade in charge of the enforcement of local laws made in the town
6. Sanitation Age Grade- An Age Group in charge of clearing and maintenance of the rural road, Village Square and of all Public Utilities

4.1.5.3. Religion

Before the coming of Europeans, Umueri people practiced traditional religion with the worship of various deities. However, they had since embraced Christianity about a century ago. Today, there are more than 85% of Christians in the town. The major Christian faiths are the Catholic and Anglican denominations.

Some other churches, especially of the Pentecostal faith, have emerged in Umueri in the past fifty years. The town is also referred to as a pinnacle of Anglican evangelism as it has one of

the oldest churches east of the Niger. Churches that are found in the town include and not limited to the following: St Immanuel Anglican Church (founded 1904), St Gabriel Anglican Church (1912), Our Lady of Victory Catholic Church (1975), St Marks Catholic Church Nneyi etc.

4.1.5.4. Infrastructure

Most of the public basic infrastructure in the town is built by the community. The community-built infrastructures are as follow:

- Umueri General Hospital
- Umueri Town Hall
- Recreation Club House
- Umueri Girls High School
- Ugume Umueri
- Umueri High School
- Obinetiti (formerly Umueri Technical College)
- Community Secondary School, Umuatuolu
- Umueri Development School, Nneyi
- Umueri Postal Agency
- Umueri Community Bank
- Afiamama Market
- Eke Market
- Nkwo Nneyi Market, etc.

The few infrastructures owned by the government include the following:

- Umueri Nomadi School at Umudiana
- Umueri, Local Government Secretariat
- Otuocha High Court
- Umueri Head Bridge
- Umueri Civic Center
- Umueri Library and Skill Acquisition Center
- Boreholes Projects sunk around the Villages

Proposed and ongoing projects include the;

- Orient Refinery,
- Anambra State Umueri International Airport
- Orient Low Staff Residential Quarters etc.

4.1.6. Geology, Topography and Hydrology of Study Area

Umuleri lies on land which is situated at an altitude of 75.86m above sea level. It falls into the vast low-lying land belt of Nigeria and specifically into the lowlands and scarp lands of eastern Nigeria. The lowlands lie west of the Ojieli River and extend as far as the river Niger. The region is composed of a relatively flat terrain.

4.1.6.1. Climatic Data

Umuleri falls into the tropical hinterland region of Nigeria. The region has up to four months of dry season and the total rainfall is between 100 and 150cm. Relative humidity in the region is over 80% in the mornings and falls to 50 and 70% in the afternoons.

Figure 47: Map of Nigeria Climatic Zones

Source: www.wikipedia.com

Below are characteristics of the region, as they specifically affect Umuleri in terms of the sunshine and temperature, humidity, pressure and winds, rainfall and seasons.

4.1.6.2. Temperature

The hottest months of the year are February, March and April. This is because these months coincide with the passage of the overhead sun, falling into the late dry season period when the harmattan haze is diminutive and the skies are clear enough to permit greater insulation with no rains to lower the temperature.

The coldest month is usually August, in the middle of the rainy season. The cold temperature is brought by the South-west monsoon winds and the heavy rains of the preceding months. The days are usually cloudy while the nights are clear.

Figure 48: Temperature Chart of Umuleri

Source: www.meteoblue.com

Air temperature is relatively influenced by an increase in distance from the coast but less cloud produces an increase in the effective out-going radiation and in consequence, a reduction of net radiation and temperature.

While in increased cloudiness, the mean daily temperature is higher. Air temperature affects building in the following ways;

- Conduction
- Radiation
- Convection
- Evaporation.

Solar energy may be transferred into the building through the radiation process. During this process, heat changes its mode of transfer. Thus energy will reach the wall in the form of radiation and will be absorbed in the external surface. It then flows across the wall internally by the material of construction.

If the material of construction is metal the flow is by conduction if the wall is having air space, the flow by convection and radiation process continues, if there is a water body, evaporation will occur as well.

Design Implication

The air temperature around the site is studied for building design considerations. The choice of building materials for construction are carefully specified and selected to afford comfortability to building occupants during all weather.

4.1.6.3. Pressure and Winds

Two important air masses move over Umuleri. These are the tropical maritime air mass which originates in the southern high-pressure belt, crosses the equator, picks up moisture from the Atlantic and enters Nigeria from the south. It is therefore cool and wet and has a south-western orientation.

The tropical continental air mass originates in the Eurasian-Arabian high-pressure belt. It picks up a little or no moisture en-route and is therefore dry. It arrives in the month of October and by January; its Influence is felt all over the country. It has a north-eastern orientation.

Figure 49: Umuleri Wind Speed Chart

Source: www.meteoblue.com

Design Implication

During the dry season, the northeast trade wind (harmattan) blows and exacts relatively high temperature during the day and cold at night. While the southwesterly accounts for ventilation and prevails at most of the seasons with different characteristics.

In conjunction with this, the design has been such that the occupancy ratio of each unit determines the placement or zoning on the site.

The buildings are oriented to ensure the comfortability of the occupants.

The runways are designed towards the prevailing wind.

According to the wind rose diagram figure the direction of prevailing wind is across South Southwest (SSW) direction. For the Orientation of a Runway, SSW direction is very suitable.

Figure 50: Umuleri Wind Rose

Source: www.meteoblue.com

4.1.6.4. Sunshine and Solar Effect

Throughout the world, life depends upon the radiation received from the sun, this is said to be so because nearly all physical and biological processes occurring near the surface or in the atmosphere involves some energy transformations.

Due to its latitude of 6°19, Umuleri receives constant and abundant sunshine. The angle of the sun's rays is almost vertical all through the year resulting in a high intensity of solar radiation. The hours of daylight are also long because of the long duration of solar radiation. As a result, the average monthly hours of daylight are almost constant. Thus, Umuleri has a mean annual temperature distribution of over 27°C.

Figure 51: Umuleri Cloudy, Sunny and Precipitation days chart.

Source: www.meteoblue.com

Design Implication

Solar radiation causes discomfort to building occupants by increasing thermal conduction of interior of the building. Thus provision is made for trees to be planted around the site to reduce the effect of solar radiation on the buildings or to serve as shading devices. The choice of roof types, wall finishes and floors are carefully determined and the buildings are being oriented such that sensitive indoor spaces do not receive direct sunlight

4.1.6.5. Humidity

Humidity is the term used to describe dampness of the atmosphere which is due to the presence of water vapour. The mean relative humidity in Umuleri ranges from 70-88% in January to 80-90% in July. Thus, it can be seen that the relative humidity is lower in the dry season than in the wet season, this is due to the effects of the two air masses, the tropical continental and tropical maritime air masses respectively.

4.1.6.6. Rainfall and Seasons

The mean annual rainfall in Umuleri is 175-200cm. The Rainfall here depends on the two major air masses. When the tropical maritime air mass is dominant, there is a long wet season from April to July, interrupted by a short dry season in august, then another wet season from September to October. The long dry season from November to March follows on when the tropical continental air mass is dominant.

In the wet season, rainfall ranges between 200cm and 300cm, while in the dry season it ranges from 25cm to 50cm. Rainfall comes in the form of intensive showers of short duration, especially at the beginning and the end of the rainy season.

Figure 52: Umuleri Precipitation amount chart.

Source: www.meteoblue.com

4.1.6.7. Vegetation

Umuleri lies in a narrow belt of fresh-water swamp. This type of vegetation is dominated by grasses. Freshwater is supplied by the heavy rainfall and the rivers. Evaporation is reduced to a minimum by the high relative humidity and drainage rendered almost impossible by the level topography. Freshwater plants such as raffia palm and a great range and density of plant species due to the vegetation belt are common in Umuleri. There is enough greenery In the Umuleri today, with very sparse settlement.

4.1.6.8. Geology and Soil

Soils in Umuleri are classified as lateritic soils. These soils are rich in free iron but have a low mineral reserve. These lateritic soils are derived from sandy deposits of various sandstone and shale. These soils are further classified under deep porous red soils and are often referred to as the red earth or acid sands. They are of low natural fertility but are easily workable and their lack of organic matter can be remedied artificially to ensure continuous cropping.

Soil formation depends on the nature of the parent rock, vegetation and the short but violent nature of the rainfall has ensured that Umuleri's soil falls into those categorized as being the worst hit by gully erosion. Topographically, because Umuleri lies at a moderate altitude (75.36m) above sea level, there is also an intermediate condition of sheet-wash erosion.

4.2. SITE SELECTION AND ANALYSIS

4.2.1. Criteria for Site Selection

Choosing the right site for the International Airport project is complicated and involves scientific, political, environmental, sociological, economical and technical uncertainties.

Before concluding on Umuleri village, Anambra East Local Government Area as the project site, several salient factors were critically examined. They are;

- **Regional plan**

The International Airport project should fit well into the regional plan which forms an integral part of the national network of airport

- **Use of airport**

Due to the large nature of an international airport, a very large expanse of land is required for its design and development. Several locations were considered within Anambra state, but the site at Umuleri in Anambra- East Local Government Area of the state was chosen.

In this case, the location of the site is being guided by the following:

- i. The airfield (airside) components such as the runways, apron, taxiways and approach aid.
- ii. The landside components such as the terminal building. Administration areas, terminal, cargo holds.
- iii. Ancillary facilities, hangers, maintenance areas and firefighting services.

- **Proximity to other airports**

The unavailability of any airport complex within Anambra state and the sufficient distance between Anambra state and the closest existing airport (Asaba Airport and Sam Mbakwe Airport, Enugu) was a motivating factor to the choice of the Umuleri airport site as it recommended that airports are not located close to another to avoid movement interference between aircraft as well as airside accidents which would frequently occur as a result of the siting of airports within close distances of one another.

- **Ground accessibility**

Umuleri town already have existing ground transportation system and this would, therefore, reduce the cost of the construction of access to the airport site but it would be best to provide access to the airport environment and site through a major highway as this would reduce the chances of traffic congestion in the town, encourage proper circulation of vehicular traffic as well as direct

and define access to the airport complex environment. This also will create restrictions within and around the airport premises as only a restricted group would use this road network or access.

- **Topography**

The airport site slopes gently from the South-East to the North-West part and is therefore relatively negligible. This will enhance the natural drainage of surface water away from the site.

- **Obstructions**

The choice of the Anambra State International Airport site at Umuleri was guided also by aviation laws which recommended that the location of the airport should be free of both visual and physical obstructions. This would be more economical and would also reduce possible accidents.

- **Visibility**

There are no structures (completed or uncompleted) existing around the airport site. This is a result of the fact that the land area of the site is massive and the possible avoidance of obstructions. It was sited away from the developed area to also reduce or eliminate the possibility of noise pollution and other adverse environmental effects or impact. This also would encourage the possible expansion of the airport complex in the future when needed.

- **Wind**

The local weather patterns were also taken into consideration while choosing the airport's site as prevailing winds, are a major factor in determining runway headings. Therefore, it essential that such airport sites are located and oriented to maximize effectively wind paths and its surrounding

environment devoid of trees to help increase the airflow within its environment and as a result encourage the successful take-off and landing of aircraft.

- **Availability of utilities**

The Umuleri town already has in use such basic utilities that would be required for the proper running of their community and such utilities can be extended to the airport site encouraging a reduced cost in their installation. These include utilities such as electricity, fueling stations (fuel, natural gas or oil), etc. Such utilities as water can be achieved through the construction and installation of borehole facilities. These are required as they would enhance efficiently the air operations.

- **Aircraft noise**

The effect of noise that would be generated within an airport site in the future was taken into consideration as it usually poses problems. With this in mind, an estimate of the magnitude and extent of noise from airport operations to its surrounding environment was determined and this resulted in the zoning of the land-use plan of the state and towns and subsequently to the location of the airport site to a suitable zone at Umuleri, far away from other activity zones.

- **Soil characteristics**

The soil of the airport site is found amongst the Eastern states of Nigeria. The soil is lateritic in nature. The ground on which the airport is being built must have a stable stratum of earth upon which building foundations can be anchored. The soil must be capable of supporting heavy loads without shifting or sinking. If the airport's runways are to be used by heavy aircraft, (airplanes

with a gross weight of 150 tones) the underlying soil and/or bedrock must be able to support the weight of the runway plus the aircraft's weight

- **Economy of construction**

The demolition and clearing of existing built-up areas, as well as the compensation of building/property owners for construction purposes, requires a lot more expenses than construction done on an unbuilt area as this would increase the project cost. The airport land at Umuleri was bought at a cheaper rate and this is as a result of the fact that it is located in a village and far away from the developed environment of the village, surrounding villages and towns.

- **Land use and its value**
- **Environmental factors**

4.3. Site Analysis

The proposed site for the International Airport project is on a very large expanse of land. The site is located within the Anambra Valley, bordered by the Anambra River (Omabala River) and Anam communities in the north, Nteje to the south, Aguleri and Nando in the east and Nsugbe in the western flank. The site can be accessed through two different ground access to transportation that is the highway. The site can be accessed through the Nkisi Expressway.

The prevailing winds are the North East (NE) and South West (SW) Trade wind. This is an integral analysis of runway orientation. The runway is to be designed towards the prevailing winds.

The site is for the most part untouched with the natural landscape.

Figure 53: Site Analysis Diagram

Source: Researcher's field work

4.3.1. Site Potential and Threat

The most important potential of this site is its expansive relatively land area. The earmarked land area shall satisfy the immediate need of the International Airport project namely, an airport terminal, transport hub.

Another advantage of the site is the almost state of its topography, biodiversity and landscape. This can be put to full advantage in the planning of the airport master plan with due

regards to the need for sustainability and minimal interference with nature. Another advantage is the proximity to Nkisi Expressway and railway transportation for easy access into the terminal.

4.3.2. Topography

The land area of the proposed project is not cultivated; most of the natural vegetation is still intact. The landscape is mostly covered with low-growing vegetative grassland interspersed with tropical trees.

The site would be cleared and topsoil removed before commencement of construction. The proposed site is relatively flat with an approximate elevation different from the road benchmark of between 0.5 to 3.35metres (Researcher's fieldwork)

4.3.3. Drainage

The area is covered with lateritic-sandy soil, for the most part, apart from the area still covered by forest, most of the clay-loamy soil of the interior has been seriously leached and presently look more like laterite soil and the soils are well-drained.

4.4. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT

4.4.1. A) Negative Impacts

The foreseeable threat and risk associated with locating this project in the chosen site is related to the following;

- i. The adjoining Nkisi Expressway and the railway are potential sources of noise nuisance to the site. The effect of this must be mitigated in the proposed design and site layout planning.
- ii. Also, the construction phase impacts on the environment can be reasonably predicted during the development of this project. These impacts include;

1. **Loss of Land Use Options:** The construction of the airport will involve the erection of permanent concrete structures on what is essentially a greenfield site. This will result in a loss of the options for alternative land use and thus represents an irreversible commitment of land resources. The loss of optional uses for the land in the future is considered to be a negative impact.
2. **Other construction phase impact include;** Loss of terrestrial habitat and biodiversity, modification to existing surface drainage, construction noise etc.

4.4.2. B). Positive Impacts

The proposal would not only benefit the immediate environment but Anambra-State and Nigeria in general because of its position as the first Passenger based international Airport to be established in Anambra state and South-Eastern Nigeria.

If properly implemented, the International Airport concept will ultimately lead to improved connectivity, job creation, urbanization and local accessibility.

Finally, it would generate employment to the local people during and after the construction phase.

4.4.3. Site Features

The site for the proposed International Airport features a natural landscape. The immediate surroundings of the site consist of residential and commercial developments. There is a forested vegetation belt on the southern, northern and eastern part of the site. This creates a buffer from the commercial activities and residential land use around the site.

4.5. DESIGN BRIEF

4.5.1. Design and Client Brief

The Proposed International Airport is the project of Anambra State Government of Nigeria, although the initiative is private-sector driven, the project will be developed through a partnership between the Anambra State Government, Orient Petroleum Resources and Elite International Investments. Elite International Investments will provide all funds under a build, operate, manage and transfer agreement. Anambra Airport City Infrastructure Limited allocated a 75% equity stake to Elite International Investments, 20% to Orient Petroleum Resources Limited and 5% to the State Government.

The government believes that transformation would maximize the contribution of the industry to the socio-economic development of Nigeria through increased trade.

The client intends to have a new facility at the most effective cost, which shall become a standard for newer class of facilities that would follow this in the nearest future.

4.5.1.1. Design Brief

The essential criteria for which the design shall be satisfactory is the creation of a facility that is aimed at bringing together airport planning, urban and regional planning, and business-site planning, to create a new urban form that is highly competitive, attractive, and sustainable and most importantly, Energy-efficient.

It is a business planning model aimed to bring clusters of travel-related businesses like tourism, hospitality, shopping, fashion and others together within an airport environment. The building so designed shall be sustainable and innovative in the use of material and construction method.

4.6. Design Concept and Evolution

After the approval of my dissertation project, I began collecting, researching and evaluating materials, that would enhance the design goals to meet not only passengers but also airport staff needs and expectations, and the functional requirements of an airport.

That criteria helped develop preliminary concepts which met the design goals.

Further development of conceptual designs and possible solutions through sketches and diagrams was carried out and evaluated based on the design criteria. I reported my progress to my Supervisor as my development evolved.

Initial Concept

The first concept I had was the linear configuration (Figure below). The advantage of this concept is that it is the simplest and most straight forward, and it allows the relationship between curbside and aircraft. Thus, passengers who are boarding aircraft have a very short walking distance from check-in to boarding gates. But this concept would not permit the number of gates intended for

this design within the given site. Then, I started to develop and evaluate variations of linear terminals which are used in most existing airport terminals

Figure 53: Linear Terminal concept

Source: author

Concept Evolution

After evaluating the existing various terminal types, I discovered that the pier configuration (Figure Below) permitted more compact arrangements of aircrafts along the pier, which is more efficient and would encourage the number of gates being proposed for the design.

Figure 54: Pier Terminal concept

Source: author

Final Concept

After experimenting with several variations, I came up with the concept of ‘fusing’ the linear and pier configurations together. (Figure below). In a bid to achieve a reasonable number of boarding gates for the airport.

Figure 55: Linear + Pier Terminal concept

Source: author

The major circulation problem in a terminal building is how to properly and adequately separate arrivals and departure and the necessity of the avoidance of congestion and confusion of multi-directional traffic especially in busy airports. Therefore, a one level separation – processing, baggage and passenger handling for departure and arrival at apron level, will not be used as it would be insufficient. This has led to the use of the ‘**VERTICAL DISTRIBUTION CONCEPT**’ in which arrivals are usually located on the apron level with departure on the floor above.

Figure 56: Vertical Distribution concept

Source: author

4.7. SPACE PROGRAMMING

Table 20: Space programming for Proposed Umuleri international airport design

	TERMINAL SPACES	FLOOR AREA PER PEAK HOUR RATE PASSENGER (M ²)	TOTAL FLOOR AREA (M ²)
	DEPARTURE:		
A	Check- In Facilities	1.20m ²	
	-Ticketing counter and office		
	-Check- in Counter		
	-Information Desk		
	-Concessions		
	-Telephone booth		
	-Security posts		
B	Baggage Sorting (Check-In Area)		
	-Sorting Lines and Conveyors		
	-Offices		
	-Concessions		

	-Security posts		
	-Changing Rooms		
	-Storage Rooms		
	-Conviniences		
C	Concourse areas		
	-Banks		
	-Postal Services Offices		
	-Concessions		
	-Security posts		
	-Conviniences		
D	Immigration		
	-Security Search counters		
	-Detention rooms		
	-Immigration Offices		
	-Interview rooms		
	-Security Officers' room		
	-Secure Store		
	-Conviniences		
E	Customs		
	-Security Search counters		
	-Detention rooms		
	-Offices		

	-Secure Store		
	-Conviniences		
F	Departure Lounge		
	-Waiting area		
	-Duty Free Shops		
	-Eating area		
	-Book Stalls		
	-Security posts		
G	V.I.P/ C.I.P Lounge		
	-Waiting area		
	-Duty Free Shops		
	-Eating area		
	-Book Stalls		
	-Security posts		
	-Press and Interview Rooms		
	-Communications facilities		
	-Conviniences		
H	Food Courts		
	-Buffet/ Bar		
	-Grill/ Coffee shops		
	-Restaurants		
I	Concourse areas		

	-Banks		
	-Postal Services Offices		
	-Concessions		
	-Security posts		
	-Conviniences		
J	Health Control area		
	-Examination Room		
	-Vaccination/Quarantine Room		
	-Doctor's Room		
	-Nurse's Room		
	-X-ray Room		
	-Staff amenities		
	-Conviniences		
K	Immigration		
	-Same as 'D'Above		
L	Customs		
	-Customs Search Desks		
	-Duty Rooms		
	-Interview Room		
	-Goods Search room		
	-Lock- up/ Cash Office		
	-General Office		

	-Customs enquiry Office		
	-Conviniences		
M	Baggage Reclaim Area		
	-Waiting area		
	-Seating		
	-Baggage Retrival Belt		
	AIRLINES:		
N	Airline Offices		
	-Executive Offices		
	-General Offices		
	-Storage Room		
	-Lost Goods Office		
	-Conviniences		
O	Airline Lounge		
	-Main Lounge/ Library		
	-Restaurant/ Cafeteria		
	-Flight Room		
	-Changing Room		
	-Conviniences		
	AIRPORT:		
P	Airport Offices		
	-Manager's office		

	-Executive Offices		
	-Information and Flight Office		
	-Storage Room		
	-Conviniences		
Q	Weather/Air Traffic Bureau		
	-Executive Offices		
	-General Offices		
	-Workshops/ Library		
	-Conviniences		
R	Control Tower		
	-Control Cabin		
	-Equipment Store		
	-Equipment Room		
	-Conviniences		

Source: The Author

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. SUMMARY

An effective airport master plan will include land use, transportation, and environmental planning, along with urban design and related elements found in traditional city and regional plans.

In this research, attempt has been made to study the various aspects of energy efficiency and sustainability on airport design, impact on business operations and provide practicable suggestions for implementation. While there is no limitation for innovation and technology, value addition in every little form is a true trend setter for sustainability and progress on a long term basis for airport terminal designs.

But, to effectively achieve the energy efficient airport terminal and sustainable airport complex envisioned, it must be more comprehensive, strategic, and investment-based.

5.2. CONCLUSION

This work examined the essential requirements for the design and development of an Energy efficient airport concept. The cases examined suggest that the success of energy efficient and sustainable airport is borne out of a range of factors, which have varying degree of influence in each location:

- Sustainable airport to reduce the carbon emission of the city and act as major example towards a green and sustainable city.

- A joined-up development partnership combining national and municipal governments and private sector backing
- Growth in the associated airport hub

The benefits of airport cities are not just economic. The case studies suggest that airports are major drivers towards the sustainability goals of any given city and it enhances the wellbeing of the users, and travelers.

5.3. RECOMMENDATION

In all the cases examined locally, the airport facilities are purpose built, but does not comply with the minimum standard required for the energy efficient and sustainable concept in terms of planning, space allocation and facility operation.

To this end some recommendations are put forth to aid the future design of an energy efficient and sustainable airport:

1. As there is a dearth of research information on the energy efficient design concept in sub-Saharan Africa and Nigeria, firms willing to embark on the design of such facility, cannot rely only on secondary information from data books, but must proceed to conduct empirical research and physical study of the requirements for this new urban form.
2. An integrated design method is most appropriate so that client, passengers, the design team and contractors are engaged early enough. This would eventually snowball into a smooth design process and enhance good communication between parties to the project.
3. Ensure successful integration of building function and form into the sustainable site context

4. Both architectural and urban design considerations for urban renewal, city planning must comply with standards.

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